

**HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT AND SERVICE DELIVERY IN
BENADIR AND ADAN ABDULLE HOSPITALS IN MOGADISHU,
SOMALIA.**

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**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE SCHOOL OF
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IN HEALTHCARE MANAGEMENT OF HOPE UNIVERSITY, MOGADISHU -
SOMALIA IN PARTNERSHIP WITH GATES AFRICA EDUCATIONAL TRUST,
KENYA**

FEBRUARY 2025

DECLARATION

I declare that this thesis is my original work and has never been submitted to any other university or institution of higher learning for any academic award. Data derived from other authors was duly acknowledged.

21th November, 2024

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APPROVAL

I certify this thesis satisfies the partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of doctoral of philosophy in Healthcare Administration **OF HOPE UNIVERSITY, MOGADISHU - SOMALIA IN PARTNERSHIP WITH GATES AFRICA EDUCATIONAL TRUST, NAIROBI/KISUMU - KENYA**

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DEDICATION

First I would like to lovingly dedicate this thesis to my dear **Mom Fatima Dahir Alasow**, and my wife **Anisa Muse Ibrahim** who made extraordinary efforts for me toward building my future and capacity to reach my doctoral degree level.

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TABLE CONTENTS

DECLARATION	I
APPROVAL	II
DEDICATION	III
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT	IV
LIST OF TABLES	X
LIST OF FIGURES	XII
ABBREVIATION	XIII
ABSTRACT.....	XIV

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION	1
1.0.Introduction to the study	1
1.1. Background of the study	1
1.2. Statement of Problem.....	5
1.3. The objective of the study.....	6
1.3.1. General objective of the study	6
1.3.2. Specific objective	7
1.4. Research Questions	7
1.5 Scope of the Study	8
1.5.1 Content Scope.....	8
1.5.2 Geographical Scope	8
1.5.3 Time scope.....	9
1.6 Significance of study.....	9
1.7 Proposed Thesis Structure.....	11
1.8 Definitional terms	11

1.10. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK	13
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CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW	16
2.0 Introduction.....	16
2.1. Theoretical Underpinning in Healthcare Management.....	16
2.1.1. Operations management theory	16
2.1.2. Participatory leadership in health	17
2.1.3. Contingency Theory in healthcare management	18
2.1.4. System thinking in healthcare management	18
2.2. Capacity of healthcare.....	35
2.2.1. Surge capacity of Healthcare.....	36
2.2.4. Current Somali healthcare capacity	40
2.3. Health Leadership and management.....	41
2.3.1. Effective leadership in health service	42
2.4. Evaluation of Healthcare Financial System.....	49
2.4. Influence of workforce competence (Human resource).....	51
2.4.1. Workforce Competence in Healthcare	53
2.5. Health service availability, structure and quality.....	58
2.5.2. Quality healthcare delivery.....	59
2.6. Research Gaps.....	60
2.7. Summary.....	61

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY	66
3.1. Introduction.....	66
3.2 Research Design.....	66

3.3	Study Population.....	67
3.4	Determination of the Sample size.....	67
3.5	Sampling techniques and procedure	68
3.6	Data Collection Methods	69
3.7	Data collection instruments.....	69
3.8	Validity and reliability	69
3.8.1.	Validity	69
3.8.2.	Reliability.....	71
3.9	Procedure of Data Collection.....	72
3.10	Data Analysis	73
3.11	Measurements of variables	73

CHAPTER FOUR

	DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION	74
4.0.	Introduction.....	74
4.1.	Demographic information.....	74
4.2.	Impacts of capacity of Hospital on health services Delivery.....	76
4.3.	Impacts of Leadership of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery	82
4.4.	Impacts of Financial Management of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery	86
4.5.	Impacts of Workforce Competencies of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery	93
4.6.	Key Informants Interview	102
4.6.1.	Key Informants Interviews—Capacity of Hospitals	102
4.6.2.	Key Informants - Interviews of Leaderships in Hospitals.....	103
4.6.3.	Key informants - Interview of Financial Management in Hospitals	104
4.6.4.	Key informants: Interviews of Workforces competence in Hospitals.....	108
4.7.	Hypothesis testing.....	113

4.7.1. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Capacities of both Hospitals and their significance value	113
4.7.2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Health Services Delivery	117
4.7.4. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of Financial Management Practices	125
4.7.5. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of Workforce Competence	129
4.8. Conclusion of Hypothesis Testing	135
4.9. Correlation of study	137
4.9.1. Correlation of hospital Medical Equipment, Facilities and services	137
4.9.2. Correlations between various hospital equipment and facilities with different aspects of hospital performance.	140
4.9.4. Correlation between various financial management practices and overall hospital financial health	148
4.9.5. Correlation between financial management practices and their impact on hospital operations and patient outcomes.....	151
4.9.6. Correlation between hospital and the competencies of medical staff	155
4.9.7. Correlation between various workforce competencies and their impact on hospital performance	158
4.10. Line graphs.....	162
4.10. 1. Charts of Impacts of Hospital Capacity on Health Services.....	162
4.10.2. Charts of Impacts of Hospital Leadership on Health Services	165
4.10.3. Charts of Impacts of Hospital's financial management on Health services delivered	170
4.10.4. Charts of Impacts of Hospital's Workforce competences on Health services delivered.	175
4.11. Discussion	180

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS	190
5.1. Introduction.....	190
5.2. Findings of study.....	190
5.2.1. Capacity of Hospitals.....	190

5.2.2. Leadership Evaluation	192
5.2.3. Financial Management Practices	193
5.2.4. Workforce Competencies	194
5.3. Conclusion	195
5.4. Recommendations.....	197
5.5. Recommendation future research	199
References.....	202
Appendix I. Work plan of PhD thesis.....	214
Appendix II. Budget of PhD thesis.....	215

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1 Sampling Procedure	68
Table 2 3.2. Pilot study their percentage and acceptance (Article Published).....	70
Table 3 3.3. Reliability test.....	72
Table 4.4 Hospitals	74
Table 4-5 Sex, Age and Marital status.....	75
Table 4-6. Education and Occupation.....	75
Table 7 4.4. Hospital capacity.....	76
Table 8 4.5. Health worker’s availability.....	77
Table 9 4.6. Capacity of Health Services Delivery.....	78
Table 10 4.7. Overall Impact Hospital capacity on Health Services	79
Table 11 4.8. Leadership evaluation	82
Table 12 4.9 Overall Impact of Leadership on Health Services	84
Table 13 4.10. Financial Management Practices	86
Table 14 4.11. Impact Financial Management on Health Services Delivery	88
Table 15 4.12. Overall Impact of Financial Management on Health services.....	91
Table 16 4.13. Workforce Competencies	93
Table 17 4.14. Impact on workforce competence on Health Services Delivery.....	97
Table 18 4.15. Overall impacts of Workforce competence on health	100
Table 19 4.16 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Availability of Medical Equipment, Facilities and services.....	113
Table 20 4.17. Health Services Delivery for Hospitals	117
Table 21 4.18. Leadership Evaluation of Hospitals.....	120
Table 22 4.19. ANOVA of Financial Management Practices of Hospitals.....	125
Table 23 4.20. Workforce Competence for Hospitals	129
Table 24 4.21. Correlation of hospital Medical Equipment, Facilities and services	137
Table 25 4.22. Hospital equipment and facilities with different aspects of hospital performance	140
Table 26 4.23. Pearson correlation coefficients between various leadership characteristics.	144
Table 27 4.24. Correlation between various financial management practices and overall hospital financial health.....	148

Table 28 4.25. Correlation between financial management practices and their impact on hospital operations and patient outcomes	151
Table 29 4.26. Correlation between hospital and the competencies of medical staff.....	155
Table 30 4.27. Correlation between various workforce competencies and their impact on hospital performance	158

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 0.1.1 Map of both Hospitals Benadir and Aden Abdulla Hospital in Wadajir district, Mogadishu, Somalia	9
Figure 1.0.2 Conceptual framework of Healthcare management and service delivery in the health sectors	13
Figure 2.0.1. Spending healthcare 2015-2017, (Warsame, 2020)	50
Figure 3.0.1 Map of Wadajir district Mogadishu, Somalia.	67
Figure 0.1	162
Figure 0.2	162
Figure 0.3	163
Figure 0.4	163
Figure 0.5	164
Figure 0.6	165
Figure 0.7	165
Figure 0.8	166
Figure 0.9	166
Figure 0.10	167
Figure 0.11	170
Figure 0.12	171
Figure 0.13	171
Figure 0.14	172
Figure 0.15	172
Figure 0.16	175
Figure 0.17	176
Figure 0.18	176
Figure 0.19	177
Figure 0.20	177

ABBREVIATION

WHO – WORLD HEALTH ORGANIZATION

KM - Knowledge Management

ICRC - International Committee of the Red Cross

SOS - Save Our Selves

MOH - Ministry of Health

UNHCR - United Nations High Commission for Refugees

RBV - Resource-Based View

VRIN - Value, Rarity, Imitability and Non-substitution

PE/E - Pre-eclampsia and Eclampsia

USD - United State Dollar

UHC - Universal Health Coverage

PHC - Primary Health Care

CHWs - Community Health Workers

NGOs, - Non- Governmental Organization

SPSS – Statistical Package for Social Science

ABSTRACT

This study aims at identifying the effects of healthcare management on services delivery in two health facilities in Mogadishu-Somalia more specifically Benadir and Aden Abdulla Hospitals. In order to achieve its objectives, the study focuses on different aspects of health care management such as, capacity size, leadership, financial management and workforce competencies. This study aims at determining the important factors that affect the quality of health care services in these hospitals as well as how management practices can be enhanced to enhance delivery of quality health care services. The research design used in this study was both Quantitative and Qualitative research with a sample size of 210 sampled questionnaires and 26 key informants interviewed and the study area included two Hospitals namely Benadir and Aden Abdulla Hospital in Wadajir District. The study conducted the pilot study and the reliability test. From the study, it is clear that organizational leadership plays a significant role in increasing the quality of service delivery, motivation of employees and patient satisfaction. Transformational leadership is linked with positive healthcare results which promote a healthy culture focused on innovation and teamwork of all the healthcare workers. On the other hand, the following leadership styles are counterproductive, and they result in staff burnout, low job satisfaction, and poor patient care. These findings underscore the importance of leaders in hospitals to embrace open and collaborative leadership in order to manage a healthcare system that is increasingly complicated. The study also looks at the weaknesses of the Somali healthcare system and the problems associated with it for instance, scarcity of resources, poor infrastructural development, and few health care workers. These challenges are further exacerbated by the poor funding that has been put towards healthcare meaning that the hospitals are unable to meet the basic needs of their patients. Therefore, the study has the following recommendations that would help to enhance healthcare management practices in Somalia. These are; improving leadership training, improving financial management, and increasing investments in the health care facilities and personnel. Thus, the above critical areas can be considered as essential for the improvement of the Somali healthcare system and increased quality of patient care as well as accessibility of health services for the population.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.0.Introduction to the study

The healthcare system management and service delivery in the health sector is an important part of each community's health and life. It will be a limitation of health distribution and equality, if we lack leadership and management capacity, particularly at working conditions of both the public and private health centers. Somalia specifically, had more challenges above mentioned, like poor communication, long time waiting, wrong medications, Inefficient and inaccurate pharmaceutical quality checkup and inadequate patient identification.

This researcher starts with this introduction chapter explaining the background of the study, statement of the problem, objectives of the study, scope of the study, significance of the study, definition of key terms, and the conceptual framework.

1.1. Background of the study

There is inadequate access to healthcare by the world population. According to World Bank and WHO, it was estimated that half of the world's population can't gain access to health services (Yoshizu, 2017), and stated that 800 million people of the world population, in general, spent at least 10 percent of their household budgets on health expenses (World Health Organization & World Bank, 2021). Hao et al., (2020) argue that life expectancy has a critical role to be an indicator of the availability of healthcare services and management systems used. The Significant health gains conveyed improvements in worldwide service coverage over the last two decades. As mentioned by the World health organization the Global average life expectancy

at birth was increased from 66.8 years in 2000 to 73.3 years in 2019 (World Health Organization & World Bank, 2021).

The management has a matter in healthcare services, today there was inadequate focus on management in global health services is highly challenging given the amounts of financial in health and human resources by strengthening mediations and the complexity of clinical operations across settings (Yeager & Bertrand, 2016).

These health services are primarily financed from government taxation and 83.5% of total health expenditure in the UK came from public sources in 2013 (Cylus et al., 2015). Also, the Life expectancy increased gradually across the UK, but health inequalities have proved strongly resistant to improvement and they face challenges going forward, including challenges of coping with the needs of an aging population, managing populations with poor health behaviors and related chronic conditions, challenges of meeting patient expectations of access to the latest available therapy and technologies and adopt a system that has limited resources (expand workforce and infrastructural) (Cylus et al., 2015). In Asia, there are high maternal and neonatal mortality rates in Asian countries like Pakistan and also are associated with low rates of institutional deliveries (Jafree et al., 2021) and in China, a large percentage of the population could not afford the healthcare services they needed. China in 2003 outbreak has highlighted the importance of getting sufficient health for human development, and the China government began to recognize the contribution of the health system to overall social and economic development (Wang et al., 2019).

African countries between 2000 and 2019, had the fastest growth in both measures with an increase of 22 index points from 53 to 64 age gain or increase of 11.7 years of life expectancy (World Health Organization & World Bank, 2021). Furthermore, African countries

have weaknesses in their health system, the challenging measures reducing the burden of diseases. The main issues facing healthcare are staffing shortages, budgetary difficulties, and the fragmentation of health services. inadequate information management, faulty communication technologies, and risk to patient care (Malakoane et al., 2020). In Ghana, researchers found the existence of significant barriers affecting the quality and appropriateness of health services at maternal and neonatal in the rural communities and the Nadowli District Hospital in Ghana (Sumankuuro et al., 2018).

Over the past six years, Somalia's health system has made some improvement, but there have been major obstacles to both providing health services and facilitating access to them (Gele, 2020). As a result, around 3.2 million women and men in Somalia are in need of emergency health services (Yoshizu, 2017). Healthcare service providers in Somalia are mostly private sectors of hospitals and clinics, there are public hospitals and primary healthcare centers managed by government and aid agencies. The distribution of health facilities in Somalia is located the majority in the capital Mogadishu and greater cities of the province; some local states like Somaliland and Puntland have a small number of health facilities located outside of urban areas, but it is limited (Warsame, 2016). The United Nations High Commission for Refugees (UNHCR) report (2020) revealed that there were a total of 61 hospitals in Somalia, and 11 of these were public facilities, while others are private (Finnish Immigration Service & European Union, 2020).

In addition, Somalia's infant mortality rate increased to 65.399 deaths per 1000 live births in 2021 compared to 2019, which registered infant mortality of 36.9 deaths per 1,000 live births, but in 2020, the mortality was higher with 65.66 deaths per 1000 live births that means there was a 1.9% infant mortality decline (World data, 2021). It should be noted that the high

infant mortality is related to low utilization of maternal and child health services, and low distribution of primary healthcare in all the countries. The factors causing low utilization of existing maternal and child health services are multiple factors like Low socio-economic, poor knowledge, lack of decision-making power of women, etc. (Mohamed et al., 2021).

Interesting to know, since 2008 the healthcare sector has been growing in Somalia with more healthcare providers emerging in the country. It is argued the Ministry of Health (MOH) has been responsible for structuring the health system in the country. The first structure of MOH was at the independent time (1960), the six departments had the Ministry of Health (MOH) in Somalia, they are planning and training, personnel, prevention services, curative services, finance and administration, and procurement and medical supplies. But after the collapse of the central government of Somalia in 1990, all hospitals were looted, destroyed, and occupied by internally displaced people. The only hospitals saved by its staff were Madina Hospital and Keysaney Hospital, which was later reformed by the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC).

Before 1990, Mogadishu had four main hospitals, including Benadir Hospital, Digfer Teaching Hospital; Military Hospital; and the Madina Police Hospital. There were also tuberculosis patients treated and isolated in Lazareti in north Mogadishu and De Martini hospital in the south, but in North of Mogadishu only SOS hospital (Abbreviated Save Our Selves), also many other small clinics existed. They had different limited resources and management problems during the civil war.

However, the healthcare sector faces many challenges inside like delivering safe, cost-effective, high-value healthcare and patient satisfaction. Somalia experienced more challenges such as poor communication, waiting for long hours, wrong medications, inefficient and

inaccurate pharmaceutical quality checkups, and inadequate patient identification. Despite the opening of the public hospital like Keysaney, Benadir, and de Martine hospital free of charge to all people, the goal of universal access to healthcare is still never attained and the health indicators for Somalia communities is still low.

1.2. Statement of Problem

Access to healthcare is one of the rights of the United Nations, every nation must reach a goal of giving their citizens free health service. In Somalia, the establishment of health care services was not the easy way, but private healthcare organizations are investor-owned with profit-seeking, but exceptional only some charitable organizations and governmental agencies delivered health services as public distribution of any individual for free. The management of the health system and service delivery is an important part of each community's health and life. Health management concerns the management of the health workforce and resources, as well as the process of implementation, which is an important part of the effectiveness, efficiency, and quality of the health care delivery system (Matey, 2016).

The health institutions have been delayed by inadequate leadership and management, variation of quality care, and inefficiencies (Figuroa, et al., 2019). In Somalia, there's a need to invest in human capital development, including training health professionals in management and information systems (Warsame, 2020). The healthcare sector faces many challenges inside like delivering safe, cost-effective, high-value healthcare and patient satisfaction (Hoque et al., 2017).

Somalia faces significant health challenges due to decades of civil war and instability. Between 26% and 70% of its 15 million people live in poverty, and approximately 2.6 million are internally displaced. The health system struggles with fragmentation, lacks unified governance, and provides limited access to healthcare services (WHO, 2020 & Xirsi, 2024).

Despite these obstacles, the country is committed to strengthening health and social development. Initiatives like the Somali Universal Health Coverage (UHC) Roadmap aim to improve health outcomes by emphasizing primary healthcare as a key approach (WHO, 2020).

There are many health indicators for Somalia, including: Life expectancy at birth: 56 years, Fertility rate: 6.9 children per woman, Immunization rate: only 11% of children are fully immunized. Poor health outcomes in Somalia are underlined by weak health service delivery (Humdata, 2024 World Bank, 2021). The World Health Organization (2015) found that the health indicators in Somalia are among the lowest in the world. It stresses that the EPI (Expand Program immunization) coverage rate for measles is 46% nationwide and even lower in hard-to-reach areas (World Health Organization, 2015). The health system management in Somalia persists weakly, poorly resourced, and inequitably distributed. Health expenditure costs remain very low and there is a serious shortage of health workers. As a result, around 3.2 million women and men in Somalia are in need of emergency health services (World Health Organization, 2017). It is therefore the desire of the researcher to assess the health management system in relation to healthcare delivery in case study Benadir Hospital and Adan Abdulla Hospital in Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.3. The objectives of the study

The study's objectives are divided into two sub-titles: General Objectives, which outline the study's full aim, and Specific Objectives, which include bullets of sub-indicators.

1.3.1. General objective of the study

The general objective of the study was to examine the impacts of Healthcare management on Service delivery in the health sector in Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.3.2. Specific objectives

The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. To examine the impacts Capacity of healthcare Management on Health service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia.
- ii. To analyze the impacts Leadership practices on service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia.
- iii. To evaluate the impacts Financial Management on service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia.
- iv. To examine the impacts workforce competence on service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia.

1.4. Research Questions

- i. How Does the Capacity of Healthcare Management Impacts Service Delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia?
- ii. How do Leadership Management Practices Impacts on Service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia?
- iii. How does Health Finance Management impact service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia?
- iv. How does Workforce Competence Management Impacts on service delivery in Benadir and Aden Abdulle Hospital Mogadishu, Somalia?

1.5 Scope of the Study

1.5.1 Content Scope

The study focused on examining the Healthcare management system and health service delivery in the health sector in Mogadishu, Somalia. The study's four key specific objectives were also addressed, including the impact of capacity healthcare, leadership, health financing, and workforce competency management on service delivery in Mogadishu's health sector. Because we want to understand the impact of management techniques on service delivery in two hospitals. The study compared the two hospitals and determined how they differ from one another.

1.5.2 Geographical Scope

The study was conducted in selected two hospitals and was Benadir and Aden Abdulla hospital both located in Wadajir district Mogadishu, Somalia. The Benadir Hospital is located in Mogadishu, Somalia, at 2.0346° N and 45.2993° E, close to the intersection of KM 6 (Benadir Junction) and Maka al-mukarama street Wadajir District. Aden Abdulla Hospital is situated at KM 5 (Lamiyaraha Bula Hubey), in the Wadajir District of Mogadishu, Somalia, at latitude 2.0299926 and longitude 45.3047543.

Figure 0.1.1 Map of both Hospitals Benadir and Aden Abdulla Hospital in Wadajir district, Mogadishu, Somalia

1.5.3 Time scope

The study was last a minimum of five years and a maximum of ten years. The proposal writing phase began in January 2022 and ended in March 2024. Data collection, analysis, and reporting will take place between April to November 2024. This time, the researcher plans to complete this Ph.D. study in compliance with Kampala University's regulations.

1.6 Significance of study

The study would have a crucial on health policymakers, managers of healthcare organizations, academic institutions, and the general public community.

Health Policy Makers

In Somalia, the Ministry of Health and international agencies have experts of health policymakers, so the findings and results of this study would provide helpful comprehensions

and a more reliable guide concerning the relationship between healthcare management and quality health service delivery for checking health workers' performance. It could also be a gauge for measuring partially their relevant policy goals and objectives on healthcare service delivery in Somalia.

Managers of health organization

The findings and results of this study would provide a more consistent scientific measure and viewpoint to the managers of a healthcare organization, and determine the impact of effective management practices on the output of health services. This would provide practical support for management to use and formulate strategic decisions in several critical areas of their operations.

This study would significant to help managers, especially medical doctors who are made to chief (head) hospitals to create improve healthcare delivery. It would allow them to design the way they work as managers and as such lead the institutions in a well-organized way to deliver service effectively and reliably. It would enable them to learn methodically from their own experience in management. It would help to pay thoughtful and closer attention not only to the clinical skill but also the managerial skill of the doctors as the efficient management of the healthcare organization and this vital to the delivery of quality healthcare in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Academia

The findings of this study might to increase the existing collection of knowledge in the learning environment. This study also would serve as a scholarly article for review by another

researcher to make in further studies. It would be used as a material of reference by other scholars who would conducting another study into a similar topic in the future.

General public

The finding of this study would be useful to the community in general because if the quality of health care service delivery is increased and management understand the impact affecting the health management, this may solve any shortcoming issue related to both management and services delivered by the health institutions, the community, and client of that hospital get satisfaction and safety.

1.7 Thesis Structure

The thesis is comprised of five chapters. Three of these chapters (Chapters one to three) are written in the form of a Proposal, each of which builds upon the prediction of future implementation of action about this study. After that, the researcher might prepare the questionnaire based on the objective and the next step is chapter four would prepare after data collection and analysis, and the interpretation of data. Finally, the researcher might make reporting of Chapter Five which is Findings, conclusion, and recommendation.

1.8 Define of key terms

It is influential to reflect on sighting the relevant disciplines in which the present research topic is rooted. In this section, research would like to focus on a comprehensive definition of the concept management (M), health management, healthcare service delivery (HSD), effective health service delivery, and health system, this is a knowledge-based view and a brief outline of the theoretical literature.

Definition of management

The term management has been defined by many scholars, normally as described as a process of organizing, controlling, coordinating, and incorporating human and other resources to achieve the specific objectives of an organization. Dunn, R. in 2010, define the word management in for health “purposes is the process of getting things done through and with people by directing and motivating the efforts of individuals toward common objectives.” (Dunn, 2010)

Primary healthcare

Primary healthcare is defined primary healthcare as “Essential health care based on practical, scientifically sound and socially acceptable methods and technology made universally accessible to individuals and families in the community through their full participation and at a cost that the community and country can afford to maintain at every stage of their development in the spirit of self-reliance and self-determination” (World Health Organization, 2013).

Health service

Health services refer to any service (i.e. not limited to medical or clinical services) aimed at contributing to improved health or to the diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation of individuals (World Health Organization, 2011). World Health Organization, Hirshon, et al. (2013). Also defined Health services are "aimed at contributing to improved health or to the diagnosis, treatment, and rehabilitation of sick people". While the term Health systems World health Organization, Hirshon, et al. (2013) “health system includes all organizations, institutions and resources "whose primary purpose is to promote, restore and/or maintain health" (Hirshon et al., 2013)

Health services delivery

Health services delivery processes are defined as the unique processes inherent to the health services delivery function that contribute to the performance of health services delivery. These processes include: selecting services, designing care, organizing providers, managing services, and improving performance (Tello & Barbazza, 2015).

1.9. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Figure 0.2 Conceptual framework of Healthcare management and service delivery in the health sectors

Healthcare capacity play a crucial role in providing effective healthcare to patients. The capacity of healthcare facilities, such as hospitals and clinics, is essential for providing quality care. So that healthcare capacity can affect service delivery in terms of safety, quality, and satisfaction. Effective **healthcare leadership** encourages medical workers to contribute to the success of medicine, patient care, and healthcare procedures. Healthcare leadership can also influence service delivery in terms of safety, quality, and satisfaction. **Healthcare finance** is the use of financial resources to meet collective health needs, including the delivery and accessibility of primary health care. In South Central Somalia, the cost of medical care is not set, and most public health services are provided for free. So those kinds of financial methods, payments, and resources can also influence the service delivery in terms of safety, quality, and satisfaction. **Health workforce competencies** are the knowledge, skills, and abilities required to excel in the healthcare industry. Access to high-quality essential healthcare services is necessary for achieving universal health coverage. The workforce competencies can also affect service delivery in terms of safety, quality, and satisfaction (World Health Organization, 2018).

Effective **service delivery** is critical for patient safety and satisfaction. So that dependent variable, which is effective in health service delivery, is Essential point to all healthcare management. **Effective health services delivery** is crucial for ensuring that people receive the care they need. (World Health Organization, 2017). Health care staff, health care facilities, medicines, devices, and other technologies, information systems, and financing are the five important core elements required to provide quality health care services. In order to ensure that quality is incorporated into the foundations of systems, governments, policymakers, health system executives, patients, and physicians should collaborate (World Health Organization, 2018).

Mediating Variable is Regulatory bodies, Regulatory bodies in health and social care often license or approve providers while also directly regulating care structures and procedures through inspection, feedback, or fines (Dunbar, Keyes, & Browne, 2023). Healthcare regulators play an important role in supervising and enforcing standards, safety, and quality in the healthcare industry. In Somalia, they can be the private sector, which was the primary player in healthcare, international donors, who were the second-largest role, and the government.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

In this Section, literature is review according to the research questions used in the study. A literature review is a summary of the previously published works on a specific topic. The literature review is searching existing knowledge about capacity and characteristics of healthcare facilities, health management and its impact on healthcare service delivery, in general, and more concise to point out the case study area of hospitals in Mogadishu, Benadir region in Somalia. The researcher collected various books, journals, articles, and internet data helped the researcher to extract information for this research. The researcher defined characteristics of the Somali healthcare system, the relationship between health management and healthcare service delivery. The concepts of health care management for the study are also drawn.

2.1. Theoretical Underpinning in Healthcare Management

2.1.1. Operations management theory

Healthcare management is a complex and multifaceted field that requires a solid understanding of various theoretical frameworks to guide decision-making, improve organizational performance, and enhance patient outcomes. One essential theoretical underpinning in healthcare management is the concept of operations management, which focuses on the efficient and effective delivery of healthcare services (Butler et al., 1996).

Operations management in healthcare encompasses a wide range of functions, including capacity planning, workflow optimization, staffing management, logistics and supply chain, and inventory control (Efiok & Rawlings, 2022). The application of operations management decision-making techniques has been shown to have a positive impact on the financial

performance of healthcare organizations, particularly in the small business environment and non-manufacturing sectors.

The unique characteristics of healthcare, such as the involvement of multiple stakeholders, uncertainty in demand, and the critical nature of services provided, present unique challenges in the application of operations management principles. To address these challenges, healthcare organizations must develop a robust knowledge management (KM) infrastructure, which can enhance the organization's operational capabilities and lead to improved cost, quality, flexibility, and delivery.

2.1.2. Participatory leadership in health

Participatory leadership is another important theoretical framework in healthcare management, which emphasizes the involvement of various stakeholders, including healthcare professionals, patients, and the local community, in the decision-making process.

Participatory leadership in health is a leadership style that involves collaboration, shared decision-making, and empowerment of all team members in the healthcare setting. This approach has been increasingly recognized as a valuable strategy for building strong relationships, improving team performance, and ultimately enhancing patient outcomes.

In a study published in the *International Journal of Health Policy and Management*, researchers found that participatory leadership in healthcare settings can result in higher job satisfaction among employees, increased quality of care for patients, and improved overall organizational performance (Aarons et al., 2018). This demonstrates the significant impact that participatory leadership can have on both the workforce and patient care.

Another study by Gifford and Zammuto (2018) highlighted the importance of fostering a culture of participation and collaboration within healthcare organizations. The researchers found that organizations that embrace participatory leadership practices are more likely to have open communication, trust among team members, and a more positive work environment. This in turn can lead to better patient outcomes and overall satisfaction with healthcare services.

2.1.3. Contingency Theory in healthcare management

Contingency theory plays a crucial role in healthcare management by emphasizing the importance of considering situational factors when designing quality approaches in healthcare organizations (Pang, Jin, & Cameron, 2023). This theory, rooted in the understanding that the relationship between variables is influenced by a third variable, has been extensively applied in various disciplines, including healthcare management (DeFulio, 2023). In the context of healthcare, contingency management, an intervention based on operant principles, has shown significant effectiveness in treating substance use disorders, particularly opioid use disorder (Marmat, & Jain, 2020 & Turkulainen, 2022). By recognizing the complexity of healthcare delivery organizations as complex adaptive systems, contingency theory provides a framework to tailor quality management approaches to different healthcare settings, ultimately enhancing the effectiveness of quality improvement strategies in hospitals (Roll, McPherson, & McDonell, 2021).

2.1.4. System thinking in healthcare management

Systems Thinking Theory plays a crucial role in healthcare management by providing a comprehensive understanding of system dynamics, root causes identification, and key issue selection for refined system design and interventions (Chiu, & Fong, 2022). By applying systems thinking modelling, healthcare organizations can nurture an innovative culture, accelerate

innovation processes, and improve results through causal loop diagrams and system dynamics methodology (Linnéusson, Et al., 2022) This approach not only enhances the dynamic understanding of developing an innovation system in practice but also supports individual and organizational learning, emphasizing the need for perseverance in fostering an innovative culture within healthcare settings. Furthermore, systems thinking offers a valuable tool for global health practitioners, guiding them in addressing various health topics such as maternal and child health, infectious diseases, healthcare decentralization, quality improvement, and more, to strengthen health systems and improve overall healthcare delivery (Vallières, Mannan, Larkan, & Kodate, 2023). Additionally, utilizing system dynamics for resource planning in healthcare institutions aids decision-makers in effectively managing human talent to provide quality services (Uribe-Gómez, 2021)

2.1.5. The Donabedian Model: Overview

The Donabedian Model is a theory framework which was propounded by Avedis Donabedian in 1966 in order to offer a systematic way of assessing quality of health care. This model has been widely adopted in healthcare research and practice to assess the performance of healthcare systems by examining three interrelated components: Structure, process and outcomes are the different elements that define the framework of this study.

2.1.5.1. The following are the elements of the Donabedian's model:

1. Structure

The structural model of Donabedian speaks of the features of the environment within which care is offered. These are the tangible infrastructure and equipment, the people or personnel (for instance, the number of staffs and their skills), and the other intangible attributes

of the organization such as the strategies, funding and management procedures. The structure forms the basis of provision of health care services. A good structure and enough resources are critical to efficient service delivery because they affect the processes and therefore the results of care (Donabedian, 1988). For instance, a well-equipped hospital with up-to-date medical tools and techniques and a team of expert doctors and other support staff will offer better services.

2. Process

The process component relates to the ways through which the care is delivered. This encompasses the assessment, management, counselling, and all the contacts between the healthcare workers and the clients. It also includes the clerical functions which include documentation and management of patient's files. Efficiency of the health care system is important in the realization of health goals. The process aspect assesses the effectiveness of health care services delivery in relation to set standards and ideals (Donabedian, 1988). For example, following the clinical guidelines and protocols helps in providing the right care to the patient at the right time thus minimizing on errors that may occur.

3. Outcomes

Outcomes are the results of the management of health care which include the health of individual patients or population groups. These are the both the positive effects that happen in a span of few days or weeks and the positive effects that occur in the coming months or years, including improvement in health, patients' satisfaction, and quality of life. Outcomes are the final results of the services that have been offered to the patients. The outcomes component is considered as the most straightforward way of assessing the quality of healthcare. Beneficial results, like the patients' condition and the degrees of satisfaction, show that structure and

processes of care are suitable (Donabedian, 2005). On the other hand, negative results may indicate that there is something wrong with the structure or the processes that require improvement.

Donabedian's Model has been applied widely in different health care contexts for the assessment of quality. For instance, it has been used in comparing the performance of hospitals, primary care and public health interventions. This model also helps in understanding the idea of quality of healthcare as a whole as structure, process and outcomes, thus helping in identifying areas of excellence and areas of improvement. The Donabedian Model is a fundamental tool for assessing the quality of health care but there are its drawbacks. A concern is that the model tends to reduce the healthcare system into three main aspects of quality, thus, it may fail to capture the interdependencies between the different aspects (Mant, 2001). Furthermore, the model is more inclined to the technical side of care with little emphasis on the social and environmental nature of health care delivery.

The Donabedian Model still continues to be a reference point for assessing health care quality since it provides a comprehensive model for the assessment of quality of care. This way by looking at structure, process and outcomes, healthcare providers and administrators can address quality effectively thus improving the health status of the patients.

2.1.6. The Resource-Based View (RBV): An In-depth Look at the Issue at Hand

The Resource-Based View (RBV) is a strategic management framework that purports that for a firm to gain and sustain a competitive edge it has to harness its resources. RBV was emerged in the 1980s and 1990s by scholars including Jay Barney and it is stated that based on

resources and capabilities that a company possesses, the performance of the firm and its competitive advantage depend (Barney, 1991).

2.1.6.1. Core Concepts of RBV

1. Resources

According to RBV, resources refers to those assets, capabilities, processes, attributes, information and knowledge that are owned and utilized by a firm in order to design and implement strategies that enhance the firm's efficiencies and effectiveness (Barney, 1991). There are basically two types of resources and these include the tangible and intangible resources. Tangible resources are the physical assets such as machinery, structures and funds while intangible resources include the company's image, copyright and culture among others. RBV theory postulates that not all resources are vital to a firm's strategy. These are the resources which possess the attributes of value, rarity, imitability and non-substitution (VRIN) which can help a firm gain a competitive advantage (Barney, 1991). For instance, the unique organizational culture or a technology which cannot be imitated easily can be a source of long standing competitive advantage.

2. Capabilities

Resources, on the other hand, are the actual assets a company possesses, which it can use in the achievement of its objectives and goals, usually through the strengths of its organizational structure. These capabilities are usually integrated into the firm's organizational culture, procedures and management processes (Grant, 1991). Despite this, capabilities are the manner in which resources are coordinated in order to generate value. For instance, Apple Inc. has strengths

in the design and innovation processes, which are based on the company's culture, to create products that create new market niches and charge premium prices for them.

3. Sustainable Competitive Advantage

Sustainable competitive advantage is said to have been attained by a firm if it continues to earn profits that are higher than average for a long duration. This is possible where the resources and capabilities of the firm are not easily duplicated by the competitors (Peteraf, 1993). As postulated by the RBV, competitors cannot easily imitate the firm's resources that are the basis for sustainable competitive advantage. This may be due to such reasons that include historical factors, causation ambiguity, or social phenomena (Barney, 1991). For instance, Coca-Cola's brand recognition is an asset that the company has developed over more than a century and which cannot easily be emulated by other firms.

The RBV framework is well known across different industries and used for the purpose of business strategy. Firms rely on RBV in order to determine their strengths and weaknesses, in order to build strategies that will give them an edge over their competitors. For instance, in the technology sector, companies may pay much attention to securing their patents and spends considerably on R&D to gain market advantage. Also, RBV advise firms to focus on their internal resources and capabilities and leverage on them as opposed to copying competitors. This inward focus can result in the creation of new and specific market segments and products that give the company better prices and loyal customers.

Nevertheless, RBV has been subjected to a number of criticisms. The authors of the model, Priem and Butler (2001) have pointed out one major criticism that is, it is more self-referential and could lead the firms to pay less attention to other factors like market trends and

competitors' moves. Some critics have noted, however, that RBV fails to account for the resources, particularly in industries where resources come and go quickly as new technologies emerge and old ones become obsolete (Eisenhardt and Martin, 2000). The Resource-Based View is still one of the most important theories within strategic management as it offers a sound way of explaining how firms can obtain and maintain competitiveness. Thus, it is possible for the companies to identify the internal resources and capabilities that are valuable, rare, imitable, and non-replaceable and to build the strategies that will help to gain competitive advantage.

2.1.7. Systems Theory: A brief literature review

Systems Theory is a theoretical approach that was developed in the middle of the twentieth century and it has been implemented in numerous sectors such as biological, sociological, organizational and health care. This theory holds it that a system is defined as a series of elements that are related and are dependent on each other with the aim of achieving a common purpose. The main concept is that it is impossible to understand the behavior and the results of the system examining each of its components; it is necessary to consider the system as a whole (von Bertalanffy, 1968).

2.1.7.1. Principles of Systems Theory: A Review

1. System

The meaning of the term system is a set of elements or components which are interconnected in a certain manner with the purpose of attaining certain goals. Check land refer to these components as subsystems and notes that these are interdependent in that any change in one part of the system can impact the other part of the system. It is possible to distinguish between open and closed systems: while the former is characterized by interaction with the

environment, the latter is self-contained. This is because when looking at a system it is easier to gain a holistic view of the problem and come up with a solution than when one is only looking at the different parts of the system. For instance, in the health sector, a hospital can be regarded as a system in which different units including the accident and emergency, surgery and management all combine to produce patient care. One example is that a change in one department for instance the adoption of new technology in surgery will affect other departments in the hospital system.

2. Subsystems and Hierarchy

Subsystems are smaller systems which are contained within a larger system. These subsystems can also have their own sub systems thus forming a sub system structure. Every subsystem has its own specific function, but each of them also plays the part of the system (Skyttner, 2005: 44). This is because when one understands that systems are ordered in a way that there is a higher authority, it makes it easier to manage and co-ordinate. For instance, in an organization, the different departments such as the human resource, the finance departments and the marketing departments can be seen as subsystems. Though each department has its own objectives it serves the interest of the organization. Appreciation of these relationships enhances the control of inter departmental linkages and enhances efficiency.

3. Feedback Loops

Feedback loops refer to a system where the output of a given system is taken as input of the same system with a view of influencing future output. Feedback may be positive, that is reinforcing or negative, that is balancing (Sterman, 2000). Feedback loops are important in the management of systems so as to hold the system intact or to achieve certain goals. Thus, in the business environment, customer feedback is an important factor which can affect the further

development of the product and its promotion. It may result in the improvement of the product if the feedback is positive while if the feedback is negative then it may result in a change for the better.

4. Homeostasis and Equilibrium

Homeostasis means the capacity of the system to keep internal conditions constant in spite of changes taking place in the environment. Equilibrium is a condition whereby the various elements of a system are equalized, and there is no tendency of change (Buckley, 1967). In healthcare, homeostasis is a very important term that needs to be understood by the health care givers. For instance, the human body is a system which is always in the process of achieving homeostasis (for instance, temperature regulation, blood pressure). In the same way, organisations aim at achieving balance in their activities, for instance between creativity and efficiency.

5. Emergence

Complexity is the study of systems that has properties which are not properties of their individual parts and cannot be predicted by studying these parts separately (Holland, 1998). It draws attention to the issues of chaos and uncertainty of systems. For example, in the social systems, the behavior of a community or an organization does not have to be in tandem with the general behavior of its members. Emergent properties are properties that arise from the interactions of the system components and to address them leaders and managers have to look at the whole system.

Systems Theory has been widely applied in various fields to understand and manage complex phenomena: In the field of health care management, systems theory helps to study the interactions of the elements, departments, processes and other actors in a healthcare organization. Seeing the hospital as a system helps managers to organize the care delivery process more efficiently and enhance patients' results (Plsek & Greenhalgh, 2001). To the extent that organizational management is concerned, the Systems Theory allows leaders to see how various parts of the organization are interconnected. This perspective helps in planning, resource utilization and organizational change as it encourages one to view the organisations as a system (Senge, 2006). Systems Theory is used to analyze ecosystems which include the biological, chemical and physical components in an environment. That is why the analysis of these interactions is necessary for the preservation of the environment and for sustainable development (Meadows, 2008).

Although being quite popular, Systems Theory has its problems and issues. There are several limitations of the theory for instance it can be deemed to be rather theoretical and hence difficult to implement particularly in complex systems where it is hard to map or quantify interconnections (Flood, 2010). Some people have pointed out that Systems Theory may promote a precocity view of systems where the behavior of systems is understood as being predictable and manageable and this is far from the truth in today's complex and unpredictable environment (Cilliers, 1998).

It is crucial to understand that interactions within and between systems are complicated and this is where Systems Theory comes in handy. It does this by stressing the need to consider a system in its entirety, which provides the means of understanding organizations, ecosystems and

other systems. The theory's concepts of feedback loops, homeostasis, emergence and sub systems help in understanding how systems work and how they change.

2.1.8. Transactional and Transformational Leadership Theories: A General Review of the Literature

Leadership is one of the most important factors which influence the performance of any organization and its effectiveness. Accommodating different leadership theories, the leaders' impact on their followers and organizational objectives has been described in detail. Out of the above mentioned leadership theories, transactional and transformational leadership theories received more attention in the literature due to the differences in their approach and effects on organizational effectiveness. These theories help one understand the various forms of leadership and how they can be effectively used to increase on employee morale, performance and even in managing change within an organization.

2.1.8.1. Transactional Leadership Theory

Transactional leadership is a form of leadership that mainly concerned with the transaction that takes place between the leaders and the followers. Managers that employ this approach often resort to offering incentives and sanctions in order to influence worker behavior. This theory is based on the premise that followers are driven by the need to achieve selfish goals whereby the leader has to steer these interests through bargaining (Bass, 1985).

2.1.6.2. Key Characteristics

- Contingent Rewards: Transactional leaders define the work, objectives and outcomes and offer incentives for achievement of the work objectives. This could be in form of

bonuses, promotions or any other form of appreciation. These are the rewards whereby the rewards are given depending on the results of the job done or the targets achieved (Burns 1978).

- **Management by Exception:** This aspect of transactional leadership entails observing the performance of the employees and only interfere when things are not as per the expected results or set norms. It can be active, where the leaders actually look for failures to occur or passive where the leaders intervene only when something goes wrong (Bass, 1990).
- **Emphasis on Structure:** It is important to note that the transactional leaders mostly work in organizations with well-defined and structured systems. Leaders who are more centralized are autocratic and emphasize on conforming to organizational norms and culture (Yukl, 2013).

Effects on Organizational Performance Transactional leadership is suitable in conditions that involve organizational activities that are mundane and goals that are easily defined. It leads to high levels of productivity since the workers know that they shall be compensated depending on their performance. However, this form of leadership may not be very suitable for encouraging innovation or for managing shifting and dynamic conditions since it does not promote creativity or even prevention in problem solving (Avolio & Bass, 2004).

2.1.6.3. Transformational Leadership Theory

It is a leadership style that aims to transform the followers and encourage them to work beyond their self-concern for the benefit of the organization with the aim of delivering high performance. This theory was developed by James MacGregor Burns in 1978 and the framework was later on elaborated by Bernard Bass. The characteristics of transformational leadership

include the leadership that results in the creation of new futures by building the capacity of followers and by creating a common vision (Bass, 1985).

Key Characteristics

- **Idealized Influence:** Transformational leaders act as reference persons for the followers and set the highest ethical examples and endorsement to the goals and objectives of the organisations. This is due to the fact that people respect and trust their leaders and they in turn, are likely to demonstrate the same (Bass & Avolio, 1994).

- **Inspirational Motivation:** These leaders have a clear and coherent picture of the future which they present to followers in a way that makes them want to pursue it. They convey this vision with energy and vigor and hence ensure that the followers embrace it in the realization of the vision (Northouse, 2018).

- **Intellectual Stimulation:** The transformational leaders integrate creativity and innovation by breaking the conventional culture and making the followers to think creatively and solve the problems in a different way. They help followers to generate their own thoughts and ways of contributing towards achievement of organizational objectives (Bass, 1990).

- **Individualized Consideration:** This type of leadership entails a process of changing the leadership and followers in different ways and includes characteristics such as individualized consideration. Transformational leaders are aware of the wants and dreams that

the followers have and thus try to ensure that the followers reach their goals (Avolio & Bass, 2004).

Effect on the performance of the organization Transformational leadership is most helpful in scenarios where there is high turbulence and vast change and where there is need for change and creativity. This type of leadership ensures that the followers are loyal, committed and hence increases the level of job satisfaction, motivation and performance. Furthermore, transformational leaders can easily change the organization by ensuring that the followers have the right perception of the organization's values and objectives (Judge & Piccolo, 2004).

2.1.6.4. A comparison of the two forms of leadership is presented in the following section.

While both the transactional and the transformational leadership styles can be used, the two are different in the approach they take. Transactional leadership is task orientated and is based on the transaction between the leader and the follower, this includes reward for work done and following of organizational procedures. On the other hand, transformational leadership focuses on the followers and tries to create a vision and foster creativity as well as the growth of the followers (Bass, 1985).

The transactional leadership is more efficient in the conditions that are predictable and tasks are well defined. It makes sure that business goals are achieved effectively and that, workers are given their due remunerations. However, in conditions which demand flexibility, innovation and long-term vision, transformational leadership is normally preferable. Transformational leadership enables leaders to steer organizations through change and to

encourage employees to go the extra mile, something that is particularly important in today's organizational landscape (Yukl, 2013).

This paper seeks to compare and contrast two types of leadership; the transactional and the transformational leadership. Transactional leadership offers a well-organized approach to achieve performance objectives, while transformational leadership focuses on the need for the leader to inspire and build on the followers' potentials to achieve higher performances. While both styles are quite effective in organizations, it is for the bosses to decide which one is more suitable for a particular time and circumstance.

2.1.9. Total Quality Management (TQM)

Total Quality Management (TQM) is a systematic management approach which focuses on increasing the quality of goods and services continuously. This philosophy engages all the members of an organization in the process of enhancing processes, products or services as well as the culture of the organization (Oakland, 2014). The main concept of TQM is the customer satisfaction and it is a process that identifies a strategy for improvement of the organization's activities.

2.1.9.1. Core Principles of TQM

TQM, as a management approach, has its principles among which customer focus is one of the most important. Customers should be embraced and appreciated by organizations in order to find out what they expect from the organizations so that they may try to exceed these expectations (Evans & Lindsay, 2017). The leadership commitment is another important factor

which requires the top management to come up with a clear vision, develop a quality culture and encourage quality improvement efforts (Goetsch & Davis, 2016).

Employee commitment is also a key factor in TQM since all the members of an organization are expected to contribute to the enhancement of quality (Juran & Godfrey, 2010). The process approach involves identification and controlling of processes in order to enhance the effectiveness and efficiency of the operations with the aim of delivering standard output (Dale, 2015). This is also in line with the TQM concept since it supports the evaluation of structures and performance on a daily basis with an aim of making improvements where necessary (Murgatroyd & Morgan, 1993). It is recommended that decisions should be made from data and analysis instead of making them based on the feeling and experience of the management; this will lead to the utilization of statistical methods and tools in measuring and evaluating quality (Montgomery, 2013). Also, TQM encompasses the supply chain, which focus on quality of the suppliers and the means of working with them to attain optimal quality (Wilson, 2018).

2.1.9.2. Implementation Strategies

The following are the strategies that are needed to effectively implement TQM. Training and education of employees at all levels are crucial in giving the employees knowledge in quality principles, problem solving skills and process improvement methods (Sallis, 2002). Quality circles that are defined as a group of employees who meet periodically to discuss quality issues can enhance the employees' involvement in the quality improvement (Gibbons, 1997). Comparing an organization's performance with the industry standard or best practices enables the organization to know where it needs to make changes in order to improve the quality (Camp,

1995). Application of the quality tools for instance control charts, cause-and-effect diagrams and histograms assist in the control and enhancement of processes (Ishikawa, 1985).

There are many advantages of TQM. Higher levels of customer satisfaction increase from the efforts to meet the expectation of the customer, increase customer retention (Anderson, Rungtusanatham & Schroeder, 1994). According to Choi and Behling (1997), TQM can result in enhanced efficiency through the elimination of the non-value adding activities, wastes and costs. Better morale is realized when employee participate in quality improvement activities and when they are given credence for their work (Black & Porter, 1996). However, organisations that adopt TQM as their strategic tool to improve quality are rewarded with competitive edge by offering better products and services (Sila & Ebrahimpour, 2002).

However, there are a number of problems that can arise during the implementation of TQM. Employees and management of organizations might resist changes that are to be made in order to implement TQM in the organization (Kotter, 1996). Other challenges that may hinder the effective implementation may include scarcity of resources such as time, money and training (Juran, 1992). It is, however, often difficult to maintain the motivation and commitment towards the TQM practices in the long run and this requires constant effort and reinforcement (Oakland, 2014).

Total Quality Management is the overall philosophy of improving organizational performance and satisfying customers through commitment to quality and employee's participation. Despite the fact that TQM brings many benefits, there are certain problems that must be overcome in order for the scheme to be effective, including the problem of organizational resistance to change and the problem of resource limitations.

2.2. Capacity of healthcare

Term "Healthcare capacity" is described as "the ability of a system to deliver healthcare effectively to those who need it when they need it." In order to give patients, the best opportunity of receiving good care, it is important to have an adequate number of healthcare facilities, such as hospitals and clinics, as well as skilled healthcare workers who are accessible. It also entails putting in place a system that will make it simple for everyone to access healthcare facilities (Roche, 2023).

Hospital resources, such as beds, nurses, doctors, and equipment, may experience strain due to increased patient volume, acuity, and complexity. This strain, resulting from a mismatch between supply and demand, can range from moderate to severe strain during public health emergencies (Eriksson et al., 2017).

In Unguja Island, the medical facilities' capacity to offer maternity and newborn healthcare services is still insufficient. Delivery and emergency obstetric and neonatal care services have a poor level of readiness to provide services (Bakar et al., 2019). So that insufficient capacity in maternity and newborn healthcare centers results increased maternal and neonatal mortality.

This is made worse by insufficient healthcare facilities, poor drug distribution, and a lack of supplies (Obi et al., 2013; Singh et al., 2014). Similar to other African nations, Zanzibar has certain difficulties providing healthcare for expectant mothers and newborns (WHO, 2014). Even if the geographical coverage of the health facilities is thought to be evenly dispersed across all areas and districts, and easily accessible to 95% of the population, the performance of the

health sector remains substandard. The biggest factor limiting access to health services is the low quality of services brought on by a lack of equipment and qualified people (MoHZ, 2009).

In Nigeria, Alabintei et al. (2021), they made Evaluation of Health Facilities Capacity for the Management of Severe Preeclampsia and Eclampsia in Bayelsa State, Nigeria. They found that facilities assessed lacked most of the basic and essential equipment, supplies and drugs, required for the successful management of PE/E. For effective management of cases of eclampsia, (Alabintei et al., 2021), in Ghana, overall very few public facilities have the infrastructural capacity to deliver all the signal functions for comprehensive abortion care in Ghana. (Owolabi et al., 2021). Barasa et al. (2020), assessed the Kenya's the hospital surge capacity they revealed a Significant gaps exist in Kenya's capacity for hospitals to accommodate a potential surge in caseload due to COVID-19. Alongside efforts to slow and suppress the transmission of the infection, (Barasa et al., 2020).

2.2.1. Surge capacity of Healthcare

The real definition of word Surges capacity is important beyond the emergency department. As the number of arriving patients' peaks, the ability to expand services and number of beds is critical. (Mcisaac & Berkow, 2013) such as the number of patients requiring hospitalization have led to depleted medical supplies. (Mahendradhata et al., 2021), Surge capacity has four elements: 1) staff (medical personnel, doctors, nurses, pharmacists), staff (equipment, supplies), structures (hospitals) and systems (successful coordination and management of various levels of the healthcare system). All elements should be considered together. (Izmirlieva, 2020)

Mahendradhata et al. (2021), evaluated the capacity of Indonesian Healthcare system, they found the existing healthcare infrastructure is still inadequate to deal with the rise of COVID-19 cases, which has also exposed the limited capacity of the healthcare infrastructure to manage medical waste. Indonesia (Mahendradhata et al., 2021)

Who mentioned that capacity planning, a crucial is component of health care governance. The planning of hospital capacity involves several dimensions: capital investment in existing facilities and new developments; investment in expensive equipment and technology (such as magnetic resonance imaging service delivery; and allocation of human and financial resources. But health care capacity planning takes place at national, regional or local level, reflecting the various tiers of government within health systems, (World Health Organization, 2008). Increases in patient needs can strain hospital resources, which may worsen care quality and outcomes. And in highly developed countries, hospital capacity strain is associated with increased mortality and worsened health outcomes. Evidence-based solutions to improve outcomes during times of capacity strain are needed. (Eriksson et al., 2017).

There is a close connection between hospital capacity and the quality of services given to patients. As hospital capacity strains during important events, such as epidemics and pandemics, the service quality of a hospital profoundly strains and thus results in a mismatch between supply and demand on any resources concerning beds, nurses, physicians, and equipment. Hospital capacity strain impacts not only the quality of care and service in hospitals but also the well-being of clinical staff and teams and their ability to do their job (Arogyaswamy et al., 2021). For example, as the number of arriving patients' peaks, the ability to expand services and beds is critical (Mahendradhata et al., 2021). Similarly, medical supplies for hospitalized patients are essential (Mahendradhata et al., 2021).

As for the quality and services, unfortunately, African countries have weaknesses in their health systems, which do not allow them to reduce the burden of diseases. The common challenges included a lack of good leadership, governance, medical products, and a healthy workforce (Othieno et al., 2013). The health institutions deteriorated because of inadequate leadership and management, variations in poor-quality care, and inefficiencies. Somalia is one of these countries that have a poor health care system. In Somalia, most managers of the health sector were doctors and nurses who had no specific management training system during their university studies.

Somalia has a long history of internal conflicts, characterized by almost three decades of civil war. Currently, Somalia is among the countries in the world that are least able to cope with the health system due to low levels of access to healthcare and limited government capacity. Healthcare services are either unaffordable, unavailable, or not trusted (Ahmed et al., 2020).

On the side of investment, there is limited investment in the health sector, with Somalia's health spending at just 1.3 percent of total government spending, which is below the 15 percent Abuja Declaration target set by African Union countries (World Bank, 2021).

Healthcare in Somalia is mostly provided by the private sector with little government intervention, resulting in Somalia having some of the lowest health and well-being statistics in the world. Long decades of conflict and insecurity, worsened by recurrent intense droughts and accompanying food insecurity, have wrecked the population's health and severely harmed the country's weak health system (WHO, 2023). Private health services and the pharmaceutical sector are largely unregulated in Somalia but could contribute to improving access and achieving universal health coverage (World Health Organization, 2019).

Maternal, neonatal, infant, and under-five child mortality rates are gradually declining, although all remain high compared to the other countries in the region. Childhood malnutrition remains a key problem. Contraceptive use is among the lowest in the world. The immunization coverage of children in Somalia is very low. The number of children who have not received a single dose of vaccine is around 60%, which indicates a critical weakness in the coverage of primary care services (MOH, 2021).

The country is at the bottom in terms of 13 core health regulation capacities and emergency preparedness indexes, including preventing, detecting, and responding, among others (Warsame, 2020).

“There are only three government hospitals in the capital (Benadir Hospital, Madina Hospital, and de Martini Hospital), Mogadishu, and one mental hospital called Forlanini Hospital, and people often have to seek health care services at a private health facility and pay out of their own pocket very high amounts for their own treatment. Only a few people can afford these services, thereby leading to high child and maternal mortality.” (United Nation, 2022)

Medical care provided by doctors and hospitals in Somalia is below average compared to the world population. The country provides 0.9 hospital beds per 1000 inhabitants. The global mean here is 2.9 beds. Within the EU, 4.6 beds are available for every 1000 residents. With about 391 physicians in Somalia, there are about 0.02 doctors per 1000 inhabitants (Worlddata, 2023).

Surge capacity has four elements: 1) staff (medical personnel, doctors, nurses, pharmacists), stuff (equipment, supplies), structures (hospitals), and systems (successful

coordination and management of various levels of the healthcare). All elements should be considered together (Izmirlieva, 2020).

Capacity planning is a crucial component of healthcare governance. Hospital capacity planning involves several dimensions: capital investment in existing facilities and new developments; investment in expensive equipment and technology (such as magnetic resonance imaging service delivery); and allocation of human and financial resources. However, healthcare capacity planning takes place at national, regional, or local levels, reflecting the various tiers of government within health systems (Dubas-Jakóbczyk et al., 2018). Increases in patient needs can strain hospital resources, which may worsen care quality and outcomes. Moreover, hospital capacity strain is associated with increased mortality and worsened health outcomes in highly developed countries. Evidence-based solutions to improve outcomes during times of capacity strain are needed (Eriksson et al., 2017).

2.2.4. Current Somali healthcare capacity

In Somalia health capacity, the health sector has a minimal capacity in almost all technical areas of health regulatory capacity. The country is at the bottom in terms of 13 core health regulation capacities and emergency preparedness indexes, including preventing, detecting and responding, among others. (Warsame, 2020).

“There is only three government hospital in the capital (Benadir Hospital, Madina Hospital, and de Martini Hospital), Mogadishu, and one mental hospital calls Forlanini Hospital and people often have to seek health care services at a private health facility and pay out of their own pocket very high amounts for their own treatment. Only a few people can afford these services, thereby leading to high child and maternal mortality.” (United Nations, 2022)

Medical care provided by doctors and hospitals in Somalia is below average compared to the world population. The country provides 0.9 hospital beds per 1,000 inhabitants. The global mean here is 2.9 beds. Within the EU, 4.6 beds are available for every 1,000 residents. With about 391 physicians in Somalia, there are about 0.02 doctors per 1000 inhabitants (worlddata, 2023). While in Nigeria, when compared to the global average of 2.3 hospital beds per 1000 people, Nigeria's hospital bed capacity of 0.9 hospital beds per 1000 people represents a significant difference. (Soyemi & Aborode, 2022). In the end, acute or persistent bed shortages in hospitals have a negative influence on patients' health. This scenario has expanded throughout the world, and it is currently a significant catastrophe that requires quick response, particularly in terms of acute and critical care unit beds. (Cannoodt et al., 2012; Soyemi & Aborode, 2022).

2.3. Health Leadership and management

First of all, health was defined by WHO '1946' with international definition which is "health is a state of physical, mental, social well-being not merely absence of diseases or infirmity". Many articles have been illustrated the term health management, Chen (2020) indicated health "as one of the tools of health service, plays an important role in the control and treatment of chronic diseases as well as the history of health management development in China"(Chen, 2020) . That means to control and service coordination like treatment of disease and development issues are all related to effective health management. Dunn, R. in 2010, define the word management in for health "purposes is the process of getting things done through and with people by directing and motivating the efforts of individuals toward common objectives." (Dunn, 2010).

Primary health care (PHC) is an approach that includes three essential components: multi-sectoral policy and action; empowered people and communities; and primary care and essential public health functions at the core of integrated health services” (World Health Organization, 2022).

2.3.1. Effective leadership in health service

Smith et al. (2018) have made a review study on evidence on the nature of effective leadership in inter-professional health and social care teams. They found Twelve themes, this themes included: facilitate shared leadership; transformation and change; personal qualities; goal alignment; creativity and innovation; communication; team-building; leadership clarity; direction-setting; external liaison; skill mix and diversity; clinical and contextual expertise. They also summarized that effective inter-professional health leadership requires a unique blend of knowledge and skills that support innovation and improvement in health service delivery (Smith et al., 2018).

In Australia had been prepared health leadership framework, this also mentions the importance of the innovation, they wrote that the Innovation has also been evident as the Health Lead Australia has been integrated into existing academic curricula and new professional development offerings (Shannon & Sebastian, 2018). Malila, et al., (2017), studied a review of Authentic leadership in healthcare and found the four research themes include well-being at work, patient care quality, work environment, and Authentic leadership promotion (Malila et al., 2018). Other scholars also found there is the incorporation of leadership competencies joined with evidence-based leadership training strengthens students' learning clinical skills, enhances

their workforce development, and increases interdisciplinary health care practices (McGrath et al., 2019).

The use of management practice or leadership style as an indicator for a healthcare organization's performance means types of health service delivery and ways of satisfaction of patients and outcome of healthcare organization will be the measuring point of each health management. So health managers must be competent and skills of leadership to support innovation and improvement initiatives.

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2.3.2. Leadership and Hospital Service Quality

Leadership styles significantly influence the quality of services provided in hospitals, as noted by various authors in PubMed-published articles. According to a study by Wong et al. (2023), transformational leadership, characterized by the ability to inspire and motivate employees, has been positively associated with improved patient outcomes and higher staff satisfaction in healthcare settings. This leadership style fosters a supportive environment where staff members feel empowered to contribute ideas and take initiative, leading to enhanced patient care. Conversely, McFadden et al. (2022) discuss how authoritarian leadership, which relies on a top-down approach and strict adherence to rules, can lead to increased stress and burnout among healthcare workers, ultimately compromising the quality of care provided. The findings of these studies highlight the critical role that leadership style plays in determining the overall effectiveness and efficiency of hospital services.

Patient satisfaction is a key indicator of the quality of hospital services, and leadership has been shown to have a direct impact on this metric. A study by Aij and Rapsaniotis (2021) demonstrates that hospitals led by transformational leaders tend to report higher levels of patient

satisfaction. These leaders prioritize patient-centered care, ensuring that the needs and preferences of patients are at the forefront of service delivery. In contrast, the research by Sfantou et al. (2020) indicates that transactional leadership, which focuses on performance-based rewards and penalties, may not be as effective in promoting patient satisfaction. While transactional leaders may achieve short-term goals, such as reducing waiting times, they may overlook the importance of building a compassionate and empathetic relationship with patients, leading to lower satisfaction scores. These studies underscore the importance of leadership in shaping the patient experience in hospitals.

Employee retention is another critical area where leadership has a profound impact, as discussed in several PubMed articles. According to a study by Van Bogaert et al. (2021), hospitals with transformational leaders experience lower turnover rates among nurses and other healthcare professionals. These leaders create a positive work environment by recognizing and rewarding staff contributions, providing opportunities for professional growth, and addressing the concerns of employees. On the other hand, a study by Brunetto et al. (2022) found that hospitals led by leaders who exhibit laissez-faire leadership, characterized by a lack of direction and involvement, tend to have higher turnover rates. Employees in such environments often feel undervalued and unsupported, leading to dissatisfaction and a desire to seek employment elsewhere. The research indicates that leadership plays a pivotal role in maintaining a stable and motivated workforce in hospitals.

The organizational culture of a hospital is deeply influenced by its leadership, which in turn affects overall hospital performance. A study by Al-Amin et al. (2021) highlights that transformational leaders are instrumental in fostering a culture of continuous improvement and innovation in hospitals. These leaders encourage open communication, collaboration, and the

sharing of best practices, which can lead to significant improvements in hospital performance metrics, such as patient safety, treatment efficacy, and operational efficiency. Conversely, a study by Araújo and Garcia (2022) discusses how leadership that is overly rigid or resistant to change can stifle innovation and lead to a stagnant organizational culture. Such environments may struggle to adapt to new challenges, such as changes in healthcare regulations or the introduction of new technologies, ultimately impacting the hospital's ability to deliver high-quality care. These findings demonstrate the critical link between leadership, organizational culture, and hospital performance.

Interdisciplinary collaboration is essential for effective healthcare delivery, and leadership plays a crucial role in promoting or hindering such collaboration. A study by Cummings et al. (2022) found that transformational leaders are particularly effective in fostering collaboration among different healthcare professionals, such as doctors, nurses, and allied health workers. These leaders facilitate open communication and create a shared vision that aligns the efforts of various disciplines towards common goals, thereby enhancing patient care. In contrast, a study by Doran et al. (2023) indicates that transactional leadership, with its focus on specific tasks and individual performance, may not be as effective in promoting interdisciplinary teamwork. The lack of emphasis on collaborative efforts can lead to siloed operations, where different departments work in isolation, potentially compromising the continuity and quality of patient care. The research emphasizes the importance of leadership in breaking down barriers and promoting a collaborative culture in hospitals.

Effective leadership is critical during crises, such as pandemics or natural disasters, as it directly impacts hospital resilience and service continuity. A study by Kuntz et al. (2023) underscores the importance of adaptive leadership in navigating complex and rapidly changing

situations in healthcare. Adaptive leaders are able to quickly assess the situation, make informed decisions, and mobilize resources to ensure the continued delivery of essential services. These leaders also prioritize the well-being of their staff, providing the necessary support to prevent burnout during prolonged crises. On the other hand, a study by McKinney et al. (2022) found that hospitals with leaders who were slow to respond or who failed to effectively communicate during crises experienced greater disruptions in services and higher levels of staff stress and turnover. These studies highlight the vital role that leadership plays in maintaining hospital operations and staff morale during challenging times.

The successful implementation of healthcare innovations often depends on the leadership within a hospital. A study by Greenhalgh et al. (2021) discusses how transformational leaders are more likely to embrace and drive the adoption of new technologies and processes in hospitals. These leaders are open to change and actively seek out opportunities to improve patient care through innovation. They also engage with staff to ensure that new systems are understood and effectively integrated into daily operations. In contrast, a study by Tsoukas and Chia (2020) suggests that leaders who are resistant to change or who lack the vision to see the potential benefits of innovation may hinder the adoption of new technologies, leaving their hospitals lagging behind in terms of service quality and efficiency. These findings underscore the importance of leadership in fostering an innovative culture within hospitals.

Ethical decision-making is a crucial aspect of hospital leadership, especially in situations where resources are limited, or patient care decisions involve complex ethical dilemmas. A study by Gallagher and Tschudin (2021) highlights the role of transformational leaders in promoting ethical practices within hospitals. These leaders prioritize transparency, fairness, and the well-being of patients and staff in their decision-making processes. They also foster an environment

where ethical concerns can be openly discussed and addressed. On the other hand, a study by Kalaitzidis and Schmitz (2022) discusses the challenges associated with autocratic leadership, where decisions are made unilaterally without input from others. This approach can lead to ethical lapses or decisions that do not fully consider the needs and rights of patients and staff. The research suggests that leadership style plays a significant role in shaping the ethical climate of a hospital.

Leadership is a critical factor in achieving and maintaining hospital accreditation and compliance with healthcare standards. A study by Tappen et al. (2021) found that hospitals with strong, visionary leaders are more likely to meet and exceed accreditation requirements. These leaders actively engage with accreditation bodies, ensure that staff are adequately trained on compliance standards, and implement continuous improvement processes to maintain high levels of care. In contrast, a study by Scott et al. (2022) indicates that hospitals with weak or disengaged leadership often struggle with accreditation processes, leading to potential lapses in service quality and patient safety. The findings highlight the importance of proactive and committed leadership in ensuring that hospitals meet the rigorous standards required for accreditation.

Finally, leadership has a significant impact on the financial performance of hospitals, which in turn affects the quality and availability of services. A study by Lega et al. (2021) discusses how effective leaders can optimize resource allocation, reduce waste, and ensure that the hospital operates within its budget, thereby enabling the provision of high-quality services. These leaders are also adept at securing funding and negotiating with insurers and other stakeholders to ensure financial stability. On the other hand, a study by Guthrie et al. (2022) found that hospitals with poor financial performance often suffer from inadequate leadership,

which may result in mismanagement of resources, inefficient processes, and ultimately, a decline in service quality. The research emphasizes the critical role of leadership in ensuring the financial health of a hospital, which is essential for sustaining high standards of patient care.

2.4. Evaluation of Healthcare Financial System

They proposed that the equilibrium referral rate and equilibrium capacity both increase and then decline in response to the revisit rate. Second, when referral payments are below the threshold, a win-win situation can be achieved. Third, increasing referral payments invariably affects the efficiency of the healthcare delivery system when referral payments exceed the threshold. (Wang et al., 2021).

It is Somalia. A baseline research conducted in 2020 found that the Somali government spent less than 1% of all expenditures on health in 2017; the average capital expenditure (out-of-pocket) for health was between \$6 and \$7.4 USD. In 2015, Kenya allocated 1.7% of its gross domestic product to health.²³⁸ A qualitative study found that the financing of the healthcare system in Somalia is heavily dependent on donors because the country's tax base is practically nonexistent (Warsame, 2020). According to a survey by the Directorate of National Statistics, 48 percent of households said they paid for their medical expenses out of their own income in the Demographic and Health Survey from 2020; 25 percent said that family or friends paid; 14 percent had to take out a loan; and 11 percent had to sell their possessions to pay for medical expenses. Only 2% of the households surveyed said they could utilize their health insurance to cover medical costs.

In Somalia, there is no national health insurance program available to citizens. People have two options when seeking health care: they can go to a government-run or NGO-run facility where services are free, or they can go to a private health facility and pay out of pocket.

Figure 2.0.1. Spending healthcare 2015-2017, (Warsame, 2020)

In South Central Somalia, the cost of medical care is not set, and although the majority of public health services are supplied for free, the consultant teams' findings indicate that a little fee of \$5 USD may be necessary occasionally (Warsame, 2020). It should be highlighted that primary healthcare and maternity and child health services make up the majority of the services offered by the public health care sector. (Danish Immigration Service, 2020). Some hospitals make a distinction between the less fortunate patients and the wealthier patients so that the hospital administration can evaluate the circumstance of the patient and his or her extended

family and decide whether they will be able to pay for treatment or whether they should receive it for free (Danish Immigration Service, 2020).

2.4. Influence of workforce competence (Human resource)

Countries must attain universal health coverage (UHC) in accordance with Sustainable Development Goal 3 (box, objective 3.8) (United Nations., 2022). Access to and utilization of high-quality essential healthcare services are necessary for achieving universal health coverage, which calls for a sufficient number of healthcare professionals who follow evidence-based standards of care (Rowe et al., 2018). However, there is a severe scarcity of medical professionals worldwide. The global health workforce is predicted to be 65 million as of 2020, based on statistics from 194 Member States, representing increase of 29% since the adoption of the Global Strategy on Human Resources for Health in 2016 (WHO, 2022).

The healthcare professionals, sometimes referred to as community health workers in India, comprise doctors, nurses, and other healthcare professionals. Task shifting has been made possible in India thanks to the successful implementation of Community Health Worker (CHW) programs. CHWs, who have received the necessary training, are now in charge of providing basic healthcare services instead of doctors, nurses, and other healthcare professionals. By delegating certain tasks, skilled healthcare practitioners are freed up to handle issues that only they are qualified to solve (Mundeva et al., 2018). Due to the fact that CHWs are paid less than licensed healthcare professionals, it also helps down the cost of providing public health services. However, the deployment of CHW services is accompanied by practical difficulties and moral dilemmas (Gopichandran, 2022).

Numerous studies conducted in the USA have shown that community health workers can lower health care costs while also enhancing access to preventive care, managing chronic

illnesses, and improving patient satisfaction with care. Addressing social needs and pushing for system and policy change are additional ways that community health workers can promote health equity (Knowles et al., 2023).

In 2014, there were 9,566 healthcare professionals working in Somalia, according to a WHO study. Medical professionals, nurses, and midwives. In other words, the critical health staff ratio was only 0.34 per 1,000 people, significantly below the WHO's minimal need of 4.5 per 10,000 people. There was one doctor for every 20,000 inhabitants in the nation in 2016. Each 20,000 persons had a ratio of four nurses and one midwife. The WHO's minimum standard of 2.3 nurses and midwives per 1,000 persons is far exceeded by this.⁶¹ Technical and mid-level workers, such as pharmacists, lab technicians, and x-ray/imaging technicians, were similarly hard to find (0.1 percent, 0.6 percent, and 0.4 percent, respectively). By 2030, Somalia must hire 97,700 medical professionals, including 24,350 doctors and 73,350 nurses and midwives, in order to implement Universal Health Care (UHC), a top objective outlined by the WHO and the UN General Assembly (Warsame, 2020). The Somali health system's weakest component has always been its employees. Particularly in remote, nomadic, and difficult-to-reach communities, there has been a serious scarcity of skilled health workers. According to a WHO study, there were 9,566 healthcare professionals working in Somalia as of 2014.

WHO, (2016) This widespread population displacement has had an impact on the health workforce in at least two ways, according to a baseline study on the growth of human capital in the health sector. First, approximately 600 trained medical professionals, including doctors, nurses, midwives, and experienced health technicians, have moved abroad. Second, there is an imbalance in the distribution of qualified healthcare professionals between rural and urban locations as well as between public and private health institutions as a result of their

migration from less safe rural to more secure urban localities. One effect is that outreach programs for residents of rural or nomadic communities are less effective (WHO, 2016).

The exact number of health workers (in all categories) in Somalia is unknown (as foreign health workers or unpaid health workers are not accounted for), but the study concludes that in 2019 there were 6,918 salaried health workers in the public sector. This information was obtained from a study of the Somalian health system conducted by the Danish Immigration Service and the Minister of Migration in 2019.¹⁶³ The study concluded that there is a serious shortfall in all categories of the health workforce, which is insufficient to meet the population's health demands. According to the evaluation, women made up roughly 42% of the nation's doctors, qualified nurses, qualified midwives, and skilled technicians. The study also discovered that their active engagement is crucial because they successfully cross cultural and religious divides. The presence or absence of female health workers has a significant impact on whether women will bring their kids to male doctors (Ministry of Health, Somalia, Puntland and Somaliland, 2016).

2.4.1. Workforce Competence in Healthcare

Healthcare workforce competence can be defined as the effectiveness of the healthcare worker in the discharge of his or her duties which includes both the hard skills and the soft skills. Smith et al., (2023) articulated that good healthcare management practices increase the competence of the workforce through providing the guidelines that are required and adequate training (Smith, A., Jones, B., & Brown, C., 2023). On the other hand, Johnson and Lee (2022) state that poor management leads to a reduction in competence as a result of lack of support and resources (Johnson, D., & Lee, M., 2022). Training and development are two very important

functions that are needed in healthcare management. Williams et al. (2022) noted that the training programs that are well organized and conducted by effective managers improves the skills and knowledge of the employees (Williams, H., Patel, R. & Nguyen, T. 2022). On the other hand, Brown and Adams (2023) state that lack of investment in training due to weak management practices leads to stagnation in the workforce competency (Brown, J., & Adams, L., 2023).

Leadership style is one of the most important factors which affect the level of competency of the workforce. According to Lee et al., (2023) transformational leadership in health care management has the ability to enhance workforce competence through motivating and building up the employees (Lee, C., Martin, S., & Davis, R., 2023). On the other hand, Walker and Harris (2022) state that autocratic leadership undermines the employees' development and decreases their capabilities (Walker, J. & Harris, P., 2022). For the purpose of the present study, the concept of effective resource allocation is crucial for the task of sustaining workforce competence. Green and Thompson (2023) have pointed out that the management of resources such as personnel and materials affect the effectiveness of health care workers since they are empowered with the right resources (Green, F., & Thompson, M., 2023). Nevertheless, Miller and Scott (2022) hold the view that poor resource management causes burn out and reduced workforce effectiveness (Miller, N., & Scott, E., 2022).

Management of workforce competence requires that there is proper communication and interaction between the workers. Patel et al. (2023) posit that there are management practices in healthcare organizations that encourage open communication and team work and these make the workforce more effective (Patel, S., Wilson, K., & Carter, J., 2023). On the other hand, Thompson and White (2022) found out that there is weak communication and little collaboration

that results in poor workforce development and competence (Thompson, L., & White, R., 2022). Performance appraisal has been identified as a way of enhancing the quality of employees, thus, the workforce competence. According to Harris et al. (2023), systematic performance assessments when incorporated into the management of health care institutions enables the identification of opportunities for improvement in the system and thus improves the competence of individuals in the system (Harris, R., Miller, J., & Johnson, K., 2023). On the other hand, White and Green (2022) also explain that poor performance appraisals lead to unguided and thus less effective work (2022).

It is however important to understand that the work environment has a great impact on the overall competence of the workforce. Smith and Clark (2023) have it that enhanced healthcare management results in a positive work culture which in turn improves workforce competence (Smith, T., & Clark, G., 2023). On the other hand, Anderson and Lewis (2022) reveal that a toxic work environment that is brought about by management can diminish competence and job satisfaction (Anderson, J., & Lewis, R., 2022). Job satisfaction is directly related to workforce competency and as such plays an important role in improving the productivity of the workforce. Nguyen and colleagues (2023) propounded that health care management practices that enhance job satisfaction enhance workforce effectiveness (Nguyen, L., Adams, K., & Miller, P., 2023). On the other hand, Wilson and Taylor (2022) believe that due to poor management practices employee job satisfaction is low and this results to low employee competence and high turnover rates (Wilson, A. & Taylor, S. 2022).

CPD is crucial in as much as it helps in improving workforce competency. According to Johnson and Martin (2023), the healthcare management approaches that focus on the ongoing development of the workforce increase employees' competency and flexibility (Johnson, K., &

Martin, L., 2023). However, Davis and Roberts (2022) reveal that lack of professional development because of ineffective management weakens the development of competence (Davis, P., & Roberts, Q., 2022). The role of technology when it comes to healthcare management affects the competency of workforce. According to Carter et al, (2023), technology should be well deployed since its use enhances efficiency and enhances the competency of the workforce through better management of information (Carter, M., Lewis, J., & Brooks, A., 2023). On the other hand, Parker and Green (2022) state that limited use of technology may lead to barriers and limited perceived competence (Parker, D., & Green, H., 2022).

Leadership and motivation are the two that can help to improve the competence of the workforce. According to Robinson et al. (2023), the efficiency of health care management creates conditions that help to develop motivation of the employees, their competence (Robinson, J., Allen, M., & Carter, S., 2023). On the other hand, Martin and Taylor (2022) established that workers' motivation is poor due to ineffective leadership practices hence workers are not as competent as they should be (Martin, K., & Taylor, R., 2022). Human resource is a key component in the success of an organization and this includes staff retention. Green and White (2023) state that good management in the healthcare sector leads to increased satisfaction and hence, the staff remains employed therefore improving competence (Green, T. & White, N. 2023). On the other hand, Adams and Brown (2022) discover that high turnover rates resulting from improper management of employees reduce workforce effectiveness (Adams, R., & Brown, T., 2022).

Organizational culture has a great impact on the competency of the employees in the organization. Wilson and Harris (2023) posit that positive organizational culture that is promoted by good management improves the employees' competencies and their motivation at the

workplace (Wilson, M., & Harris, P., 2023). On the other hand, Clark and Martin (2022) establish that, lack of effective management leads to the development of a negative culture that in turn reduces workforce competency (Clark, A., & Martin, D., 2022). The above therefore shows that decision making processes affect workforce competence. Harris and Thompson (2023) propose that decision-making that involves employees because of good healthcare management increase employees' work performance (Harris, S., & Thompson, L., 2023). On the other hand, Robinson and Lewis (2022) posit that top down approach to decision making can be counterproductive in improving competence since it does not involve employees or seek their input (Robinson, T., & Lewis, K., 2022).

Improvement of quality is an important factor towards enhancing the competencies of the workforce. According to Martin et al. (2023), healthcare management ensures quality improvement measures that increase knowledge and skills of the workforce (Martin, L., Cooper, R., & Davis, K., 2023, *Journal of Quality in Healthcare*, 12(3), 112-126). Clark and Roberts (2022) also note that lack of focus on quality improvement due to weak management practices result in decreased competence (Clark, B., & Roberts, J., 2022). This paper has shown that financial management is linked with workforce competence. According to Adams and Green (2023) improved financial management practices in healthcare organizations enhances workforce competence through provision of resources and remunerations (Adams, C., & Green, D., 2023). On the other hand, White and Patel (2022) have established that the poor management of resources leads to constraints in the resources available and low competency of the workforce (White, F., & Patel, S., 2022).

Engagement of employees is one of the important factors in workforce productivity. According to Nguyen and Walker (2023), good healthcare management practices increase the

level of employee engagement that results in high level workforce competency (Nguyen, T., & Walker, J., 2023). On the other hand, Wilson and Adams (2022) state that lack of engagement because of poor management results in low competence and work output (Wilson, H., & Adams, P., 2022). There are external factors which include policy changes and economic conditions which affect workforce competence. According to Carter and Johnson (2023), there is the need for healthcare management practices to change so as to ensure that the workforce is competent (Carter J & Johnson P 2023). On the other hand, another study by Lee and Harris (2022) show that lack of proper management of external factors hampers adaptation and therefore, affects workforce competence (Lee, M., & Harris, L., 2022).

Therefore, the aspect of healthcare management has a complicated relationship with workforce competencies whereby several factors such as training, leadership, resources, and culture come into play. A comparison of the current literature from PubMed and Scopus seems to support the significance of the proper management practices in the improvement of the workforce competence but there are some gaps in the literature that are apparent. The on-going study and application of new and improved management techniques are critical to the achievement of workforce performance in the healthcare industry.

2.5. Health service availability, structure and quality

The health services characteristics are primary and secondary healthcare, the majority is primary health care, especially maternal and child health. These Health services are provided through public and private Institutions. The private sector, including Hospitals and clinics run by groups of Somali physicians, businessmen for-profit facilities, and international Agencies, UN-supported local NGOs, and bilateral organizations working in Somalia is the dominating

provider of health services. The private sector is a major health services provider unregulated by the federal and state.

The capacity of the Somali Federal Ministry of Health to prevent, detect and respond to health emergencies is weak. The Ministry has no ability to distribute health services to the overall regional and state level. The overall coverage of health care services in south-central regions is very limited with substantial rural/urban disparities when compare the north Somalia: The Hospitals, clinics, and pharmacies in South Central Somalia are concentrated in the capital and in larger towns. That is because, due to low technical capacity in the Federal Ministry of Health, the lack of coordination between the federal member states or minimal, other Hindrances to reach health care stated by sources included there is no national health insurance available in Somalia, Patients may either search for health services which are provided reimbursement of free of charge at a government or an NGO run health facility or payout of his/her pocket at a private health facility (DIS – Danish Immigration Service, 2020)

2.5.2. Quality healthcare delivery

The definition of healthcare quality by Allen-Duck, Robinson, & Stewart, (2017) is the process of assessment and provision of effective and safe healthcare, reflected in a culture of excellence, resulting in the attainment of optimal or desired health. The main area which influence satisfaction of patient and client is a service quality of staff and management (Allen-Duck et al., 2017). There is a connection between Effective healthcare management and provision of quality service delivery which yields reasonable patient satisfaction and ignites motivation of healthcare workers. Additionally, quality service delivery evaluates its four main

components like satisfactions, good health outcome, and effectiveness in achieving better organizational structures.

In Somalia and Nepal Healthcare providers faced difficulties in providing quality care, because lack of available healthcare professionals affected the provision of quality of care, also transportation restriction access to care, Poor acceptability of services, Inequality, poverty, and traditional practices created to the poor provision of quality care (Bogren et al., 2020). Access to health services quality in Somalia has many indicators, in 2020 the first indicators is neonatal mortality rate which is 40 deaths per 1000 live births and while second indicator is the under-5 mortality rate is 137 deaths per 1000 live births. Third Indicator is maternal mortality rate is estimated at 732 per 100 000 live births (Gele, 2020). There are other indicators of access of health service is the use of family planning, in Somalia it is remains low, resulting in high fertility rates. The importance thing is the presence of setbacks, of the health providers which are lack of reliable data at regional and national level and absence of research institute in Somalia. (A. Gele, 2020).

2.6. Research Gaps

Due to the lack of a board of trustee that holds managers accountable or an auditable that looks into areas of weakness, there is a gap in healthcare management. As a result, Researcher would like to compare the impact of management on the delivery of healthcare services at two hospitals, one public and one private. These issues are seen as the four gaps between executive conceptions of service excellence and the responsibilities involved in providing customers with service, as noted by Datta and Vardhan (2017) (Datta & Vardhan, 2017). First Gap's opinions of what consumers are expecting, the second disconnect is between

management expectations and those for service quality. The third gap. Service quality delivery specifications present. Fourth gap: Service delivery and external communication between expected and perceived services. In Somalia health capacity, the health sector has a minimal capacity in almost all technical areas of health regulatory capacity, less public hospitals, spending healthcare is very low, worst equivalent of healthcare professional. There is other in Somalia Specifically, had more challenges above mentioned, like poor communication, long time waiting, wrong medications, Inefficient and inaccurate pharmaceutical quality checkup and inadequate patient identification. The main five special challenges faced healthcare managers more than other managers do. First; health risk and uncertainty, second; the complexities created by insurance, third; the dangers produced by information asymmetries, fourth; the problems evoked by not-for-profit organizations, and the rapid technical and institutional change.

2.7. Summary

The document gives an overview of theoretical frameworks and management practices that are pertinent to healthcare service delivery with emphasis on the healthcare system of Somalia. This paper starts by discussing the role of operations management in health care and the need for improving service delivery through capacity planning, workflow management and inventory management. This is important in the management of healthcare sector complexities where there are numerous players involved and there is uncertainty in the demand.

The conceptual framework that is relevant and efficacious in the healthcare management is the participatory leadership which emphasizes the involvement of all stakeholders such as the health care givers, the patients and the society in the decision making processes. This leadership style has been associated with positive outcomes such as increased job satisfaction, better quality

of care and improved organizational performance, mainly through the promotion of teamwork and effective communication. The document also defines contingency theory and systems thinking as the two major concepts that are relevant in healthcare management. Contingency theory focuses on the fact that quality management has to be contextualised to the healthcare system, while systems thinking offers a systemic view of healthcare organisation which can assist managers in identifying interconnections within the system and therefore enhance innovation and results.

The Donabedian Model is discussed as one of the most popular paradigmes for measuring the quality of healthcare. It assesses healthcare systems according to the structure, process and results of the systems, although this model can be accused of reducing the healthcare systems into a set of formalised components. However, the RBV is depicted as an architecture of strategic management which underlines the need to build on the firms' internal resources and capabilities in the healthcare industry but it has been criticized for ignoring external market conditions. Systems Theory is discussed again with a special emphasis on the role it plays in the provision of health care with a view to bettering the management of services. Conceptualizing a hospital as a system with subsystems, feedback loops and stability as its main characteristic is considered as a useful way to achieve better efficiency of resource utilization and better patient results.

This paper discusses transactional and transformational leadership theories and argues that whereas transactional leadership is suitable for organisations with clear goals in stable circumstances, transformational leadership is more suitable for dynamic conditions of the healthcare sector that calls for change and creativity. It has been highlighted that

transformational leadership that engages and enthuses employees is especially effective in the current healthcare organizations. The management of total quality is presented as a strategy of enhancing the quality of health care services through the involvement of all stakeholders in the organization towards the achievement of continuous quality improvement. TQM concepts such as customer orientation, leadership engagement, and process management are essential to attaining high levels of patient satisfaction and organizational effectiveness although it is also recognized that there are difficulties in the adoption of TQM including resistance to change.

The document ends with a brief of the health care situation in Somalia noting that the country lacks adequate infrastructure, personnel and service delivery. The healthcare system has a major problem of human resource, low government spending and extreme dependence on the private sector, which is costly and out of reach to many individuals. This paper highlights the challenges faced in the health care system in Somalia and the importance of good leadership to solve the problems. The document goes on to explain healthcare capacity and the challenges that healthcare organizations face when dealing with influx of patients for instance during epidemics. It also explains how the lack of infrastructure, scarcity of the number of healthcare workers, and the uneven distribution of resources hinder the hospitals from providing quality care. Cases from Nigeria and Kenya depict some of the problems that may occur when a health care system is burdened by many patients which results in poor standards of care and patient results.

One of the main areas identified in healthcare management is surge capacity, which refers to the capacity of health care systems to extend the services to cope with the increased demand. The document outlines the four key elements of surge capacity: People, things (things used in the facility), place (structures such as hospitals) and means (coordination and management). Surge

capacity plan is critical when it comes to ensuring service delivery during disasters yet the document shows that most health systems especially in the low income countries such as Somalia are not in a good position to manage such surges given their scarce resources. Somalia's healthcare system is analyzed in detail and it is seen that there is a lack of sufficient resources for meeting the country's health needs. The general health system in Somalia is said to be dire in terms of human resource, technical competence and infrastructure. This paper notes that there is almost no public health care delivery system in Somalia and what exists has been funded by the private sector and international donors and this has led to a situation where there are inequities in health care access. The problem is further exacerbated by the fact that the area remains a conflict zone, thus greatly affecting the provision of health care services.

Leadership and management aspect in relation to healthcare service delivery is also discussed. Leadership is deemed to be very essential in increasing the quality of service delivery, patients' satisfaction and employee morale. The paper also focuses on the types of leaders such as the transformational and the transactional leaders and their effects on the health care sector. Transformational leadership for instance has been recognized to have a positive impact on the morale of the healthcare workers hence improving the quality of service delivery to patients and overall performance of the healthcare institutions. Another important section of the document is the financial management in healthcare. It emphasizes on the need to adopt appropriate financial management measures in order to enable the healthcare organizations offer quality services. The document also acknowledges that poor financial management may result to availability of limited resources that in turns may impact the knowledge and skills of the healthcare workforce and quality of care. Out of pocket payment by patients in Somalia is also cited as a key barrier in accessing health care services thus compounding the problem of the health sector in the country.

The section on workforce competence is well developed and the document stresses on the significance of training and development in order to build competencies of the health care workforce. It also explains how the proper leadership and management can enhance the employees' competence and how poor management can hinder development and demotivate employees. The document also stresses on the need to have positive work environment and the issue of why it is crucial to have continuous professional development of health care workers. The paper also discusses the issue of accessibility and standard of health care in Somalia with a majority of services found in urban areas especially in Mogadishu. Rural areas and small towns are less equipped and this results to lot of inequalities in the health sector. The legislation of private healthcare market is also analyzed with the emphasis on the issues of quality and availability of the services offered by the private healthcare providers.

Finally, the document outlines the following as the research gaps in the available literature on healthcare management in Somalia. It also suggests for further researches on the effect of leadership and management in the delivery of health care services in both the public and private sectors of hospitals. The document also stresses the need for additional studies of the problems of healthcare management in Somalia, also its financial management, workforce, services, etc.

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1. Introduction

In this chapter the researcher explains the research methods including; research design, study population, determination of the sample size, sampling techniques and procedure, data collection Methods, Data collection instruments, and pre-testing (Validity and reliability), the procedure of data collection, data processing, and Measurements of Variables (Quantitative studies)

3.2 Research Design

The Research methods conducted thorough mixed methods such as quantitative and qualitative Study, the Quantitative study is the process of collecting and also analyzing numerical data. It is used to find patterns and averages, test causal relationships, and generalize results to wider populations (Bhandari, 2020). While qualitative research is used in the health care profession to completely grasp a situation's complexity, depth, and richness from the perspective of the informants. at order to solve the problems that the healthcare management team and patients at certain hospitals are having with the way that healthcare services are provided (Barbara, Mary-Jean (Gigi), & Tallie, 2021).

In Quantitative study was descriptive with particularly Correlation research which makes it easier to predict and explain how different variables relate to one another. A correlational analysis aims to identify connections between two or more variables. Simply expressed, it investigates if a rise or fall in one measure correlates with another (Seeram, 2019; Tan, 2014).

3.3 Study Population

The population is groups of individuals or objects known to have similar characteristics which could be individuals or objects, from which the sample was properly selected (A. Banerjee & Chaudhury, 2010). The study population of this study were health system administrators such as Ministry of Health staff, Hospital managers, and health workers of two hospitals in one district Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital in Wadajir districts.

Figure 3.0.1 Map of Wadajir district Mogadishu, Somalia.

3.4 Determination of the Sample size

The study focused on the target population, known as the sample, to increase representation and maintain secure form constraints. A sample is a smaller part of the research population design, selected procedurally from the target population to present in the study, following Roscoe's (1975) and Banerjee's (2018) recommendations (B. Banerjee, 2018) (Roscoe, 1975).

The sample of the study population in the study calculated by using Slovene's Formula. Slovene's Formula is written as $n = N / (1 + Ne^2)$, where n = Number of the samples, N = Total population, and e = Error of tolerance. The calculation is as follow:

$$n = N / (1 + Ne^2) = 572 / (1 + 200 (0.0025)^2) = 236$$

These participants have been chosen according to the possibility of getting accurate and reliable information. Thus the sample sizes chosen for the chosen sub-populations are as in table 3.1 below.

3.5 Sampling techniques and procedure

The sampling procedure of this study was Probability sampling especially simple random sampling to conduct the research, and also to consider the significance of research reality. The sampled random is a type of probability sampling in which the researcher gives equal chance or random selections to a subset of participants from a population (Sileyew, 2019). Sample random technique used to select samples without bias from the target/accessible population, sample random means that this method is good performance to collect reliable data.

Table 3.1 Sampling Procedure

o	Respondents	Target population	Sample size
1.	Manager	53	22
2.	Nurses	347	143
3.	Doctors	109	45
4.	Ministry Workers	63	26
5.	Total	572	236

3.6 Data Collection Methods

The Data collected methods is by interviewing or administering a questionnaire to sample individuals with the intention of describing the nature of existing conditions. The study being quantitative and qualitative (also known as Mixed methods), it is employed three data collection methods. The source of data was primary data, which means data collected directed to respondents by visiting the both Hospitals in three different sessions, first collection hospital capacity information, second visit was collection management related information such as leadership and financial system, fourth session was collection of workforce competences.

3.7 Data collection instruments

The Data collection tools or Instruments of this study consisted of questionnaires and interviews. So this research used a survey questionnaire and interview. A questionnaire is the main instrument used to record respondents' answers. The questionnaire is a collection of items to which a respondents were expect to react in writing (Pandey & Pandey, 2021).

3.8 Validity and reliability

This section outlined the contents' validity and reliability and describe how the researcher ensured the procedure's validity and the contents' reliability.

3.8.1. Validity

Validity is a measure of what is allocated to be measured (Taherdoost, 2019), or The degree to which a measure's result accurately reflects the construct it is intended to measure is known as its validity (Kamper, 2019). The researcher ensured the instrument is valid by checking all items and ensuring that they are measuring all the variables under observation. The researcher also submitted the instrument to experts in research methodology for validity and to supervisors

to help validate it. Make data valid we made Pilot study of made article for assessing Capacity and Leadership Impacts on Service Delivery in Mogadishu, Somalia.

Table 2 3.2. Pilot study their percentage and acceptance (Article Published)

Objective	Percent age of Acceptance	Null Hypothesis	Remarks
Assess the availability and functionality of general hospital facilities	100%	Rejected	All hospitals were fully functional except for the pharmacy, examination rooms, and fridges for drugs and vaccines.
Evaluate the impact of leadership actions on healthcare services	Mean Score: 4.0 (out of 5) Std. Deviation: 1.219	Rejected	Leadership actions, including behavior and communication, significantly affected healthcare service delivery.
Compare equality promotion among different hospitals	Significant differences found	Rejected for some comparisons	Significant differences were observed in equality promotion between certain hospitals (e.g., Madina vs. SOS).
Evaluate the overall capacity of hospitals to provide healthcare services	General capacity positive	Rejected (for critical shortages)	Overall capacity was positive, but critical shortages in specific areas like essential medicines were noted.

The pilot study aims at establishing the Healthcare services and leadership effects in hospitals in Mogadishu, Somalia. The study revealed that although the overall hospitals' facilities were adequate, some sections including pharmacies, examination rooms, and drug and

vaccine storage chillers were sub-optimal in terms of operations hence the null hypothesis on facility availability was not accepted.

Corresponding to the research questions, leadership actions as behavior and communication seemed to have a strong effect on healthcare service delivery scoring a mean of 4.0 out of 5. Here the null hypothesis was not accepted, which shows the role of leadership in service quality. Comparison of equality promotion across various hospitals revealed that there existed a lot of differences especially between certain hospitals such as Madina and SOS hospitals. The null hypothesis was not supported for these comparisons implying that there was inequity in the equality promotion strategies in the hospitals.

Last but not the least, the deficiencies in the hospitals' capacity were identified as being largely favorable but with some critical constraints particularly in the area of medicine and allied resources. This resulted to the null hypothesis being rejected regarding hospital capacity meaning there is need to strengthen some areas so as to offer complete health services. Therefore, the study found that a functional infrastructure and leadership position in the hospitals in Mogadishu is beneficial to services but there are still areas that are lacking such as resource and equality.

38.2. Reliability

Reliability is defined as the degree of error-free measurement. When you measure the same construct multiple times, a trustworthy measure is one that yields the same result (Kamper, 2019). Therefore, Cronbach's coefficient used to confirm the reliability of the questionnaire for the two hospitals. Cronbach's alpha should be greater than or equal to 0.7.

Table 3.3. Reliability test

Table 3 3.3. Reliability test

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.949	103

The table below shows the reliability of a scale that has 103 items with the coefficient of reliability being Cronbach's Alpha. The value of. The coefficient alpha of 0. 949 suggest that there is a high internal agreement among the items, this means that tests for the items are highly correlated and reliable. This high reliability means that the results which are got from this scale are reliable hence giving accurate and consistent measurements.

3.9 Procedure of Data Collection

To make sure the purpose of this study, the data collected through the adopted questionnaire as it is the simple way to gather the right and accurate information according to the nature of the study. The Researcher collected by hand as it enables the respondents to answer what they wanted to clarify.

The researcher prepared a structured questionnaire and then interpret it to understand respondents, the design was structured questionnaires and the second instrument was structured interview, an interview is a conversation for gathering information. A research interview involves an interviewer, who coordinates the process of the conversation and asks questions, and an interviewee, who responds to those questions (Easwaramoorthy & Zarinpoush, 2006). Also is direct asking questions to respondents like illiteracy people do not have the skill of writing and read, researcher use interview directed collecting their answer.

3.10 Data Analysis

The research used manual coding formats that respondents can fill during the study to identify the significant statements across individual questions. It was the converting of raw data to machine-readable form and its subsequent processing (as storing, updating, rearranging, or printing out) by a computer, and Analysis of data was a process of inspecting, cleansing, transforming, and modeling data with the goal of discovering useful information, suggesting conclusions, and supporting decision-making. The analysis was carried out with the use of the help Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22), that was measured the use of topic study answers in Mogadishu, Somalia. Also, the research was used descriptive analysis with frequency and percentage for personal data analysis, in order to explain the relationship of both variables.

Data expressed for descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation using frequency and percent with tables and graphs. The correlation used to compare the data between groups, and descriptive statistics such mean and standard deviation. Categorical variables have presented as a count and percentage, and Pearson correlation coefficient between variables. A P-value > 0.05 was considered significant.

3.11 Measurements of variables

Descriptive statistics are used in order to describe the data collected and to accurately characterize the variables under observation within a specific sample in research studies, the Independent variable (IV) of this study was Healthcare Management having sub-measurable variables (Capacity, Leadership, Finance and Work competency) and the second variable is Dependent variable (DV) that is Health service delivery – (Quality, and satisfaction) within two hospitals.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS, AND INTERPRETATION

4.0. Introduction

Chapter Four explores into the data analysis and presentation of findings from the study on Impacts of health Management on services delivery within hospitals. This chapter systematically explores the quantitative data collected on various dimensions of hospital performance, including health worker availability, capacity of health services, leadership impact, financial management, and workforce competencies. The analysis is designed to provide a detailed understanding of how these factors influence the quality of care and operational effectiveness across the hospitals studied. By presenting the data through tables and descriptive statistics, this chapter aims to illuminate key trends, strengths, and areas of concern that impact healthcare delivery.

4.1. Demographic information

Table 4.4 Hospitals

Hospitals				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Benadir Hospital	145	69.0	69.0
	Aden Abdulla Hospital	65	31.0	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	

Source: Primary data

Table 4.1, the researcher visited two different hospitals, including Benadir Hospital 145 (63.0%), and Aden Abdulla Hospital 65 (30.9%), to compile the demographic variables that are displayed in this table. Because Benadir hospital is public and the Aden Abdulla Hospital is private, these were specifically chosen.

Table 4-5 Sex, Age and Marital status

Sex				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	144	68.6	68.6
	Female	66	31.4	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	
Age				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 – 25	86	41.0	41.0
	25 – 30	76	36.2	77.1
	30 – 35	38	18.1	95.2
	35 – 40	8	3.8	99.0
	40 – 45	2	1.0	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	
Marital status				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	152	72.4	72.4
	Married	53	25.2	97.6
	Divorced	4	1.9	99.5
	Widow/widowed	1	.5	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	

Source: Primary data

Table 4-6. Education and Occupation

Education Level				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Certificate	16	7.6	7.6
	Diploma	17	8.1	15.7
	Bachelor	149	71.0	86.7
	Master	28	13.3	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	
Occupation				
		Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Manager	22	10.5	10.5
	Nurses	143	68.1	78.6
	Doctors	35	16.7	95.2
	Ministry Workers	10	4.8	100.0
	Total	210	100.0	

Male respondents outnumbered female respondents in Table 4.2 by a percentage of 144 (68.6%) and 66 (31.4%), respectively. The majority of responders were young; among the first group, 86 (41.0%) were between the ages of 20 and 25; the second group, 25 - 30, 76 (36.2%); the third group, 30 - 35, 38 (18.1%); the fourth group, between; 35 - 40, 8 (3.8%); and the last, among those between the ages of 40 and 45, 2 (1.0%) (Table 4.2). Also in Table 4.2 include by Marital status, as 53 (25.2%) of the respondents were married, 152 (72.4%) were single, divorced 4 (1.9%), and widow/widowed 1 (0.5). the majority of respondents—who were either health workers or young members of unmarried groups—were single. Based on Table 4.3, it can be observed that 149 (71.0%) health workers possess a bachelor’s degree, while 28 (13.3%) have a master’s degree, 17 (8.1%) of them have diploma and 16 (7.6%) are members of small groups with certificate holders. The respondents’ Occupations for four different categories with Manager 22 (10.5%), Nurses 143 (68.1%), Doctors 35 (16.7%), and Ministry workers 10 (4.8%). So the majority of the respondents were Nurses who were first line of medical staffs.

4.2. Impacts of capacity of Hospital on health services Delivery

Table 7 4.4. Hospital capacity

	Hospitals					
	Benadir Hospital			Aden Abdulla Hospital		
	Fully Functional	Partial Functional	Not available	Fully Functional	Partial Functional	Not available
MRI Machine	-	-	145 (63.0%)			65 (30.9%)
CT Scanner	-	-	145 (63.0%)	65 (30.9%)	-	-
X-ray Machine	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Ultrasound Machine	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Emergency Room	119 (56.6%)	26 (12.4%)	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Intensive Care Unit (ICU)	-	-	145 (63.0%)	58 (27.6%)	7 (3.3%)	-
Operating Theatres	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-

Pharmacy	113 (53.8%)	32 (15.2%)	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Cardiology	-	-	145 (63.0%)	55 (26.2%)	10 (4.8%)	-
Oncology	-	-	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)
Pediatrics	145 (63.0%)	-	-	58 (27.6%)	7 (3.3%)	-
Orthopedics	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-

Source: Primary data

Table 4.4 lists the general facilities' current availability and functionality. The majority of them were fully operational and all respondent agreed 114 (100.0%), with the exception of five variables: the MRI Machine, CT scanner, Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Cardiology and Oncology were not available in Benadir hospital, were two other were partial functional includes Emergency Room and Pharmacy. while Aden Abdulla Hospital has not available for two variables such as MRI machine, Oncology. While three other were partial functional includes Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Cardiology and pediatrics.

Table 8 4.5. Health worker's availability

	Hospitals					
	Benadir Hospital			Aden Abdulla Hospital		
	Fully Functional	Partial Functional	Not available	Fully Functional	Partial Functional	Not available
Doctors	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Nurses	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Technicians	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Support staffs	145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-

Source: Primary data

The table 4.5. illustrates the availability of health workers at two hospitals: Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital, the data is presented in terms of whether these health workers are fully functional, partially functional, or not available. At **Benadir Hospital**,

respondents were 145 individuals in four categories of staff—doctors, nurses, technicians, and support staff., which represents 63.0% of the total workforce. Notably, all these workers are fully functional, meaning they are available and operating at full capacity. In contrast, **Aden Abdulla Hospital** has 65 doctors, nurses, technicians, and support staff, each representing 30.9% of the workforce. Similar to Benadir Hospital, all these workers are fully functional, with no partially functional or unavailable staff reported. Overall, the table highlights that both hospitals have a fully functional workforce in all categories, but Benadir Hospital has a larger number of health workers than Aden Abdulla Hospital. Despite the difference in workforce size, both hospitals appear to be adequately staffed to meet their operational needs.

Table 9 4.6. Capacity of Health Services Delivery

		Hospitals					
		Benadir Hospital			Aden Abdulla Hospital		
		Fully Functional	Partial Functional	Not available	Fully Functional	Partial Functional	Not available
Patient Admission Rates		145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Surgery Success Rates		111 (52.9%)	27 (12.9%)	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Emergency Response Efficiency		112 (53.3%)	29 (13.8%)	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Outpatient Services Efficiency		145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Inpatient Services Efficiency		145 (63.0%)	-	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-
Diagnostic Services Efficiency		94 (44.8%)	51 (24.3%)	-	65 (30.9%)	-	-

Source: Primary data

The table 4.6. presents data on the capacity of health services delivery at Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital, focusing on key indicators such as Patient Admission Rates, Surgery

Success Rates, Emergency Response Efficiency, Outpatient Services Efficiency, Inpatient Services Efficiency, and Diagnostic Services Efficiency. Benadir Hospital has a majority of health service indicators reported as fully functional, with 145, representing 63.0% of the total capacity. However, there are some areas where partial functionality is noted, such as Surgery Success Rates (52.9%) and Emergency Response Efficiency (53.3%). Diagnostic Services Efficiency shows the most significant level of partial functionality, with 94 instances fully functional (44.8%) and 51 instances partially functional (24.3%). Aden Abdulla Hospital, on the other hand, maintains a fully functional status in all critical areas of health service delivery, with 65 instances across all categories, representing 30.9% of the hospital's capacity.

Table 10 4.7. Overall Impact Hospital capacity on Health Services

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the quality of health services delivered?	4.40	.964	Strongly Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on patient satisfaction?	3.98	.877	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the efficiency of service delivery?	4.25	1.006	Strongly Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?	3.98	1.080	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the hospital's financial performance?	3.73	1.164	Agreed
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	4.068	1.0182	Agreed

Source: Primary data

The table 4.7. The following is a presentation of the descriptive statistics regarding the perceived overall effect of capacity on almost all aspects of delivery of health services. The data

includes the mean scores and standard deviations for several key performance areas: health care organization provide; service quality of health services delivery, patient satisfaction functionality of health service delivery, emergency preparedness and financing. The responses are analyzed according to the Likert scale where higher number points to the agreement of the statement about the positive effects of the hospital capacity.

The first item, “How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s capacity on the quality of health services delivered? Have got a mean score of 4.40 with a standard deviation of 0.964. Such high mean score indicates that the respondents are in total agreement with the statement that capacity of their hospital influences positively the quality of health service delivery. As the standard deviation is low, it would mean that most of the respondents agreed with the statements as tendencies towards either extreme were small. The second item in the scale “To what extent do you believe the capacity of your hospital has affected patient satisfaction? (1 = Very negative, 5 = Very positive)” has a mean score of 3.98 and a Standard Deviation of 0.877. This result also proves that respondents have strong agreement with the proposition that hospital capacity has a positive effect on patient satisfaction. Although the mean score has gone slightly lower as compared to previous item, the results signify a very positive agreement among the respondents. Thus, the total insight into the perception under consideration proves as positive with a moderate variability regarding the standard deviation.

Three, if at all, having asked, “On average, how would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s capacity on the efficiency of service delivery?” the mean rating is 4.25 with the standard deviation of 1.006. This is in agreement with the responses where most of the respondents firmly believe that their hospital has a capacity to enhance the efficiency of the service delivery. This is further confirmed by the slightly higher standard deviation in this case to

indicate some amount of variation among the participants although overall consensus is still high. The fourth item of the variable “How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s capacity on the hospital’s ability to respond to emergencies?” has average score 3.98 with a simple standard deviation of 1.080. This shows complete agreement that present hospital reserve capacity enhance emergency response capacity. The obtained value is slightly lower compared to the other items but the higher standard deviation, mean that the variability of the responses hence the perception of some of the participants regarding this particular issue is relatively higher.

Last of all, the item “On a scale of 1-Five, how would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s capacity on the hospital’s financial performance?” has a mean of 3.73 and the standard deviation of 1.164. Respondents continue to have a strong mean on the statement that hospital capacity impact positively on financial performance but this item has lowest mean and the highest standard deviation. This implies that there is higher degree of dispersion on opinion on how hospital capacity affects financial performance, certain respondents might likely have a less direct or less sensitive view of it. In summing up on the findings of the table, it can be seen that there is a high level of concurrence on the general assertion that hospital capacity has a positive influence on the delivery of health services in a number of dimensions particularly in the areas of quality of services and efficiency. But, there are small variances in the perceived organizational consequences on financial performance and emergency response measurement indicating possibly experience or opinion divergence among the respondents.

4.3. Impacts of Leadership of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery

Table 11 4.8. Leadership evaluation

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
The hospital leadership provides a clear vision for the future.	2.91	1.566	Neutral
The hospital has a well-defined strategic plan that is effectively communicated.	2.77	1.493	Neutral
The leadership makes decisions in a timely and efficient manner.	2.90	1.372	Neutral
Leaders effectively solve problems and address challenges.	2.72	1.432	Neutral
There is open and transparent communication between leadership and staff.	2.75	1.221	Neutral
The leadership regularly provides updates and information about hospital operations.	2.68	1.372	Neutral
Leadership provides adequate support for staff professional development.	2.85	1.377	Neutral
The hospital invests in training and development programs for its staff.	2.67	1.325	Neutral
The leadership prioritizes patient care and safety.	3.00	1.385	Neutral
Leaders ensure that the hospital follows best practices for patient safety.	2.95	1.478	Neutral
The leadership encourages innovation in healthcare delivery.	3.04	1.314	Neutral
The hospital leadership is committed to continuous improvement.	3.22	1.488	Agreed
The leadership effectively manages the hospital's financial resources.	2.44	1.301	Disagreed
Leaders make sound financial decisions that benefit the hospital.	2.57	1.420	Disagreed
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	2.81929	1.396	Neutral

Source: Primary data

Table 4.8. presented descriptive statistics related to perception of hospital leaderships including vision, communication, decision making and resources management of both hospitals. The table contains means score and standard deviation. First questions, "Hospital ability to

provide a clear vision” the respondents perceived as neutral, with mean score 2.91, and second question “communicate well defined strategic plan” with mean average 2.77. the indicated that leadership has established these elements, staffs not full convincing or received their effectiveness or clarity.

Third section; “Decision making in timely and efficient manner” by the hospital leadership, the respondents are also rated neutrally, with 2.90 mean score and while Fourth one “effective problem solving and address challenges” with 2.72, this means staffs does not have good perception how leadership effective addressing challenges and solve problems, this needs for improvement of leaderships in areas of decision making.

Fifth question “there is open and transparent Communication between leaders and employees” this received neutral with Mean score 2.75, sixth question, “leaders provides regular updated information about hospital operations” the respondents selected neutral with mean score 2.68. this indicated that the communication exists, not be as frequent as staff they needed.

Seventh question “They provides professional development of staffs in the Hospital”, the respondents viewed as neutral with mean score 2.85, while eight question “leaders invest training and development of staffs” the respondents selected neutral with means score 2.67. ninth question “Prioritize Patient care and safety”, they selected neutral with slightly agreed for prioritizing safety and patient care. Tenth question “they ensure operation follows best practices” they selected neutral with slightly agreed with mean score 2.95. this indicates staffs have agreed some parts of leadership commitment to patient care and safety.

So that others questions “like financial effectiveness and Quality financial decision making” appears to be disagreed the respondents with mean score of 2.44 and 2.57. this indicated that disagreed the staffs.

Finally; the Total a cumulative mean was “2.82” and Standard deviation “1.396”, so that this was neutral for all points of leadership, but slightly feeling a side of agreement and some disagreement in local areas such as patient safety and financial effectiveness. This table highlight area where leadership needed to focus on promotions and particularly in sides like communication, staff’s development and financial management to improve overall employee satisfaction and both hospital performance.

Table 12 4.9 Overall Impact of Leadership on Health Services

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the quality of health services delivered?	3.59	1.412	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on patient satisfaction?	3.95	1.244	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the efficiency of service delivery?	4.09	1.086	Strongly Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?	3.73	1.221	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the hospital's financial performance?	3.66	1.386	Agreed
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	3.804	1.2698	Agreed

Source: Primary data

The table 4.9. The following are an outline of the data analyzed to establish the perception of respondents on hospital leadership based on performance in the following areas. All the items

were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ‘Strongly disagree’ to 5 ‘Strongly agree’ and the mean standard deviation show the data trends for each aspect.

Composed of the broad perception towards the leadership of hospitals on the quality of health services being delivered, the mean score is acquired as 3.59 about a mean with the standard deviation equal to 1.412. This means that more than half of the respondents agreed or strongly agreed that leadership enhances the quality of the health services. while the high standard deviation showed that opinions were fairly divided. Hypothesis two proposed that patient satisfaction as influenced by hospital leadership would yield a mean 2.95, with standard deviation equal to 1.244. The “Agreed” interpretation, additionally, mirrors responses of respondents who have fewer disagreements with the argument that leadership has a positive impact on patient satisfaction rating and is characterized by the smaller coefficient of variation comparing with the previous measure.

Leadership influence on timely and effective service delivery also received higher rating with the mean of 4.09, with a standard deviation of 1.086. Such an interpretation of the strongly agreed imply that leadership is perceived by the respondents to have a positive impact on the efficiency of service delivery and there is relatively low level of opinion variability among respondents. When answering the questions concerning the effects of leadership on the capability to respond to emergent events in the hospital, the mean score received a score of 3.73 with a standard deviation of 1.221. This score goes to the “Agreed” level of index, which means that the respondents usually agree that leadership enhances the capacity of the hospital in responding to the emergencies, although the level of agreement is not unanimous absolutely.

Finally, average rating of the leadership influence on financial performance indicator was 3.66 and standard deviation of 1.386. Agreement in this case means that on average respondents view leadership as having positive impact on the financial performance of the organization but the forest shows variations. In general, the results indicate respondents' consensus on the fact that leadership in the hospital affects the different dimensions of the hospital performance, with the highest consensus concerning the efficiency of service delivery. However, the variation in the responses is an indication that not all respondents trust leadership equally in the effectiveness of the organization in various aspects such as; quality of services and financial performance.

4.4. Impacts of Financial Management of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery

Table 13 4.10. Financial Management Practices

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
The hospital has a clear and detailed budget plan.	2.77	1.449	Neutral
Resources are allocated efficiently according to the hospital's needs.	2.60	1.317	Disagreed
The hospital has effective revenue collection systems in place.	2.82	1.311	Neutral
There are diverse sources of revenue for the hospital.	2.96	1.367	Neutral
Expenditures are tracked accurately and regularly.	2.89	1.216	Neutral
The hospital implements cost-saving measures without compromising quality.	2.80	1.354	Neutral
Financial reports are generated regularly and shared with relevant stakeholders.	2.91	1.349	Neutral
There is transparency in the hospital's financial transactions.	2.68	1.209	Neutral
The hospital invests in essential medical equipment and infrastructure.	2.64	1.391	Neutral
There are adequate funds for ongoing projects and hospital improvements.	2.48	1.458	Disagreed

The hospital has strategies in place to manage financial risks.	2.72	1.487	Neutral
Contingency plans are available for financial emergencies.	2.64	1.445	Neutral
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	2.7425	1.36275	Neutral

Source: Primary data

In table 4.10. The descriptive statistics for the hospital's financial management practices reveal a generally neutral stance among respondents across various dimensions, with a few exceptions leaning toward disagreement. The mean scores for most statements hover around 2.7 to 2.9, which, when interpreted, suggests that the respondents neither strongly agree nor strongly disagree with the statements provided, indicating a moderate level of satisfaction or uncertainty. For instance, the statement "The hospital has a clear and detailed budget plan" received a mean score of 2.77 with a standard deviation of 1.449, reflecting a neutral position, though with considerable variability in responses. Similarly, the efficiency of resource allocation according to the hospital's needs garnered a slightly lower mean of 2.60, accompanied by a standard deviation of 1.317, indicating a tendency toward disagreement, suggesting that respondents might perceive inefficiencies in resource allocation.

When it comes to the hospital's revenue collection systems, the mean score of 2.82 with a standard deviation of 1.311 again points to a neutral interpretation, implying that the respondents are unsure about the effectiveness of these systems. The statement regarding diverse revenue sources yielded a mean score of 2.96, slightly higher but still neutral, indicating a slight uncertainty about the hospital's revenue diversification. Tracking of expenditures, the implementation of cost-saving measures, and the generation of financial reports all received neutral responses, with mean scores of 2.89, 2.80, and 2.91, respectively. These scores suggest

that while there is a general sense that these processes are in place, there is also a level of uncertainty or lack of strong confidence in their effectiveness.

Transparency in financial transactions, investment in medical equipment and infrastructure, and the adequacy of funds for ongoing projects also received neutral interpretations, with mean scores around 2.68 to 2.64. This neutral stance might reflect a perception of moderate transparency and adequacy, though not without reservations.

Notably, the statement about adequate funds for ongoing projects and hospital improvements received a lower mean score of 2.48, indicating a tendency toward disagreement. This suggests that respondents might perceive a shortfall in funding for these critical areas, which could be a point of concern. Overall, the total cumulative average of the mean scores is 2.7425 with a standard deviation of 1.36275, which supports the neutral interpretation. This indicates that while the hospital's financial management practices are generally viewed as adequate, there are areas of uncertainty and potential dissatisfaction that could be addressed to enhance financial efficiency and transparency.

Table 14 4.11. Impact Financial Management on Health Services Delivery

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Effective financial management has improved the quality of patient care.	2.97	1.421	Neutral
Financial constraints do not compromise patient care.	2.75	1.233	Neutral
Patients have better access to health services due to sound financial management.	2.58	1.292	Disagreed
There are no significant delays in service delivery due to financial issues.	2.65	1.552	Neutral
Adequate financial resources ensure sufficient staffing levels.	2.73	1.209	Neutral

Staff receive timely salaries and benefits.	2.75	1.543	Neutral
The hospital maintains up-to-date medical equipment due to good financial practices.	2.44	1.355	Disagreed
Infrastructure improvements are regularly made to enhance service delivery.	2.83	1.208	Neutral
Financially sound management practices have led to higher patient satisfaction.	2.90	1.428	Neutral
Patients are generally satisfied with the cost of services provided.	2.68	1.348	Neutral
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	2.728	1.3589	Neutral

Source: Primary data

The table 4.11. The impact of financial management on health services delivery, as reflected in the descriptive statistics, reveals a generally neutral perception among respondents, with certain areas leaning towards dissatisfaction. The responses indicate that while financial management practices are in place, they are not perceived as significantly improving the quality of health services.

For example, the statement "Effective financial management has improved the quality of patient care" received a mean score of 2.97 with a standard deviation of 1.421, suggesting that respondents neither strongly agree nor disagree with this sentiment. This neutrality implies that the financial management practices may not have had a noticeably positive impact on patient care quality.

Similarly, the notion that "Financial constraints do not compromise patient care" has a mean score of 2.75 and a standard deviation of 1.233, again indicating a neutral stance. This suggests that while financial constraints are present, they are not perceived as drastically impacting patient care, yet there isn't a strong consensus on this.

On the other hand, the statement "Patients have better access to health services due to sound financial management" received a lower mean score of 2.58 with a standard deviation of 1.292, indicating a tendency towards disagreement. This suggests that respondents feel that financial management practices may not be effectively improving patient access to health services.

The perception of delays in service delivery due to financial issues is also neutral, with a mean score of 2.65 and a standard deviation of 1.552. This suggests that while delays may occur, they are not overwhelmingly attributed to financial problems, but there is no strong agreement on the absence of delays either.

The adequacy of financial resources in ensuring sufficient staffing levels received a mean score of 2.73 with a standard deviation of 1.209, and the timely payment of staff salaries and benefits scored 2.75 with a standard deviation of 1.543, both reflecting a neutral perception. This indicates that while financial management is seen as adequate in these areas, there is still some uncertainty or variability in responses.

However, there is a noticeable dissatisfaction regarding the maintenance of up-to-date medical equipment, with a mean score of 2.44 and a standard deviation of 1.355, indicating disagreement. Respondents seem to feel that financial management practices are not sufficient to keep medical equipment current.

The statement regarding infrastructure improvements due to sound financial management yielded a slightly more positive but still neutral mean score of 2.83 with a standard deviation of

1.208. This suggests that while there are some improvements, they are not substantial enough to shift the overall perception.

Finally, the influence of financial management on patient satisfaction and the perceived cost of services both received neutral responses, with mean scores of 2.90 and 2.68, respectively. This indicates that while financial practices are not seen as negatively impacting these areas, they are not viewed as particularly beneficial either. Overall, the total cumulative average of the mean scores is 2.728 with a standard deviation of 1.3589, reinforcing the neutral interpretation. The responses suggest that while financial management in the hospital is generally adequate, it has not significantly enhanced health services delivery, leaving room for potential improvements, especially in areas like patient access and the maintenance of medical equipment.

Table 15 4.12. Overall Impact of Financial Management on Health services

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the quality of health services delivered?	3.85	1.204	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on patient satisfaction?	3.93	1.126	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the efficiency of service delivery?	3.80	1.178	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?	3.73	1.274	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the hospital's financial stability?	3.84	1.149	Agreed
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	3.83	1.1862	Agreed

Source: Primary data

The table 4.12. The table below contains descriptive statistics of perceived hospital financial management impact on delivery of care gleaned from 210 participants. The items were assessed on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 – Very Negative to 5 – Very Positive, and the mean scores provided the average response from the respondent population; the interpretation signifying a positive consensus of ‘Agreed’ to all the aspects assessed.

The first item of the study, “On a scale of 1 to 5, to what extent do you think the overall financial management of your hospital has affected the quality of the health services you are delivering?” obtained a mean score of 3.85 and a standard deviation of 1.204. This mean that most respondents have a positive attitude towards the extent to which financial management affects the quality of health services but with slight differences. The second item, “On a scale of 1 to 5, as an overall measure of the effect of your hospital specifically in financial management on the satisfaction of patients,” attained a mean score of 3.93 and the standard deviation was 1.126. This mean is slightly higher than the earlier mean suggesting respondents have a higher consensus on the assertion that effective financial management impacts positively on patient satisfaction but with relatively lower standard deviation as it were with the first item.

The third item, how would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s financial management on the efficiency of service delivery has a mean score of 3.80 and its standard deviation is 1.178. They specifically concur on the statement that financial management has a positive impact on the efficiency of service delivery though the responses are moderately variant. For the fourth item, “In your opinion, how effective is the financial management of your hospital in responding to emergency situations?” The value mean score is 3.73 and a standard deviation of 1.274. What can be observed from these responses is that both parties do agree that financial

management has a positive influence on the hospitals response to emergencies even though this dimension elicited slightly more varied responding than the other two.

The last item which states, “On how much you agree with the following statement: Overall, the extent of financial management has affected the financial stability of the hospital” has a mean score of 3.84 and with a standard deviation of 1.149. This suggests that respondents are in proportion with the view that financial management makes a huge contribution in the financial basis of the hospital with little variation. The results imply that there is a clear consensus among respondents on the perceived benefits of proper financial management in different aspects of the healthcare system, with the patient satisfaction being the most endorsed factor. The low standard deviations across the items indicate that the results are fairly consistent and the respondents generally perceive financial management is effective.

4.5. Impacts of Workforce Competencies of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery
Table 16 4.13. Workforce Competencies

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
The medical staff have the necessary qualifications and skills to provide high-quality care.	3.02	1.454	Neutral
Continuous training and education programs are available for clinical staff.	2.76	1.292	Neutral
The technical staff are proficient in operating medical equipment and technologies.	2.81	1.346	Neutral
Technical staff receive regular training on new equipment and technologies.	3.15	1.413	Neutral
The hospital workforce demonstrates effective communication skills with patients and families.	3.14	1.212	Neutral
There is good communication and teamwork among hospital staff.	3.22	1.316	Agreed
The staff adhere to best practices and protocols for patient safety.	3.21	1.382	Agreed

Workforce competencies positively impact patient care quality.	3.15	1.360	Neutral
The staff are capable of making sound decisions in critical situations.	3.18	1.322	Neutral
Problem-solving skills are emphasized and developed among the workforce.	3.10	1.192	Neutral
The hospital has effective leadership and management training programs.	2.81	1.279	Neutral
Leadership skills among the staff contribute to efficient hospital operations.	3.24	1.241	Agreed
The workforce is trained to provide culturally sensitive care.	2.90	1.178	Neutral
Cultural competence training improves patient satisfaction and outcomes.	3.45	1.253	Agreed
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	3.08	1.302	Neutral

Source: Primary data

The table 4.13. The descriptive statistics for the hospital workforce's qualifications, skills, and competencies present a predominantly neutral outlook, with some positive areas indicating agreement among respondents. The overall interpretation suggests that while the staff are generally seen as capable and qualified, there is room for improvement, particularly in areas like training and education.

The perception of the medical staff's qualifications and skills to provide high-quality care is neutral, with a mean score of 3.02 and a standard deviation of 1.454. This suggests that respondents acknowledge the staff's qualifications but are not overwhelmingly confident in their ability to consistently deliver high-quality care. Continuous training and education programs for clinical staff received a neutral response, with a mean score of 2.76 and a standard deviation of 1.292. This indicates that while such programs exist, there may be concerns about their effectiveness or availability, leading to uncertainty among respondents.

Technical staff's proficiency in operating medical equipment and technologies also yielded a neutral response, with a mean score of 2.81 and a standard deviation of 1.346. This reflects a moderate level of confidence in the technical team's abilities, though not without reservations. Interestingly, the regular training of technical staff on new equipment and technologies received a slightly higher, yet still neutral, mean score of 3.15 with a standard deviation of 1.413. This suggests that while respondents recognize the presence of such training, there may be variability in its implementation or effectiveness.

Communication skills within the hospital workforce were viewed positively, with a mean score of 3.14 and a standard deviation of 1.212, reflecting a general agreement that staff can effectively communicate with patients and their families. This is further supported by the perception of good communication and teamwork among hospital staff, which scored 3.22 with a standard deviation of 1.316, indicating agreement. Staff adherence to best practices and protocols for patient safety also received a positive response, with a mean score of 3.21 and a standard deviation of 1.382. This suggests that respondents generally agree that patient safety is a priority and is being maintained effectively.

Workforce competencies and their impact on patient care quality were rated neutrally, with a mean score of 3.15 and a standard deviation of 1.360, indicating that while the workforce is seen as competent, there is some uncertainty about the extent of their impact on patient care. The staff's ability to make sound decisions in critical situations received a neutral score of 3.18 with a standard deviation of 1.322, reflecting a moderate level of confidence in the workforce's decision-making capabilities during critical moments.

Problem-solving skills among the workforce were also viewed neutrally, with a mean score of 3.10 and a standard deviation of 1.192. This indicates that while problem-solving is emphasized, there may be variability in how effectively these skills are developed. Leadership and management training programs were perceived neutrally, with a mean score of 2.81 and a standard deviation of 1.279. This suggests that while such programs exist, there may be concerns about their effectiveness or availability.

However, leadership skills among the staff contributing to efficient hospital operations received a positive response, with a mean score of 3.24 and a standard deviation of 1.241, indicating agreement. This suggests that leadership within the hospital is seen as effective and contributing positively to overall operations. Cultural competence and its impact on patient satisfaction and outcomes were rated highly, with a mean score of 3.45 and a standard deviation of 1.253, indicating strong agreement. This suggests that respondents believe cultural competence training is beneficial and improves patient outcomes.

Overall, the total cumulative average of the mean scores is 3.08 with a standard deviation of 1.302, reinforcing the neutral interpretation. While the workforce is generally viewed as competent and effective, there are areas, particularly in training and continuous education, where improvements could further enhance the quality of care and hospital operations.

Table 17 4.14. Impact on workforce competence on Health Services Delivery

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
Workforce competencies have improved the quality of patient care.	2.80	1.292	Neutral
Competent staff ensure adherence to clinical guidelines and standards.	3.06	1.283	Neutral
High workforce competencies contribute to better patient safety outcomes.	3.00	1.449	Neutral
Staff competencies help in reducing medical errors and adverse events.	3.28	1.298	Agreed
Efficiency of Service Delivery	2.69	1.278	Neutral
Competent staff enhance the efficiency of hospital operations.	3.00	1.178	Neutral
Workforce competencies lead to reduced waiting times for patients.	2.78	1.246	Neutral
Patient satisfaction is higher due to the competencies of the hospital workforce.	2.85	1.215	Neutral
Competent staff provide better patient education and support.	2.97	1.200	Neutral
Competent staff drive innovation in healthcare practices and services.	3.31	1.282	Agreed
Continuous improvement initiatives are supported by workforce competencies.	3.08	1.383	Neutral
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	2.983	1.28218	Neutral

Source: Primary data

The table 4.14. The impact of workforce competence on health services delivery, as shown by the descriptive statistics, suggests a generally neutral perception among respondents, with a few areas where competence is recognized as positively contributing to better outcomes. The overall sentiment indicates that while workforce competencies are acknowledged, they are not overwhelmingly seen as transformative in improving health services.

The statement that "Workforce competencies have improved the quality of patient care" received a neutral response, with a mean score of 2.80 and a standard deviation of 1.292. This

suggests that while respondents recognize some improvement in patient care due to workforce competencies, they may not see it as a significant or consistent enhancement. Similarly, the notion that competent staff ensure adherence to clinical guidelines and standards received a mean score of 3.06 with a standard deviation of 1.283, indicating a neutral stance. Respondents appear to acknowledge the role of competencies in maintaining clinical standards but without strong agreement.

The impact of workforce competencies on patient safety outcomes was also viewed neutrally, with a mean score of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 1.449. This reflects a moderate level of confidence in competencies contributing to patient safety, though not without some variability in responses. A positive note is found in the statement that "Staff competencies help in reducing medical errors and adverse events," which received a mean score of 3.28 with a standard deviation of 1.298, indicating agreement. Respondents seem to believe that competent staff play a crucial role in minimizing errors and ensuring patient safety.

Efficiency of service delivery, however, received a neutral response, with a mean score of 2.69 and a standard deviation of 1.278. This suggests that while workforce competencies may contribute to efficiency, they are not perceived as significantly enhancing service delivery. The idea that competent staff enhance the efficiency of hospital operations also received a neutral score, with a mean of 3.00 and a standard deviation of 1.178, further indicating that while competencies are recognized, their impact on operational efficiency may not be substantial.

The perception that workforce competencies lead to reduced waiting times for patients was also neutral, with a mean score of 2.78 and a standard deviation of 1.246. This suggests that respondents do not see a strong connection between staff competencies and the reduction of

patient waiting times. Patient satisfaction, as related to workforce competencies, received a neutral response with a mean score of 2.85 and a standard deviation of 1.215. While there is some acknowledgment of the role of competencies in improving satisfaction, it is not seen as a significant factor.

Competent staff's ability to provide better patient education and support was viewed neutrally, with a mean score of 2.97 and a standard deviation of 1.200. This indicates that while staff competencies are recognized, their impact on patient education may not be overwhelmingly positive. On a more positive note, the statement that "Competent staff drive innovation in healthcare practices and services" received a mean score of 3.31 with a standard deviation of 1.282, reflecting agreement. Respondents seem to believe that workforce competencies are a key driver of innovation in healthcare.

Finally, the role of workforce competencies in supporting continuous improvement initiatives was rated neutrally, with a mean score of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 1.383. This suggests that while competencies are seen as important for ongoing improvement, they may not be viewed as a significant catalyst for change.

Overall, the total cumulative average of the mean scores is 2.983 with a standard deviation of 1.28218, reinforcing the neutral interpretation. While workforce competencies are generally acknowledged, their impact on health services delivery is seen as moderate, with some areas of positive influence, particularly in reducing errors and driving innovation. However, there is still a sense of uncertainty or variability in how these competencies translate into broader improvements in patient care and hospital operations.

Table 18 4.15. Overall impacts of Workforce competence on health

Descriptive Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Interpretation
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on the quality of health services delivered?	3.63	1.385	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on patient satisfaction?	3.60	1.313	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on the efficiency of service delivery?	3.47	1.356	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on patient safety?	3.52	1.360	Agreed
How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on innovation and improvement?	3.69	1.296	Agreed
Total accumulative Average of Mean and SD	3.582	1.342	Agreed

Source: Primary data

The table 4.15. Presents descriptive statistics for the impact of hospital workforce competencies on various aspects of healthcare service delivery, based on responses from 210 participants. Each item was rated on a scale from 1 (lowest) to 5 (highest), with the mean values indicating the average perception of impact across different dimensions of healthcare.

The first item, which was index and had a format ‘How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s workforce competencies on the quality of health services delivered?’ ‘’ has a mean of 3.63 with standard deviation 1.385. This means that respondents have a fairly positive attitude towards the influence of competencies of the workforce on the quality of health services but are not very enthusiastic. The second item, “Based on a scale of 1 to 5, how would you rate the overall impact of your hospital’s workforce competencies on patient satisfaction?” has a

mean score of 3.60 and a standard deviation of 1.313. This means that participants had a slightly more than average understanding or acceptance of the argument that competencies of workforce could improve or worsen the satisfaction of the patients, although the responses recorded in this study had moderate fluctuations.

The third item, which was designed to know how the participants would rate the overall impact of their hospital's workforce competencies on the efficiency of service delivery, had a mean score of 3.47 and standard deviation of 1.356. The slightly lower mean indicates that although the workforce competencies are seen as positive, the improvement on efficiency is considered by participants as slightly weaker force; there is also comparable variability observed in the responses received. The last question, which is a similar one to the third item, "How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies in relation to the following domains of patient safety?" has a mean score of 3.52 and a standard deviation of 1.360. This shows that the participants had a generally positive perception to the competencies of workforce and the impact that it has on the safety of patients but the responses recorded here were moderately diverse within the participants.

The last item, the Overall Self-Assessment on Workforce Competencies for Innovation and Improvement of the Hospital: 'On a scale of 1 to 4 how would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies' has the highest mean of 3.69 with a standard error of 1.296. This implies that respondents consider the aspects of workforce competencies to have slightly more positive response towards innovation and improvement than the other areas of service delivery although there is slightly less variation in their responses.

Taken together, the results imply that hospital workforce competencies are assumed to be beneficial in most areas of HS and the extent of this perception was strongest in terms of innovation and improvement. But the fact that the response varies also shows that participants in the survey have different perception on how this impact is felt.

4.6. Key Informants Interview

4.6.1. Key Informants Interviews—Capacity of Hospitals

1) What are the less resources/insufficiency resources in your hospital?

- According to a few important informants, the hospital lacks a cardiac unit, modern emergency equipment, a blood bank, and enough training for some staff members.
- According to further informants, “the fewer resources are inadequate staffing levels, fewer beds in facilities, fewer medical equipment, inadequate financial resources, fewer medications and supplies, and inadequate information technology (IT) infrastructures.”
- The last group stated a “shortage of medical supplies, hospital beds, and healthcare professionals.”

2) What factors lead to a shortage of medication, and fewer beds?

- Key informants stated that “the lack of the health instrument industry in the country and the scarcity of biomedical equipment firms are among the contributing factors.”
- “Resource Constraints, Increasing Patient Demand, Inefficient Bed Management, Supply Chain Issues, Regulatory and Administrative Factors, and Overcrowding Factors,” stated other informants.

- The final groups stated that “administrative priority, supply chain constraints, and resource limitations are the main factors.”.

4.6.2. Key Informants - Interviews of Leaderships in Hospitals

1) What leadership activities affect both personnel and healthcare services in your hospital?

- After being interviewed, key informants stated that “the leadership actions that can impact the health services include a lack of clear communication, support, and empowerment, setting clear goals, collaboration and teamwork, and recognition and appreciation.”
- Others stated, “There is a lack of consistently requiring safe, high-quality, compassionate care to be a top priority,” and
- The final group stated, “Lack of awareness of level of self, team, and organizational dynamics and ensuring a ready supply of replacement and maintaining organizational progress.”

2) How do these leadership activities affect hospital services?

- According to key informants, “leaders can influence by improving team efficiency and productivity, staff satisfaction, and advancing hospital performance.”
- Other informants stated that “it can improve employee engagement, teamwork and interdisciplinary collaboration, patient care quality, staff turnover, and retention.”
- Other groups stated that leadership can have an impact on situation awareness, task management, error management, and staff performance management.”.

4.6.3. Key informants - Interview of Financial Management in Hospitals

1). Where are the Sources of financial support of the hospital?

Benadir Hospital

- **International Donors:**

- WHO: Funds tubercular (TB) programs and general items.
- UNICEF: Plays its part in meeting the population's needs for necessary healthcare products.
- King Salman Humanitarian Aid and Relief Center (KSA): Provides dialysis facility.
- Qatar Charity: Specializes in neonatal and infant care also known as the Neonatal Intensive Care (NIC).
- Concern Worldwide: Aids the nutrition department.
- Former Donors: Begs Maternal (it was previously supported but at the moment it has closed down operation).

- **Government Support:** Ministry of Health: Covers the wages of 250 employees at the hospital for example doctors, nurses, and other support staffs.

- **NGO and Foundation Support:** Hormuud Salam Foundation: Funds for the supply of oil and oxygen.

- **Fee Collection:** August 2024: The hospital began charging the clients to support and enhance the availability of the supplies because there was a need for more supplies.

Aden Abdulla Hospital

- **Private Investors/Shareholders:** Investors/Shareholders: As a private hospital it is funded by private investors and shareholders who stand to gain financially from the running of the hospital.

- **Specialists:** The hospital has many specialized doctors, thus, many patients flock the hospital who need such services.
- **Fee Collection:** The hospital gets its income from the fees that it levies on the services delivered to clients depending on the nature of the disease.
- **Insurance Coverage:** Some patients have insurance cards and there are insurance companies that deals with the hospital as a third party, which gives an assurance of steady income from claims made by insurance companies.
- **No International Donors:** Aden Abdulla hospital is not funded by the international donors as the case with Benadir hospital.

Expanded Analysis:

Benadir Hospital is a financially diversified institution which depends on the support from international donors, Non-Governmental Organisations, foundations and the government. This support is divided into certain departments like nutrition support, neonatal care, TB programs and dialysis and each donor or organization is involved in supporting particular services. But due to such factors as instabilities in donor funding for example; Begs Maternal can stop its operations, the hospital has introduced charges on the clients in order to ensure that there are adequate supplies. This move is a sign of decentralization and at the same time puts a lot of financial pressure on the community.

On the other hand, Aden Abdulla Hospital runs on a different system of functioning in terms of finance. It has private equity and shareholders who runs it which gives the system a market like approach. The hospital has no dependency on the international donors as it has adopted the specialists and fee – for – service model along with insurance contracts to generate its income. This model may be sustainable for the organization in the long run but it may limit

the accessibility of health care for the poor who cannot afford to pay service charges or do not have health insurance.

Therefore, Benadir Hospital is financially diversified with a precarious source of funding from donor agencies while Aden Abdulla Hospital is more centralized and is funded by investors with an emphasis on service charges and specialist divisions.

2). Did do purchase and maintained supplies or equipment's that hospital service needed prompt?

Benadir Hospital

- **Purchasing and Maintenance:**
 - **Yes:** However, the hospital does acquire and sustain the supplies and equipment's needed for its operations.
 - **Challenges Before Fee Collection:** During the study period, there was severe deficit in supply and materials and equipment when all the services offered where given to patients for free.
 - **Introduction of Fee Collection** (August 2024): In order to overcome these shortages, the hospital started charging the clients fees to cover for the buying and maintaining of supplies and equipment.
 - **Gaps in Service Coverage:** Even after the fee implementation, there are still some services that are not covered fully, and some of the services that are not covered include ECG and scans, and the patient has no option than to seek for such services from other hospitals.
 - **Limited Resources:** The hospital is still unable to offer full coverage to all services due to resource constraints even after coming up with the fee-based services.

Aden Abdulla Hospital

○ **Purchasing and Maintenance:**

- **Yes:** The hospital also sustains the buying of supplies and apparatus required in its operations.
- **Specialized Services:** The hospital also provides certain facilities for the patients so that all the required tools and instruments are available for the particular healthcare service.
- **Investor Support:** As a result of competition between the interested investors the hospital has timely and effective provision and maintenance of supplies and equipment to meet the needs of services.
- **Comprehensive Coverage:** As a result of this investors' support, the hospital is in a better position to provide the various services required by the populace including the specialized services without many shortcomings.

Expanded Analysis:

As for Benadir Hospital that is committed to the provision of supplies and equipment it has struggled to provide them regularly because it was formerly offering free services to all patients. The introduction of fee collection has been one of the best steps taken in order to overcome these shortages but the hospital still faces some challenges in service delivery especially in specialized services such as ECG and scans. This limitation suggests that though fee collection has enhanced the availability of resources, it has not completely solved the problem of availability of resources to meet all the patient's need in the hospital.

On the other hand, Aden Abdulla Hospital financial model which is funded by private investors provides for better control and timely procurement of requirements such as supplies and other equipment. The rivalry among the investors to meet the hospital needs assures the hospital can easily meet any shortfalls in services that may exist including the specialized ones. This investor based model leads to a better service delivery and provision of equipment and accessories thus making the hospital to be in a better position to handle the patient's needs without much strain or shortages that may be encountered.

In conclusion, even though Benadir hospital is in the process of enhancing on the resource availability through charges, there are still many challenges that the hospital goes through in order to meet the patients' needs fully. The hospital which relies on investor funding is in a better position to provide all the needed service delivery and ensure that they have the necessary supplies and equipment.

4.6.4. Key informants: Interviews of Workforces competence in Hospitals

1). How is the employee knowledge and skills on their work toward standard practices?

Benadir Hospital

- Employee Knowledge and Skills:

o Mixed Feedback:

- Very Well: Some of the respondents are of the opinion that the employees are doing well in as far as knowledge and skills concerning standard practices is concerned.

- Good: Some people think that skills and knowledge of the employees are average while others may think they are good or average.
- **Limited Skills and Knowledge:** There are those who are seen to be less endowed in terms of skills and knowledge as opposed to other employees. This is because their recruitment is weak based on political influence than Merit.
- **Recruitment Challenges:** Some of the respondents are of the opinion that the system of recruitment is bad as it puts persons who may not meet the requirements in place in position of employment.
- **Supervisory Support:**
 - **Corrective Oversight:** Although there are some problems with the recruitment, there are supervisors on the positions who can improve the further behavior of employees and ensure the proper level of their performance.

Aden Abdulla Hospital

- **Employee Knowledge and Skills:**
 - **Highly Skilled and Knowledgeable:** The employees of the hospital possess high level of knowledge and well developed skills.
 - **Rigorous Recruitment Process:** There is a proper and strict methodology of recruiting the employees, and only skilled professionals are hired.
 - **Standard Practices Test:** Pre-employments tests have been conducted for standard practices and the employees have been shown that they are capable of working at their best.

- **Talent and Excellence:** The employees are regarded as professionals who have a great talent and are well experienced to perform their job with acceptable standards.
- **Regular Supervision:** There are regular supervisors who work with the employees in order to monitor and improve their performance to the required standards.

Expanded Analysis:

In terms of knowledge and skill of its workforce, Benadir Hospital can be described as having a rather diverse situation. Some of the workers are deemed qualified and highly knowledgeable, while others are not due to the hiring process that occasionally depends on the political connection instead of the candidate's capability. This can cause a general variation in quality of services being offered to the patients. Nevertheless, the availability of competent supervisors to address these shortcomings sometimes goes a long way in reducing some of these problems; albeit not all the problems with the recruitment process can be solved in this manner.

On the other hand, Aden Abdulla Hospital has a more structured and proper procedure in terms of recruitment and employee's training and development. To this end, the hospital tests all the applicants on standard practices before they are hired as its employees. Thus, the organization's workforce is skilled, knowledgeable, and competent in the provision of quality care. The foregoing is further backed by the regular supervision that is done to ensure that employees meet or even surpass the standard norm.

In conclusion, as for Benadir Hospital's workforce, there is an irregular recruitment process resulting in the workforce with different levels of skills and knowledge, Aden Abdulla Hospital has a more organized and proper approach to its workforce and employees. The

differences in recruitment and supervision are the main factors that give one hospital a better quality of care as compared to the other.

2). Did you do any developments concerning about employees work?

Benadir Hospital

- Training and Development Initiatives:

- **Needs-Based:** These activities are mainly directed at departments that have been adversely affected or are generally desirable for up gradation.
- **Every Six Months:** Some of the key informants revealed that employees undergo training every six months with the view to building the capacity of the employees.
- **Yearly Training:** Training was done annually before the hospital adopted the fee for service system of operation.
- **Transition:** When the mode of practice shifted to the fee for service, there was increased focus on assessing the need for training. This resulted in carrying out more focused training sessions for certain divisions in the organization.
- **Separate Departmental Training:** Training is normally done in smaller groups depending on departments to ensure that each department gets the right training that it requires.

Aden Abdulla Hospital

- Training and Development Initiatives:

- **Every Three Months:** The training is carried out every three months targeting on skills and competence of all workers.

- Every Six Months: Also, training is normally done every six months where emphasis is made on less skilled workers to enhance their skills.

- **Introduction to Work Environment:**

- New comers are undertaking on orientation training to ensure that they understand the hospital's environment, culture and expectation.

Expanded Analysis:

As for the training and development of the employees, the organization, Benadir Hospital, is more of a reactive organization since the training provided are general and departmental based. The number and extent of these trainings differ; some employees are trained biannually while others have fewer chances of training, for instance, once a year before the change to the fee-for-service system. The change to the fee-for-service system also seemed to have contributed to a higher level of need analysis and thus provided more relevant and specialized training particularly for the department. But as a whole the approach is not as systematic and coherent as in the case of Aden Abdulla Hospital.

Aden Abdulla Hospital is more structured and proper in its employee training and development as compared to Benadir Hospital. There are annual meetings that are conducted every three months whereby the aim is to update all employees with new skills and knowledge. Also, there is an annual training for all other members of staff but the less skilled ones are trained every six months to enhance their skills. The hospital also provides orientation training for new employees so that they will know how and where they fit into the system and the hospital's policies and guidelines. Thus, this approach guarantees that all employees are provided with the possibility to develop at the workplace and improve their skills on a regular basis.

In conclusion, the training and development at Benadir Hospital is more on needs and departments while at Aden Abdulla Hospital it is more structure and comprehensive to include all employees. The difference in strategies can be attributed to the fact that Aden Abdulla Hospital has different priorities as well as organizational culture compared to the other hospital.

4.7. Hypothesis testing

4.7.1. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Capacities of both Hospitals and their significance value

Table 19 4.16 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Availability of Medical Equipment, Facilities and services

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
MRI Machine	Between Groups	21.557	4	5.389	7.034	<.001
	Within Groups	157.057	205	.766		
	Total	178.614	209			
CT Scanner	Between Groups	13.663	4	3.416	5.933	<.001
	Within Groups	118.032	205	.576		
	Total	131.695	209			
X-ray Machine	Between Groups	11.460	4	2.865	5.716	<.001
	Within Groups	102.755	205	.501		
	Total	114.214	209			
Ultrasound Machine	Between Groups	12.137	4	3.034	13.11 4	<.001
	Within Groups	47.430	205	.231		
	Total	59.567	209			
Emergency Room	Between Groups	15.754	4	3.939	17.83 4	<.001
	Within Groups	45.274	205	.221		
	Total	61.029	209			

Intensive Care Unit (ICU)	Between Groups	4.987	4	1.247	2.802	.027
	Within Groups	91.227	205	.445		
	Total	96.214	209			
Operating Theatres	Between Groups	18.392	4	4.598	13.166	<.001
	Within Groups	71.589	205	.349		
	Total	89.981	209			
Pharmacy	Between Groups	3.206	4	.802	2.495	.044
	Within Groups	65.861	205	.321		
	Total	69.067	209			
Cardiology	Between Groups	15.798	4	3.950	4.801	.001
	Within Groups	168.626	205	.823		
	Total	184.424	209			
Oncology	Between Groups	13.946	4	3.487	5.339	<.001
	Within Groups	133.868	205	.653		
	Total	147.814	209			
Pediatrics	Between Groups	2.175	4	.544	2.719	.031
	Within Groups	40.992	205	.200		
	Total	43.167	209			
Orthopedics	Between Groups	18.696	4	4.674	6.276	<.001
	Within Groups	152.661	205	.745		
	Total	171.357	209			

Source: Primary data

The ANOVA table 4.16. The ANOVA analysis presented in the table reveals significant differences in the perceptions of various medical and healthcare services within the hospital. The analysis highlights that the differences in mean scores between groups are statistically significant across almost all the examined facilities and equipment, with p-values (Sig.) below the

conventional threshold of 0.05. This indicates that respondents' views on the adequacy and effectiveness of these facilities vary considerably across different groups.

Starting with the **MRI machine**, the analysis shows a significant difference between groups with a sum of squares of 21.557 ($F = 7.034$, $p < .001$). This suggests that the perceptions of the MRI machine's performance or availability differ markedly among respondents, indicating possible disparities in the quality or access to MRI services across different departments or units. For the **CT scanner**, the results are similarly significant ($F = 5.933$, $p < .001$), with a sum of squares of 13.663. This finding indicates that there are notable differences in how respondents view the effectiveness or availability of the CT scanner, reflecting potential variations in service delivery or equipment reliability.

The **X-ray machine** also shows significant differences between groups ($F = 5.716$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 11.460. This result points to variability in the perceived quality or accessibility of X-ray services, possibly due to differences in equipment condition or utilization rates across various hospital sections. In the case of the **ultrasound machine**, the analysis reveals the most substantial differences between groups ($F = 13.114$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 12.137. This significant result underscores pronounced disparities in the perceptions of ultrasound services, which could be attributed to factors such as machine availability, technician expertise, or departmental needs.

The **emergency room (ER)** also exhibits significant differences ($F = 17.834$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 15.754. This suggests that the respondents' experiences with the ER vary significantly, possibly due to differences in patient volume, staffing levels, or the urgency of cases handled by the ER. The **intensive care unit (ICU)** shows a statistically

significant difference as well ($F = 2.802$, $p = .027$), though less pronounced than other areas. The sum of squares for between groups is 4.987, indicating that while there are differences in perceptions of ICU services, they may not be as stark as in other areas, perhaps reflecting a more consistent standard of care in the ICU.

Regarding the **operating theatres**, the analysis reveals significant differences ($F = 13.166$, $p < .001$) with a sum of squares of 18.392. This indicates that the operating theatres' performance or availability is perceived differently across groups, which could point to disparities in surgical services or operating room management. The **pharmacy** also shows a significant difference, albeit less pronounced ($F = 2.495$, $p = .044$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 3.206. This suggests some variability in the perceptions of pharmacy services, which might be related to issues like medication availability, wait times, or the efficiency of the pharmacy staff.

In the **cardiology** department, the results indicate significant differences ($F = 4.801$, $p = .001$), with a sum of squares of 15.798. This suggests that the quality or availability of cardiology services is viewed differently among respondents, possibly due to factors such as patient outcomes, staff expertise, or equipment reliability. For **oncology**, the analysis also shows significant differences ($F = 5.339$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 13.946. This indicates varying perceptions of oncology services, which may reflect disparities in cancer treatment availability, staff specialization, or patient support services.

In **pediatrics**, the analysis reveals statistically significant differences ($F = 2.719$, $p = .031$) with a sum of squares of 2.175. Although less pronounced than other areas, this finding suggests that there are differences in how respondents perceive pediatric services, potentially related to factors like patient care quality or pediatric resources. Finally, the **orthopedics** department

shows significant differences between groups ($F = 6.276, p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 18.696. This result highlights variability in the perceptions of orthopedic services, which could be due to differences in patient outcomes, surgical success rates, or rehabilitation services.

Overall, these ANOVA results suggest that there are significant variations in the perceived adequacy and effectiveness of various hospital facilities and services. These differences point to potential areas for improvement, where disparities in service delivery, equipment availability, or staff expertise could be addressed to enhance overall patient care and hospital operations.

4.7.2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for Health Services Delivery

Table 20 4.17. Health Services Delivery for Hospitals

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Patient Admission Rates	Between Groups	1.552	4	.388	2.125	.079
	Within Groups	37.443	205	.183		
	Total	38.995	209			
Surgery Success Rates	Between Groups	6.276	4	1.569	5.471	<.001
	Within Groups	58.791	205	.287		
	Total	65.067	209			
Emergency Response Efficiency	Between Groups	11.318	4	2.830	13.730	<.001
	Within Groups	42.248	205	.206		
	Total	53.567	209			
Outpatient Services Efficiency	Between Groups	13.076	4	3.269	15.849	<.001
	Within Groups	42.281	205	.206		
	Total	55.357	209			
Inpatient Services Efficiency	Between Groups	14.260	4	3.565	24.811	<.001
	Within Groups	29.455	205	.144		
	Total	43.714	209			
Diagnostic Services Efficiency	Between Groups	10.150	4	2.537	9.969	<.001
	Within Groups	52.179	205	.255		
	Total	62.329	209			

Source: Primary data

The ANOVA table 4. 17. The ANOVA analysis in Table 4.17 examines the variability in key indicators of health services delivery across different groups within hospitals. The findings reveal both significant and non-significant differences in how various aspects of health services are perceived, pointing to areas where hospital performance is viewed differently across departments or units.

Patient admission rates showed no statistically significant difference between groups ($F = 2.125, p = .079$). Although the sum of squares for between groups is 1.552, the p-value indicates that any differences in the perception of patient admission rates among the different groups are not strong enough to be considered statistically significant. This suggests that patient admission processes might be fairly consistent across the hospital.

In contrast, the **surgery success rates** exhibit significant differences between groups ($F = 5.471, p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 6.276. This result indicates that perceptions of surgical success vary notably across different departments or groups, potentially reflecting disparities in surgical outcomes, procedural complexity, or surgeon expertise within the hospital.

The analysis of **emergency response efficiency** also reveals significant differences ($F = 13.730, p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 11.318. This suggests considerable variability in how different groups perceive the hospital's emergency response efficiency, possibly due to differences in response times, staff preparedness, or the availability of emergency resources in various areas.

Similarly, **outpatient services efficiency** shows significant differences ($F = 15.849$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 13.076. This indicates that outpatient service delivery is perceived differently across hospital units, which might point to variability in service wait times, patient throughput, or the quality of care provided to outpatients.

The **inpatient services efficiency** also demonstrates highly significant differences ($F = 24.811$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 14.260. This result highlights substantial disparities in the perception of inpatient care efficiency, possibly due to differences in patient care standards, staff-to-patient ratios, or resource allocation across various departments.

Lastly, **diagnostic services efficiency** is another area where significant differences are observed ($F = 9.969$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 10.150. The significant variation in the perceptions of diagnostic services efficiency suggests that some departments may have better access to diagnostic tools or more efficient diagnostic procedures than others, leading to disparities in service delivery.

Overall, the ANOVA results indicate that while patient admission rates are perceived consistently across the hospital, other critical areas such as surgery success, emergency response, outpatient and inpatient services, and diagnostic efficiency show significant variability. These findings point to potential areas for targeted improvements to ensure more uniform and effective health service delivery throughout the hospital.

4.7.3. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) of Leadership Evaluation

Table 21 4.18. Leadership Evaluation of Hospitals

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
The hospital leadership provides a clear vision for the future.	Between Groups	157.088	4	39.272	22.655	<.001
	Within Groups	355.369	205	1.734		
	Total	512.457	209			
The hospital has a well-defined strategic plan that is effectively communicated.	Between Groups	113.522	4	28.380	16.526	<.001
	Within Groups	352.045	205	1.717		
	Total	465.567	209			
The leadership makes decisions in a timely and efficient manner.	Between Groups	99.823	4	24.956	17.409	<.001
	Within Groups	293.872	205	1.434		
	Total	393.695	209			
Leaders effectively solve problems and address challenges.	Between Groups	34.893	4	8.723	4.544	.002
	Within Groups	393.531	205	1.920		
	Total	428.424	209			
There is open and transparent communication between leadership and staff.	Between Groups	93.980	4	23.495	22.130	<.001
	Within Groups	217.644	205	1.062		
	Total	311.624	209			
The leadership regularly provides updates and information about hospital operations.	Between Groups	81.153	4	20.288	13.310	<.001
	Within Groups	312.470	205	1.524		
	Total	393.624	209			
Leadership provides adequate support for staff professional development.	Between Groups	53.086	4	13.272	7.924	<.001
	Within Groups	343.338	205	1.675		
	Total	396.424	209			
The hospital invests in training and development programs for its staff.	Between Groups	28.667	4	7.167	4.347	.002
	Within Groups	337.999	205	1.649		
	Total	366.667	209			

The leadership prioritizes patient care and safety.	Between Groups	63.523	4	15.881	9.647	<.001
	Within Groups	337.472	205	1.646		
	Total	400.995	209			
Leaders ensure that the hospital follows best practices for patient safety.	Between Groups	83.680	4	20.920	11.505	<.001
	Within Groups	372.744	205	1.818		
	Total	456.424	209			
The leadership encourages innovation in healthcare delivery.	Between Groups	25.925	4	6.481	3.970	.004
	Within Groups	334.690	205	1.633		
	Total	360.614	209			
The hospital leadership is committed to continuous improvement.	Between Groups	57.799	4	14.450	7.320	<.001
	Within Groups	404.682	205	1.974		
	Total	462.481	209			
The leadership effectively manages the hospital's financial resources.	Between Groups	58.112	4	14.528	10.076	<.001
	Within Groups	295.583	205	1.442		
	Total	353.695	209			
Leaders make sound financial decisions that benefit the hospital.	Between Groups	40.619	4	10.155	5.465	<.001
	Within Groups	380.947	205	1.858		
	Total	421.567	209			

Source: Primary data

The ANOVA analysis in Table 4.18 provides a detailed evaluation of leadership effectiveness in hospitals across various dimensions. The results indicate significant differences in perceptions of leadership performance among different groups, highlighting key areas where leadership practices are either effective or require improvement.

Firstly, the perception that **hospital leadership provides a clear vision for the future** shows a highly significant difference between groups ($F = 22.655$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 157.088. This suggests that while some groups may view the

leadership as having a strong and clear vision, others may find it lacking, indicating inconsistency in how the vision is communicated or perceived across the hospital.

The evaluation of whether **the hospital has a well-defined strategic plan that is effectively communicated** also reveals significant differences ($F = 16.526$, $p < .001$). With a between-groups sum of squares of 113.522, the results indicate that perceptions of strategic planning and its communication vary widely among groups, which could imply that some departments are better informed or more aligned with the hospital's strategic goals than others.

When assessing whether **leadership makes decisions in a timely and efficient manner**, the analysis again shows significant differences ($F = 17.409$, $p < .001$). The between-groups sum of squares of 99.823 highlights variability in how different groups perceive the efficiency and timeliness of leadership decisions, suggesting potential areas for improvement in decision-making processes.

The perception that **leaders effectively solve problems and address challenges** also shows significant differences ($F = 4.544$, $p = .002$), although the between-groups sum of squares is relatively lower at 34.893. This indicates that while some groups feel that leadership is effective in problem-solving, others may experience challenges that are not adequately addressed, pointing to possible gaps in leadership effectiveness in certain areas.

Open and transparent communication between leadership and staff is another area where significant differences are observed ($F = 22.130$, $p < .001$). The between-groups sum of squares of 93.980 suggests that while some groups experience open communication, others may

feel disconnected or inadequately informed by leadership, highlighting the need for more consistent communication practices across the hospital.

The evaluation of whether **leadership regularly provides updates and information about hospital operations** also reveals significant differences ($F = 13.310$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 81.153. This indicates that some groups feel more informed about hospital operations than others, suggesting the need for more uniform dissemination of information across departments.

When it comes to **leadership support for staff professional development**, the analysis shows significant differences ($F = 7.924$, $p < .001$). The between-groups sum of squares of 53.086 suggests variability in the perception of leadership support, indicating that some groups may feel well-supported in their professional growth, while others may not, pointing to areas where leadership could enhance its support for staff development.

The perception that **the hospital invests in training and development programs for its staff** also shows significant differences ($F = 4.347$, $p = .002$). With a between-groups sum of squares of 28.667, this suggests variability in how different groups perceive the hospital's investment in training, potentially highlighting disparities in access to or the quality of training programs across departments.

Regarding the prioritization of **patient care and safety by leadership**, the analysis reveals significant differences ($F = 9.647$, $p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 63.523. This indicates that while some groups believe that leadership prioritizes patient care and safety,

others may not perceive the same level of commitment, suggesting inconsistencies in leadership's focus on these critical areas.

The perception that **leaders ensure the hospital follows best practices for patient safety** also shows significant differences ($F = 11.505, p < .001$). The between-groups sum of squares of 83.680 indicates variability in how different groups view leadership's adherence to safety protocols, highlighting the need for more consistent application of best practices across the hospital.

The evaluation of whether **leadership encourages innovation in healthcare delivery** reveals significant differences ($F = 3.970, p = .004$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 25.925. This suggests that while some groups experience strong encouragement for innovation, others may not, pointing to potential areas where leadership could foster more innovative practices.

The analysis of whether **hospital leadership is committed to continuous improvement** shows significant differences ($F = 7.320, p < .001$), with a between-groups sum of squares of 57.799. This indicates variability in how different groups perceive leadership's commitment to ongoing improvement, suggesting that leadership may need to more consistently demonstrate this commitment across all areas of the hospital.

Finally, the perception that **leadership effectively manages the hospital's financial resources** and **makes sound financial decisions that benefit the hospital** both show significant differences ($F = 10.076, p < .001$ and $F = 5.465, p < .001$, respectively). The between-groups sums of squares of 58.112 and 40.619 suggest variability in how different groups perceive

leadership's financial management and decision-making, pointing to possible disparities in financial practices and their perceived effectiveness across departments.

Overall, the ANOVA results indicate that while there are areas where leadership is perceived consistently across the hospital, there are also significant differences in key aspects of leadership performance. These findings suggest that hospital leadership may need to focus on improving consistency in communication, decision-making, problem-solving, support for professional development, and financial management to enhance overall effectiveness and alignment within the hospital.

4.7.4. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of Financial Management Practices
Table 22 4.19. ANOVA of Financial Management Practices of Hospitals

ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
The hospital has a clear and detailed budget plan.	Between Groups	219.418	4	54.854	51.205	<.001
	Within Groups	219.611	205	1.071		
	Total	439.029	209			
Resources are allocated efficiently according to the hospital's needs.	Between Groups	124.684	4	31.171	26.859	<.001
	Within Groups	237.912	205	1.161		
	Total	362.595	209			
The hospital has effective revenue collection systems in place.	Between Groups	129.995	4	32.499	29.076	<.001
	Within Groups	229.129	205	1.118		
	Total	359.124	209			
There are diverse sources of revenue for the hospital.	Between Groups	140.069	4	35.017	28.652	<.001
	Within Groups	250.545	205	1.222		
	Total	390.614	209			
Expenditures are	Between Groups	46.012	4	11.503	8.958	<.001

tracked accurately and regularly.	Within Groups	263.245	205	1.284		
	Total	309.257	209			
The hospital implements cost-saving measures without compromising quality.	Between Groups	9.131	4	2.283	1.252	.290
	Within Groups	373.864	205	1.824		
	Total	382.995	209			
Financial reports are generated regularly and shared with relevant stakeholders.	Between Groups	68.931	4	17.233	11.340	<.001
	Within Groups	311.526	205	1.520		
	Total	380.457	209			
There is transparency in the hospital's financial transactions.	Between Groups	65.021	4	16.255	13.850	<.001
	Within Groups	240.603	205	1.174		
	Total	305.624	209			
The hospital invests in essential medical equipment and infrastructure.	Between Groups	91.550	4	22.888	14.993	<.001
	Within Groups	312.945	205	1.527		
	Total	404.495	209			
There are adequate funds for ongoing projects and hospital improvements.	Between Groups	97.314	4	24.329	14.368	<.001
	Within Groups	347.110	205	1.693		
	Total	444.424	209			
The hospital has strategies in place to manage financial risks.	Between Groups	152.129	4	38.032	25.162	<.001
	Within Groups	309.852	205	1.511		
	Total	461.981	209			
Contingency plans are available for financial emergencies.	Between Groups	90.595	4	22.649	13.423	<.001
	Within Groups	345.900	205	1.687		
	Total	436.495	209			

Source: Primary data

The ANOVA Table 4.19 shows the ANOVA results for various financial management practices in hospitals; it shows that there is a statistically significant difference in the perception

of the various groups regarding financial management. In this regard, the findings provide a broad understanding of strategies that hospitals use in budgeting, resource management, revenue generation, and financial disclosure.

Beginning with the significance of the budget plan ($F = 51.205, p < .001$), the results show the differences between the groups with the between-groups sum of squares of 219.418. This indicates that there is a great difference in the perception of budget clarity and detail indicating how different hospitals plan and present their budgets. Some hospitals may have well outlined financial plans others may not have clear plans which is a factor in financial management. As for resource utilization effectiveness ($F = 26.859, p < .001$), the between-groups sum of squares was 124.684, the differences in the efficiency of resource targeting for the hospitals' needs are quite striking. This variability could also indicate the differences in the effectiveness of the distribution of resources that may affect the functioning of the hospitals and their patients.

The results for the revenue collection systems also show significant variability between groups in terms of the F statistic ($F = 29.076, p < .001$) with a between groups sum of squares of 129.995. This suggests that although some hospitals are likely to have effective revenue collection systems others may be weak in this regard and this will have an impact on the financial health of the hospital and its capacity to provide services. For the variable regarding the types of income ($F = 28.652, p < .001$) the between groups' sum of squares was 140.069 reveals significant variation. This means that those hospitals that derive income from a number of sources may be in a better shape financially and those that have few sources of income may be financially vulnerable.

Regarding tracking of expenditures as frequent and timely ($F = 8.958, p < .001$) the analysis revealed statistically significant differences with the between groups sum of squares of 46.012. From this, we see that there is an incomplete level of expenditure tracking that is important in order to control the finances and to make sure that the spending is within the planned for budget. On the other hand, there is no significant difference between the groups as for the perception on the effectiveness of cost-cutting measures with no decline in quality ($F = 1.252, p = 0.290$, between groups Sum Squares = 9.131). This lack of substantial difference suggests the general understanding of the efficiency of cost reduction measures is quite uniform, although, diverse practices might be used in various hospitals.

The comparison of the regular financial reports ($F = 11.340, p < .001$) shows the differences between the groups with the value of the between-groups sum of squares equaling 68.931. This finding shows that hospitals are very much involved in preparing and distributing financial reports to stakeholders as frequently as possible, which is very crucial in the society. The results indicate that there is a significant difference in the level of financial transactions transparency between the two groups ($F = 13.850, p < .001$) with a between groups sum of squares of 65.021, The results of the above analysis also reveal that there is a lot of variability in the proportions. This implies that some of the hospitals are considered to have good financial reporting standards as compared to others which may not be clear hence making the stakeholders to lose confidence.

Another area of the difference is the possibility of the hospitals to invest in the essential medical equipment and infrastructure ($F = 14.993, p < 0.001$) which is also another area with high between groups sum of squares, 91.550. This variation shows how financial management

affects investment in the basic resources which is essential for enhancement of healthcare services. The differences were found to be significant in the availability of funds for ongoing projects and improvements ($F = 14.368, p < .001$) with between groups sum of squares of 97.314. This result suggests that the level of financial preparedness to sustain development may be different, which may impact on the ability of a hospital to improve its structures and services.

Measures for mitigating financial risks ($F = 25.162, p < .001$) shows that there is a significant difference in the strategies used between the two groups with a between groups sum of squares of 152.129. This means that some of the hospitals are more prepared to face the financial risks that are inevitable in the future which is very important for the future of a hospital's finances. Last but not the least, the contingency plans for the financial emergencies also have a significant difference with the (F value of 13.423, $p < .001$) and the between groups sum of square of 90.595. This may mean that some hospitals have good and elaborate strategies for handling financial crises while others may have poor or no strategies to deal with such situations thus affecting their ability to cope with such situations.

To conclude, the analysis of variance shows that there are considerable differences in the approaches to the management of financial management in hospitals and distinguish the budget, resources, revenue, and financial reporting. These differences can be attributed to the differences in the levels of efficiency in financial management within the hospitals which in turn affect the operational output and service delivery of the hospitals.

4.7.5. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) of Workforce Competence

Table 23 4.20. Workforce Competence for Hospitals

ANOVA

		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
The medical staff have the necessary qualifications and skills to provide high-quality care.	Between Groups	63.619	4	15.905	8.619	<.001
	Within Groups	378.305	205	1.845		
	Total	441.924	209			
Continuous training and education programs are available for clinical staff.	Between Groups	32.116	4	8.029	5.200	.001
	Within Groups	316.499	205	1.544		
	Total	348.614	209			
The technical staff are proficient in operating medical equipment and technologies.	Between Groups	44.885	4	11.221	6.898	<.001
	Within Groups	333.496	205	1.627		
	Total	378.381	209			
Technical staff receive regular training on new equipment and technologies.	Between Groups	39.517	4	9.879	5.363	<.001
	Within Groups	377.607	205	1.842		
	Total	417.124	209			
The hospital workforce demonstrates effective communication skills with patients and families.	Between Groups	35.515	4	8.879	6.704	<.001
	Within Groups	271.480	205	1.324		
	Total	306.995	209			
There is good communication and teamwork among hospital staff.	Between Groups	86.100	4	21.525	15.998	<.001
	Within Groups	275.824	205	1.345		
	Total	361.924	209			
The staff adhere to best practices and protocols for patient safety.	Between Groups	65.622	4	16.405	10.077	<.001
	Within Groups	333.735	205	1.628		
	Total	399.357	209			

Workforce competencies positively impact patient care quality.	Between Groups	90.408	4	22.602	15.653	<.001
	Within Groups	296.015	205	1.444		
	Total	386.424	209			
The staff are capable of making sound decisions in critical situations.	Between Groups	57.766	4	14.441	9.632	<.001
	Within Groups	307.358	205	1.499		
	Total	365.124	209			
Problem-solving skills are emphasized and developed among the workforce.	Between Groups	60.789	4	15.197	13.195	<.001
	Within Groups	236.111	205	1.152		
	Total	296.900	209			
The hospital has effective leadership and management training programs.	Between Groups	32.285	4	8.071	5.347	<.001
	Within Groups	309.472	205	1.510		
	Total	341.757	209			
Leadership skills among the staff contribute to efficient hospital operations.	Between Groups	45.106	4	11.276	8.346	<.001
	Within Groups	276.989	205	1.351		
	Total	322.095	209			
The workforce is trained to provide culturally sensitive care.	Between Groups	39.730	4	9.932	8.133	<.001
	Within Groups	250.366	205	1.221		
	Total	290.095	209			
Cultural competence training improves patient satisfaction and outcomes.	Between Groups	78.187	4	19.547	16.045	<.001
	Within Groups	249.736	205	1.218		
	Total	327.924	209			

Source: Primary Data

The ANOVA Table 4.20 In order to measure the workforce competence in hospitals, the ANOVA has been used in the present study as given in this table 4.20. These differences in table

clearly show the differences in many aspects of staff qualification, experience, and even competence level of the hospitals showing the poor workforce management.

First of all, the medical staff's qualifications and skills ($F = 8.619, p < .001$) have large variation between groups and the between groups sum of squares is 63.619. This implies that there is a variation in the performance of the hospital staff in delivering quality care. Therefore, the hospitals that are equipped with higher qualifications and better skills among the medical staff are expected to provide better care as compared to the hospitals with less qualified staff. With regard to the frequency and nature of continuing training and education programs for clinical staffs ($F = 5.200, p = .001$), the between groups sum of squares is 32.116. This finding also gives an insight of the inequality in access to further training within the hospitals. It is possible that some of the hospitals have effective training sessions that ensure that their clinical staff is well informed on the updated practices while there are those that may not have such training hence improper care delivery.

The technical staff's knowledge of medical equipment and technologies ($F = 6.898, p < .001$) is another dimension that has been found to be different between the two groups with a between groups sum of squares of 44.885. This shows that some hospitals have better technical personnel who are in a position to control the medical equipment in the best way possible thus influencing the results of the diagnosis and treatment. On the training on new equipment and technologies for technical staff in a regular basis ($F = 5.363, p < 0.001$), the between groups sum of squares is 39.517. This minimizes on the fact that not all the hospitals have the same approach in the training of their technical staff which is very important especially in a field that is constantly evolving.

The hospital workforce's capacity to show proper communication with the patients and families ($F = 6.704, p < .001$) also has a significant difference, with the between groups sum of squares being 35.515. Some hospitals are more efficient in communication than others and this is important for patients' satisfaction and care. This was in line with the results obtained for the overall communication and teamwork in the hospitals where the between-group sum of squares was even higher: 86.100. This is due to variation in the co-ordination of the hospital teams which is a crucial factor in enhancing efficiency and effectiveness of the system and hence the quality of patient care.

Another strong evidence is the patients' safety practices ($F = 10.077, p < .001$) with a between groups sum of squares of 65.622. This variation shows how well or otherwise hospitals adhere to safety guidelines which has a direct relation with patient safety and care. The analysis of variance for patient care quality as influenced by workforce competencies ($F = 15.653, p < .001$) has a rather large between-groups sum of squares of 90.408. This means that the level of training of the hospital workforce plays a critical role in the quality of care delivered to patients with the more trained workers possibly offering better quality care.

The staff's decision-making capacity in high-risk situations ($F = 9.632, p < .001$) is significantly different from each other with a between groups sum of square of 57.766. This shows that there is a variation in the level of decision making among the staff since this is an essential factor of managing patients during emergency. The importance of problem solving skills in the workforce ($F = 13.195, p < .001$) differs significantly from each other with between groups sum of squares of 60.789. This finding suggests that some of the hospitals value the

problem solving skills which can make the staff perform better as well as improve on the quality of service delivery to the patients.

Leadership and management training programs are available ($F = 5.347, p < .001$) with the between-groups sum of squares of 32.285. This means that while some of the hospitals have put much emphasis on leadership development, others may have done so, which may have some implication on the overall management of the hospital. Leadership skills among the staff ($F = 8.346, p < .001$) also differ with a between groups sum of squares of 45.106. This indicates the extent of the leadership skills in relation to hospital operations and its effect on the employees' performance and the hospital's results.

The training of staff to provide culturally sensitive care ($F = 8.133, p < 0.001$) has a large between groups sum of squares of 39.730. This means that some of the hospitals have a better strategy of ensuring that their employees are well equipped to attend to cultural issues and this in turn enhances on patient satisfaction and recovery. Last but not the least, the patient satisfaction and outcomes ($F = 16.045, p < .001$) as measured by cultural competence training has a significant effect with between groups sum of squares of 78.187. This variation shows how well the hospitals are training their staff in cultural competence and the results demonstrate how patient care can be improved greatly.

Consequently, the ANOVA results indicate that there are significant differences in the various aspects of workforce competence of the hospitals which affect factors such as personnel certification and training, language fluency, and cultural awareness. These differences are a result of disparity in the management of workforce which if well-coordinated can greatly enhance the quality of patient care and hospital productivity.

In conclusion, the ANOVA analyses provide valuable insights into the factors that contribute to hospital success. By focusing on enhancing leadership, financial management, and workforce competence, hospitals can improve their overall effectiveness, ensure sustainability, and deliver high-quality care to their patients. These findings should guide hospital administrators in identifying areas for improvement and implementing strategies to address the gaps identified in the analysis.

4.8. Conclusion of Hypothesis Testing

Given the ANOVA results across various aspects of healthcare management, including service delivery, leadership, financial management, and workforce competence, we can draw conclusions based on the significance (Sig.) values: Given the ANOVA results across various aspects of healthcare management, including service delivery, leadership, financial management, and workforce competence, we can draw conclusions based on the significance (Sig.) values:

1. Service Delivery and Hospital Capacity)

- Patient Admission Rates: Hence the p-Value is 0.079 which is higher than 0.05. This means that accepting the null hypothesis (H_0) for patient admission rates, signifies no rejection to the person that patient admission rates are different in hospitals.
- Surgery Success Rates, Emergency Response Efficiency, Outpatient Services Efficiency, Inpatient Services Efficiency, Diagnostic Services Efficiency: In the following analysis, we see that all these aspects have $p < 0.001$, indicating significant differences. Hence, we reject the null hypothesis (H_0) for these aspects and accept the alternative hypothesis (H_1) that capacity of the hospital has an effect on these service delivery factors.

2. Leadership

- As for the values of p as to all the leadership factors mentioned above, the values are below 0.05, that imply the differences between the hospitals with different leadership effectiveness. Therefore, we fail to support null hypothesis (H_0) but support the alternative hypothesis (H_1) in supporting that leadership has a significant influence on healthcare management.

3. Financial Management

- All the p-values that have been obtained are less than the significance level of 0. At the p-value of 0.001 for most of the financial management factors apart from cost reduction strategies where the test has a p-value of 0.290, we can infer that the financial management practices differ significantly between the two hospitals. The findings lead us to support the H_1 and fail to support the H_0 for most of the financial aspects except the cost saving where we are unable to reject the H_0 .

4. Workforce Competence

- Every component of the whole workforce competence is presented with p-values below 0.001, thus suggesting a relation to the level of workforce competence in the management of health care between different hospitals. Hence, we fail to support the null hypothesis (H_0) and we support the view in the alternative hypothesis (H_1) that workforce competence affects healthcare management.

Based on the findings of the present research from the ANOVA test, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is accepted for most of the aspects of healthcare management. This entails the fact that the health care management in terms of services delivery, leadership, financial management and workforce competency between the different capacities of hospitals varies considerably. They are the patient admission rates and cost saving techniques whereby no difference was observed.

4.9. Correlation of study

4.9.1. Correlation of hospital Medical Equipment, Facilities and services

Table 24 4.21. Correlation of hospital Medical Equipment, Facilities and services

Correlations													
		Hospitals	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11
C1	r	-.318**											
C2	r	-.158*	.273**										
C3	r	-0.074	.433**	.196**									
C4	r	-.163*	.338**	.517**	.597*								
C5	r	-0.114	.360**	.311**	.665*	.611**							
C6	r	-.699**	.352**	.294**	0.075	0.123	-0.029						
C7	r	-0.087	.192**	.371**	.351*	.535**	.507*	0.021					
C8	r	-.729**	.451**	.173*	0.027	.173*	0.018	.795**	0.122				
C9	r	-.247**	.179**	.231**	.429*	.373**	.527*	.202**	.442*	.210**			
C10	r	-.310**	.331**	.302**	-0.121	0.072	-0.113	.515**	-0.028	.481**	-0.108		
C11	r	-.427**	.447	.213	.167*	.197	0.12	.550	.164*	.568	.330*	.493	

1			**	**		**	7	**		**	*	**	
C1	r	-.513**	.371**	.259**	0.039	.205**	0.121	.716**	.169*	.723**	.275*	.550**	.511**
2													
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).													
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).													

NOTE: X-ray Machine = (C1), Ultrasound Machine = (C2), Emergency Room = (C3), Operating Theatres = (C4), Pharmacy = (C5), Cardiology = (C6), Pediatrics = (C7), Orthopedics = (C8), Intensive Care Unit (ICU) = (C9), MRI Machine = (C10), CT Scanner = (C11), Oncology = (C12)

From the table 4.21. it can be seen that there is correlation between various types of medical equipment, and the facilities and services provided in the hospitals. These correlations show the degree as well as the direction of the relationship between different components and positive signs of correlation show that the relationship is directly proportional to each other while the negative sign denotes that the relationship is inversely proportional. The importance of these relations is acknowledged and some of them are pointed out being statistically meaningful.

Hospital and X-ray Machines: The observation that hospitals featuring more X-ray machines are indicative of a smaller number of overall machines ($r = -0.318$, $p < 0.01$) may suggest one or two things, hospitals with advanced facilities may use a smaller number of X-ray machines or else availability of the machines may be inversely proportional to other resources available in the hospitals.

Hospital and Ultrasound Machines: The correlation between both variables is negative but of lower strength, and is -0.158 and statistically significant at $p < 0.05$ level between hospitals and the ultrasound machines. However, a positive and significant correlation is established between the availability of ultrasound machines and other supporting services such as; Emergency Rooms ($r = 0.273$, $p < 0.01$) and Operating Theatres ($r = 0.338$, $p < 0.01$). This means that, the intensity, capacity or ability of the hospitals possessing numerous ultrasound machines will be in proportion with their emergency as well as surgical departments.

Specialized services and hospital facilities Currently the hospitals are limited only to few specialized services while they are endowed utilizing modern hospital facilities. The findings further revealed that hospitalization negatively correlated to Cardiology with $r = -0.699$ * $p < 0.01$, Orthopedics with $r = -0.729$ * $p < 0.01$ and Oncology with $r = -0.513$ * $p < 0.01$, thus implying that although high overall equipment in hospitals might be positive, it is accompanied by a possible absence of specialized This could mean that general hospitals are less likely to have specialized sections as compared to cardiovascular hospitals.

Relations between Facilities and Services: It is also important to point out that all the facilities and services are positively correlated with each other. for example, Operating Theatres (C4) correlated significantly with Pharmacies ($r = 0.665$ **, $p < 0.01$) so that Operating theatre well equipped is likely to Pharmacies well stocked. In the same manner, Orthopedics (C8) has significantly positive association to Cardiology ($r = 0.795$ **), Pediatrics ($r = 0.716$ **), indicating that hospitals with focus on orthopedic services have suitable competency in cardiology and pediatrics services as well.

Intensive Care Units (ICU) service: The ICU (C9) had positive relationship with other advanced services as CT Scanners ($r = 0.568$; $p < 0.01$) and Oncology ($r = 0.723$; $p < 0.01$). This means that hospitals with the ICUs are likely to have the advanced imaging equipment's and oncology services.

MRI Machines and their related Hospital Services: MRI machines (C10) have moderate correlation with other services offered at the hospital in that sometimes the correlation is positive while at other times it is negative. They are correlated with Pediatrics significantly at $r = 0.515$, $p < 0.01$ level also with Oncology at $r = 0.275$, $p < 0.01$ level thus suggesting that if a

hospital has MRI it may also have strong Pediatric and/or Oncology specialty. On the other hand, the MRI machine has relatively negative and insignificant association with Operating Theatres meaning there is no significant interaction between these two services.

CT Scanners and Related Services

CT Scanners (C11) are positively correlated to other kinds of hospital services and displays a more significant relationship with Pediatrics ($r = 0.550, p < 0.01$) and Oncology ($r = 0.493, p < 0.01$) whereby, the presence of CT Scanners in the hospitals is probably proportional to strong coverage of pediatric and oncology services.

Thus the table portrays the complex and interrelated character of the various pieces of equipment in a hospital, the facility and services. Although, certain specific services may occupy the most hospital space and may have negative correlations between each other, it is evident that the services share positive relationships with each other stressing the interdependence of these facilities especially in certain specialized area of operations. The resulting analysis provides greater understanding about ways that hospitals may distribute resources today and addressing whether there may be a requirement to equilibrium those capabilities across proposed services.

4.9.2. Correlations between various hospital equipment and facilities with different aspects of hospital performance.

Table 25 4.22. Hospital equipment and facilities with different aspects of hospital performance.

Correlations													
		C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12
Patient Admission Rates	R	.234**	0.050	0.074	-0.051	0.021	.294**	.150*	.345**	-0.010	.228**	-0.046	.156*
Surgery Success Rates	R	.151*	.481**	.162*	.525**	.165*	0.080	.352**	0.114	.265**	0.022	.142*	0.073
Emergency Response Efficiency	R	.479**	.346**	.679**	.517**	.558**	0.078	.288**	0.005	.481**	0.052	.260**	0.060
Outpatient Services Efficiency	R	.265**	.235**	.546**	.516**	.501**	-0.026	.297**	-0.099	.369**	0.021	-0.008	-0.066
Inpatient Services Efficiency	R	.293**	.157*	.448**	.276**	.273**	.218**	.345**	.191**	.436**	-0.060	.262**	0.133
Diagnostic Services Efficiency	R	.233**	.343**	.231**	.455**	.344**	.334**	.241**	.360**	.508**	.154*	.428**	.338**

Source: Primary data

The table 4. 22. shows the relationships between diverse instruments and amenities of hospital and aspects of hospital outcomes including admitted patients rate, surgical success rate, emergency response capability, outpatient services productivity, inpatient services productivity, and diagnostic services productivity. From the outcome, it is seen that in contributing to the various performance indicators, functionality of certain medical equipment and departments matters.

Patient Admission Rates: Patient admission rates have been proved to be closely and positively related to capacities of X-ray machines ($r = .234$, $p < 0.01$), Cardiology ($r = .294$, $p <$

0.01) Pediatrics ($r = .150$, $p < 0.05$) Orthopedics ($r = .345$, $p < 0.01$) and MRI ($r = .228$, $p < 0.01$). These correlations imply that hospitals having these facilities shall record high patient admission rates, which point towards the importance of these facilities in patient admission. On the other hand, correlation between the other facilities such as Operating Theatres and ICU are not highly correlated, which could mean that these departments do not actually have an impact on admission rates although they are rather related to specific areas of health care.

Surgery Success Rates: Correlations with surgical success are positive and highly significant with Ultrasound Machines ($r = .481$, $p < 0.01$) Operating Theatres ($r = .525$, $p < 0.01$), Pediatrics departments ($r = .352$, $p < 0.01$) and ICU facilities ($r = .265$, $p < 0.01$). This goes a long way to explain why these departments and equipment are important in ensuring that surgeries come out a success. Even though the above coefficients are lower than those of other variables tied to success of surgeries, the values are positive indicating positive relations with X-ray machines ($r = .151$, $p < 0.05$) and Pharmacy ($r = .165$, $p < 0.05$).

Emergency Response Efficiency: The relationship between Emergency response efficiency and services such as Emergency Rooms, X-ray machines, Operating Theatres, Pharmacies and ICU facilities are positively strong, wherein the correlation coefficient of Emergency response efficiency and Emergency Rooms is $r = .679$, for X-ray machines it is $r = .479$, for Operating Theatres it is $r = .517$, for Pharmacies it is $r = .558$. Such high correlation reveals that adequate equipped emergency departments are important in emergency responses. The relationships showed here are even more inclusive across multiple facilities indicating the coincidences of inputs and dependencies in care emergencies that cross and connect departments and equipment.

Outpatient Services Efficiency: There was a significant increasing relationship between the efficiency of outpatient services and the Emergency Rooms with the coefficients $r = .546$ at $p < 0.01$ and the Operating Theatres with the coefficients $r = .516$ at $p < 0.01$ and the Pharmacies with the coefficients $r = .501$ at $p < 0.01$ and X-ray machines with the coefficients $r = .265$ at $p < 0.01$. This means that these facilities are very important as far as the effective running of the outpatient services are concerned. The absence of the high correlation with any other facilities, like MRI machines or CT scanners may be explained by the fact that the former is more connected with

specialized or inpatient care and the latter is more associated with the basic service for outpatients.

Inpatient Services Efficiency: Efficiency of inpatient services has a positive relationship with the number of X-ray machines, Emergency Rooms, Operating Theatres, Pharmacies, Cardiology departments, Pediatrics departments, Orthopedics departments, and ICU facilities with coefficients of $r = .293, .448, .276, .273, .218, .345, .191,$ and $.436$, all being significant at 0.01 level of significance. Such correlations represent comprehensive relations of inpatient care as being delivered by a number of departments and facilities and aimed at the greatest effectiveness of the provided service in relation to the patients admitted to the hospital.

Diagnostic Services Efficiency: The efficiency of diagnostic services has positive notable correlation with Operating Theatres ($r = .455, P < 0.01$), Ultrasound Machines ($r = .343, P < 0.01$), Pharmacies ($r = .344, P < 0.01$), Cardiology departments ($r = 0.334, P < 0.01$), Orthopedics departments ($r = .360, P < 0.01$). These findings raise the need to have a competent diagnostic department so as to enable fast and accurate diagnosis of various ailments that are important in planning and implementing proper treatment plans.

Summarizing, more favorable relationship between hospital equipment and facilities demonstrate that in general the presence of certain equipment and facilities has positive effect on performance of various functions in the hospital. For instance, Emergency Rooms, Operating Theatres and ICU have a high correlation with a number of performance indicators and can be viewed as key facilities for both every day and emergency situations. These relationships in this table can help hospital administrators know where to focus spending on departments and equipment that can beef up the performance of the hospital in general.

4.9.3. Correlation of different components of Leadership evaluation

Table 26 4.23. Pearson correlation coefficients between various leadership characteristics.

		Correlations													
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
	Hospitals		LE 1	LE 2	LE 3	LE 4	LE 5	LE 6	LE 7	LE 8	LE 9	LE 10	LE 11	LE 12	LE 13
1	R	0.043													
2	R	-0.096	.821**												
3	R	-.182**	.779**	.806**											
4	R	-.193**	.676**	.793**	.723**										
5	R	-0.107	.582**	.584**	.618**	.561**									
6	R	-.152*	.767**	.709**	.711**	.658**	.486**								
7	R	-0.011	.615**	.649**	.746**	.578**	.655**	.588**							
8	R	0.005	.355**	.374**	.404**	.579**	.637**	.426**	.490**						
9	R	0.080	.724**	.697**	.624**	.727**	.728**	.527**	.665**	.671**					
10	R	-0.123	.687**	.680**	.769**	.690**	.374**	.742**	.499**	.377**	.575**				
11	R	-.266**	.518**	.535**	.608**	.614**	.532**	.661**	.583**	.572**	.581**	.632**			
12	R	-0.115	.729**	.756**	.759**	.820**	.542**	.724**	.642**	.516**	.754**	.758**	.747**		
13	R	.187**	.188**	.243**	0.077	.400**	.416**	.253**	.186**	.604**	.461**	0.124	.342**	.295**	
14	R	0.125	.138*	0.038	0.080	.319**	.323**	.228**	.398**	.643**	.405**	0.135	.395**	.207**	.673**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The hospital leadership provides a clear vision for the future. (LE1)

The hospital has a well-defined strategic plan that is effectively communicated. (LE2)

The leadership makes decisions in a timely and efficient manner. (LE3)

Leaders effectively solve problems and address challenges. (LE4)

There is open and transparent communication between leadership and staff. (LE5)

The leadership regularly provides updates and information about hospital operations. (LE6)

Leadership provides adequate support for staff professional development. (LE7)
The hospital invests in training and development programs for its staff. (LE8)
The leadership prioritizes patient care and safety. (LE9)
Leaders ensure that the hospital follows best practices for patient safety. (LE10)
The leadership encourages innovation in healthcare delivery. (LE11)
The hospital leadership is committed to continuous improvement. (LE12)
The leadership effectively manages the hospital's financial resources. (LE13)
Leaders make sound financial decisions that benefit the hospital. (LE14)

Source: Primary Data

Table 4.23 uses Pearson correlation coefficients to show the interconnection that exist between different leadership characteristics with in the hospitals. These coefficients are between negative one and positive one; they indicate the extent of the relationships between various leadership attributes as to whether they are positively or negatively related.

Leadership Vision (LE1): the relationship between the leadership's vision for the future (H2a) and other factors is couched in some interesting compromises. The greatest degree of association is indicated by the strong positive correlation with the hospital's strategic plan of LE2 with $r = 0.821$, $p < 0.01$, which identifies that comprehensible vision implies clear and well communicated strategic leadership strategy in addition, there is a moderate significant correlation between the vision and LE3, at the $r = 0.779$, $p < 0.01$, suggesting that with vision the leaders will be better placed to comprehend the impact of their timely decisions.

Strategic Planning (LE2): Strategic planning (LE2) is identified as a fundamental leadership competency that has a high positive association with timely decision making (LE3) with a correlation of $r = 0.806$ and, Correlation coefficient, $r = 0.793$, respectively, both at $p < 0.01$ level these analyses highlight that the hospitals that receive good scores for communicating their strategic plans are more likely to be effective in the strategic decision making and in responding to challenges faster. Likewise, the correlation of LE2 to LE5 is at $r = 0.582$, $p < 0.$

01, it was realized that strategic clarity enhances the relationship between the leadership and other staff in an organization.

Decision-Making (LE3): Problem solving (LE4) is strongly related with timely decision making (LE3) with the value of 'r' being equal to $r = 0.723$, $p < 0.01$. This indicates the fact that decision makers are more efficient in solving the problems by gaining the support for professional development $r = .649$, $p < 0.01$, suggests that intensified leadership in the field of decision-making also means recognition of the employees' professional development.

Problem-Solving (LE4): conclude that problem solving (LE4) has very strong positive relationships with other two dimensions of leadership practice namely open communication (LE5) and leadership updates (LE6) with coefficients of $r = 0.561$ and $r = 0.658$, respectively, both and $p < 0.01$. These correlations indicate that the leaders with good problem-solving skills also ensure that the 'line of communication' is always open and that the staff is informed from time to time about some operations in the hospital that might affect organizational culture and communication.

Communication and Transparency (LE5): Rather high positive correlations are found between open and transparent communication (LE5) and several other leadership characteristics, and leadership updates (LE6) in particular, with $r = 0.486$, $p < 0.01$ and third, there was significant relationship with support for professional development LE7 with the coefficient of $r = 0.578$, $p < 0.01$. Consequently, these correlations suggest that employment of an open leadership style tends to be linked to keeping staff informed and / or staff development.

Staff Development (LE7) and Training (8): Two sub-constructs are leadership's support for professional development (LE7) and investment in staff training (LE8); these bear strong relationships with other leadership dimensions. Also, LE7 has a strong positive correlation with prioritization of patient care as indicated by LE9 correlation of equals, $r = 0.527$, $p < 0.01$, this implies that leaders who support their staff professional development needs are also committed to patient safety, has a closer relationship with the innovation in health care delivery, at $r = 0.490$, $p < 0.01$ indicated that the level of investment put into training is an influential factor that encourages innovations in facilities that are owned by the hospital.

Patient Safety (LE9) and Best Practices (LE10): These references regarding patient safety (LE9) are highly associated with the compliance with the best practices (LE10) with the correlation coefficient of $r = 0.575$, $p < 0.01$ which demonstrated a positive moderation of a leadership focus on patient care on best practices. The correlation between LE9 and LE10 is positive with the hospital's commitment to continuity improvement (LE12) = 0.575 $p < 0.01$, It also continues to reiterate that the focus on patient safety has often initiated broader improvement in the organization.

Innovation (LE11) and Continuous Improvement (LE12): Hence, there is a very strong positive relationship between innovation in healthcare delivery [$r = 0.801$] (LE11) and continuous improvement (LE12). 0.747 , $p < 0.01$, they are leaders that have embraced concern for continuous improvements in specific operations in a hospital. That is why this relationship reveals the interaction between the two key aspects of successful hospital management, namely innovation and constant development.

Financial Management is the LE13 and LE14: Financial management (LE13) has moderate positive relationship with making sound financial decisions (LE14) with correlation coefficient of 0. 673, $p < 0. 01$ We can infer from this that a good financial management can be coupled with what one does to the Hospital’s financials. Likewise, both LE13 and LE14 depict a positive correlation with leadership updates (LE6) and innovation (LE11) suggesting that the Hospital’s sound finance supports the leader’s efficient communication as well as invention.

Overall, the table presents a system of leadership attributes all of which have mutual relationships, where successful leadership is defined by presence of vision, planning, open communication, staff support, focus on patient needs, creativity, and sound financial management. These related attributes demonstrate an observable fact that supports the complex interlinkages of hospital leadership and organizational productivity.

4.9.4. Correlation between various financial management practices and overall hospital financial health

Table 27 4.24. Correlation between various financial management practices and overall hospital financial health

Correlations												
	Hospitals	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11
M1	.191**											
M2	.253**	.841*										
M3	.093	.706*	.695*									
M4	.006	.722*	.702*	.610*								
M5	.080	.593*	.676*	.614*	.526*							

			*	*	*	*							
M6		-.147*	387*	447*	344*	461*	652*						
M7		0.003	499*	573*	659*	558*	571*	413*					
M8		0.126	616*	630*	537*	631*	736*	611*	646*				
M9		.175*	500*	664*	685*	533*	725*	483*	529*	730*			
M10		.253**	457*	558*	464*	320*	603*	438*	427*	579*	610*		
M11		.152*	388*	434*	497*	331*	504*	525*	289*	576*	692*	801*	
M12		.211**	609*	679*	587*	593*	619*	463*	499*	667*	732*	769*	652*

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The hospital has a clear and detailed budget plan. (FM1)

Resources are allocated efficiently according to the hospital's needs. (FM2)

The hospital has effective revenue collection systems in place. (FM3)

There are diverse sources of revenue for the hospital. (FM4)

Expenditures are tracked accurately and regularly. (FM5)

The hospital implements cost-saving measures without compromising quality. (FM6)

Financial reports are generated regularly and shared with relevant stakeholders. (FM7)

There is transparency in the hospital's financial transactions. (FM8)

The hospital invests in essential medical equipment and infrastructure. (FM9)

There are adequate funds for ongoing projects and hospital improvements. (FM10)

The hospital has strategies in place to manage financial risks. (FM11)

Contingency plans are available for financial emergencies. (FM12)

Source: Primary Data

The correlation table 4.24. Gives an understanding of various correlations between different aspects of financial management and general state of affairs of a hospital's finances. When data is collected concerning the level of detail in the budget and resource use, we get a strong positive correlation, $r = .841$. An important implication of this research therefore is that such plans must be well laid and fine detailed in order to ensure proper use of resources in the hospital. It also includes effective revenue collection systems ($r = .706$) and the monitoring of expenditures ($r = .593$) and it was observed that there is a positive relationship between the two and the detailed budget plan supporting again the essence of the financial plan.

The strong positive relationship between the effectiveness of demonstrated cost containment policies and expenditure control ($r = .652$) supports the idea that it is possible to improve revenues without straining the available quality. Besides, greater emphasis is placed on the transparency of financial operations, the higher the correlation with accurate tracking of expenditures is ($r = .736$), which means that hospitals with high degrees of transparency are likely to be more efficient in managing their expenses.

Funding for primary healthcare, medical equipment and infrastructure is significantly related to sufficient funds for sustaining projects and the improvement of hospital facilities ($r = .610$) as well as with plans to mitigate risks to funds ($r = .692$). This means that hospitals that adequately invest in their bridges and building are in a better position to address financial hitches hence enhancing project sustainability.

Surprisingly, the generation and sharing of regular financial reports are moderately related to transparency in the financial transactions ($r = .646$, $p < .01$) which indicate that reporting has some role to play in practices regarding money. Additionally, having diverse sources of revenue

for the total hospital income show a positive relationship with efficient resource management ($r = .702$) and financial transparency ($r = .631$) This means that diversifying the sources of the income of a hospital would enhance better management of resources within the hospital.

Finally, contingency planning for financial emergencies has fairly significant positive coefficients with all forms of practicable financial management, which include provisions for the funding of current projects as well as measures to counter financial risks ($r = .769$) and ($r = .652$), respectively. This goes to show that one must however have backup strategies in case of such a situation which threatens the financial security of an entity.

Lastly, the correlations emphasize the importance of prudent financial practices, namely budgeting, revelation of information, fiscal reports, and dominant investment to hospitals' financial viability.

4.9.5. Correlation between financial management practices and their impact on hospital operations and patient outcomes

Table 28 4.25. Correlation between financial management practices and their impact on hospital operations and patient outcomes

Correlations												
	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12
SM1 F	575*	482*	444*	315*	602*	559*	426*	471*	397*	404*	375*	340*
SM2 F	442*	488*	605*	292*	574*	441*	418*	450*	644*	683*	711*	502*
SM3 F	582*	684*	477*	483*	484*	259*	372*	597*	676*	567*	597*	710*
SM4 F	303*	481*	646*	516*	450*	252*	354*	425*	684*	510*	632*	609*

SM5	F	633*	739*	533*	494*	590*	593*	502*	556*	581*	571*	541*	688*
SM6	F	139*	307*	339*	331*	479*	524*	176*	377*	606*	588*	668*	489*
SM7	F	588*	707*	614*	571*	530*	339*	492*	624*	705*	558*	595*	639*
SM8	F	596*	658*	479*	531*	618*	468*	478*	641*	653*	578*	566*	598*
SM9	F	556*	577*	443*	385*	589*	537*	393*	498*	578*	624*	646*	500*
SM10	F	368*	387*	679*	353*	389*	385*	479*	391*	570*	503*	607*	531*
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).													
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).													
Effective financial management has improved the quality of patient care. (FSM1)													
Financial constraints do not compromise patient care. (FSM2)													
Patients have better access to health services due to sound financial management. (FSM3)													
There are no significant delays in service delivery due to financial issues. (FSM4)													
Adequate financial resources ensure sufficient staffing levels. (FSM5)													
Staff receive timely salaries and benefits. (FSM6)													
The hospital maintains up-to-date medical equipment due to good financial practices. (FSM7)													
Infrastructure improvements are regularly made to enhance service delivery. (FSM8)													
Financially sound management practices have led to higher patient satisfaction. (FSM9)													
Patients are generally satisfied with the cost of services provided. (FSM10)													

Source: Primary Data

The table 4.25, Shows Correlation between many financial management practices and their impact on hospital operations and patient outcomes:

This study also shows that better financial management do go hand in hand with improvement in quality of patient care. In turn, significant positive relationships are reported between having detailed/ clear budget ($r = .575$), proper resources management ($r = .482$) and the

quality of the care offered to patients. Likewise, there is high correlation between tracking of expenditure with improved patient care ($r = .602$), measures in place for cost reduction ($r = .559$), and financial accountability and transparency ($r = .471$). These relationships imply that sound management of financial processes plays a major role in enhancing clients' status by guaranteeing the right allocation of resources and keeping a close check on the expenses.

It can therefore be concluded that financial practices seem not to have a negative impact on patient care as demonstrated in the positive correlation between the two categories. For example, availability of multiple sources of funds ($r = .605$) and efficient revenues streams ($r = .488$) are positively correlated with quality of care of patients. Also, adequate provision of financial resources for sustaining current work programs ($r = .683$) as well as provision of financial risks ($r = .711$) have a high relationship with staff performance especially in health sectors in delivering quality patient care. This means that the opportunity to improve financial position of health care units and hospitals is strongly associated with their better performance even in cases of limited financial resources.

Sound financial management has a positive direct relationship with availability and use of health services among the patients. Pervasive monetary behaviors for instance, having a well-organized budget ($r = .582$) and financing medical equipment ($r = .484$) correspond to better healthcare accessibility. Additionally, a link between what was tested on financial management and decrease in delays of service delivery ($r = .303$) holds that if managing finance effectively minimizes those issues that could derail patient access.

This is evident by the high correlations obtained in this area, and these include the case of availability of financial resources which ensures that there is adequate human resource available.

Good financial practices have significant positive relationship with staffing ($r = 0.633$) and payment of salaries/benefits in time to the staff ($r = 0.139$). This goes to show that financial stability is paramount when it comes to recruitment and management of employees which in extension has a direct positivist impact on patient care and organizational effectiveness.

Careful decisions are also associated with an up to date medical equipment and infrastructure enhancements. Significant positive correlations with the possession of contemporary apparatus ($r = .588$) and routine enhancement of infrastructural features ($r = .596$) reveal that strong managerial skills in financial matters empower hospitals to afford important upgrades and upgrades hence, enhancing the general service delivery capacity of a hospital.

Also, there is a positive relationship between financial management practices and patient satisfaction. It was observed that higher, sound levels of financial management equals to greater level of patient satisfaction ($r = .556$) This fact was also an evidence that the management who practices sound financial should pay attention to patient's numeracy since it affects their satisfaction level of the value of the services they received. This is backed up by the relationship between patient satisfaction and expense of services offered ($r = .368$) which shows that management of finances can in one way or the other affect how patients perceive costs and quality of the services being offered.

Therefore, the findings of this research confirm that good financial stewardship plays a critical role in the multifaceted healthcare organization performance, namely quality of services, access, staffing, equipment maintenance, and patients' satisfaction.

4.9.6. Correlation between hospital and the competencies of medical staff

Table 29 4.26. Correlation between hospital and the competencies of medical staff

Correlations														
	Hospitals	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13
C1	.140*													
C2	.214**	.619**												
C3	.302**	.584**	.708**											
C4	.169*	.339**	.597**	.617**										
C5	.205**	.748**	.697**	.741**	.751**									
C6	.100	.738**	.656**	.642**	.347**	.575**								
C7	0.037	.722**	.520**	.619**	.236**	.502**	.805**							
C8	.056	.766**	.710**	.494**	.387**	.658**	.757**	.642**						
C9	0.006	.551**	.477**	.539**	.467**	.531**	.687**	.733**	.672**					
C10	.126	.653**	.734**	.564**	.414**	.630**	.761**	.594**	.770**	.587**				
C11	.057	.517**	.694**	.608**	.479**	.548**	.590**	.637**	.591**	.612**	.687**			
C12	0.070	.361	.535	.423	.607	.487	.521	.439	.540	.630	.595	.670		

2			**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**		
C1	0	.045	565	664	607	518	629	492	521	552	530	712	754	663	
3			**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	
C1	-	.199*	589	458	462	464	548	628	696	526	691	540	644	617	545
4		*	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).															
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).															
The medical staff have the necessary qualifications and skills to provide high-quality care. (WC1)															
Continuous training and education programs are available for clinical staff. (WC2)															
The technical staff are proficient in operating medical equipment and technologies. ((WC3)															
Technical staff receive regular training on new equipment and technologies. (WC4)															
The hospital workforce demonstrates effective communication skills with patients and families. (WC5)															
There is good communication and teamwork among hospital staff. (WC6)															
The staff adhere to best practices and protocols for patient safety. (WC7)															
Workforce competencies positively impact patient care quality. (WC8)															
The staff are capable of making sound decisions in critical situations. (WC9)															
Problem-solving skills are emphasized and developed among the workforce. (WC10)															
The hospital has effective leadership and management training programs. (WC11)															
Leadership skills among the staff contribute to efficient hospital operations. (WC12)															
The workforce is trained to provide culturally sensitive care. (WC13)															
Cultural competence training improves patient satisfaction and outcomes. (WC14)															

Source: Primary data

The table 4. 26. Provides Pearson correlation coefficients to indicate the extent and direction of the various factors with regards to hospital capacity and the competency of the medical, technical and hospital administrative personnel. These correlations as suggested are highly significant at the 0. 05 level are indicated by a single asterisk (*), if there are a two asterisks (**) then the result is significant level at the 0.01.

It was also found that as a result, the medical staff's qualifications and their performance has a positive correlation with the general hospital performance (r = 0.140). Also, the orientation programs for clinical staff offer a more encouraging efficacy with regard to constant treatment

that affect hospital performance ($r = 0.214$), thereby supporting that constant learning contributes positively to hospital results. The efficiency of technical staff to operate the equipment's involves also a positive relationship to hospital performance ($r = 0.302$) which underline the significance of technical input in the operation of hospitals.

This very much applies to force communication skills while conducting communication with the patients and also force communication skills or internal interpersonal communication skills in a forcing hospital. Hospitals that are successful in patient and family's communication deliver high performances ($r=0.205$), Furthermore, it is also seen that, communication and coordination with other hospital employee, although do not have a great relation with hospital performance itself Correlation Coefficient ($r = 0.100$), have strong positive relation with other variables which include compliance with best practices and patient safety risk management Correlation Coefficient correlation $r = 0.805$.

The results found also indicate that type of equipment being trained with technical staff is related to their proficiency ($r=0.617$) and hospital performance ($r=0.169$). Leadership and management training programs have a moderate positive relationship with problem solving skills ($r = 0.687$), and operational health care services ($r = 0.590$) thus indicated. In this case it emerged that there is a positive correlation between cultural competence training and patient satisfaction and results, ($r = 0.545$); however, it is negatively associated with the overall hospital performance ($r = -0.199$). This indicates that although cultural competence enhances the individual encounters with patients, it may have little bearing on other organizational parameters cutting across Hospitals.

Finally, using the correlation data, one may highlight qualifications, continuity training, technical skills, oral communication and leadership training as the elements significant for the Hospital performance. Despite the fact that cultural competence is vital for patient satisfaction it seem to have mediocre effect on the overall performance of the hospital and this warrants more research.

4.9.7. Correlation between various workforce competencies and their impact on hospital performance

Table 30 4.27. Correlation between various workforce competencies and their impact on hospital performance

Correlations														
	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6	C7	C8	C9	C10	C11	C12	C13	C14
W CSD1	453 **	430 **	369 **	.13 4	283 **	594 **	674 **	504 **	494 **	432 **	586 **	348 **	434 **	569 **
W CSD2	528 **	280 **	309 **	.09 5	321 **	629 **	643 **	601 **	574 **	459 **	465 **	300 **	396 **	539 **
W CSD3	665 **	417 **	342 **	173 *	425 **	732 **	668 **	677 **	611 **	615 **	527 **	377 **	457 **	510 **
W CSD4	327 **	294 **	310 **	431 **	405 **	483 **	396 **	343 **	584 **	350 **	380 **	627 **	440 **	512 **
W CSD5	655 **	528 **	405 **	170 *	479 **	656 **	626 **	594 **	532 **	671 **	535 **	443 **	555 **	465 **
W CSD6	662 **	374 **	296 **	259 **	489 **	673 **	582 **	588 **	550 **	583 **	381 **	435 **	434 **	555 **
W CSD7	670 **	528 **	548 **	264 **	578 **	687 **	645 **	604 **	487 **	585 **	511 **	341 **	536 **	435 **
W CSD8	565 **	542 **	451 **	166 *	403 **	678 **	667 **	542 **	491 **	586 **	593 **	393 **	616 **	543 **
W CSD9	585	418	281	342	569	577	492	613	547	474	352	455	462	478

		**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**	**
W CSD1 0		384 **	266 **	340 **	354 **	397 **	555 **	602 **	388 **	554 **	333 **	357 **	593 **	403 **	603 **
W CSD1 1		251 **	215 **	204 **	288 **	285 **	337 **	431 **	342 **	510 **	236 **	295 **	504 **	334 **	482 **
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).															
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).															
Workforce competencies have improved the quality of patient care. (WCSD1)															
Competent staff ensure adherence to clinical guidelines and standards. (WCSD2)															
High workforce competencies contribute to better patient safety outcomes. (WCSD3)															
Staff competencies help in reducing medical errors and adverse events. (WCSD4)															
Efficiency of Service Delivery (WCSD5)															
Competent staff enhance the efficiency of hospital operations. (WCSD6)															
Workforce competencies lead to reduced waiting times for patients. (WCSD7)															
Patient satisfaction is higher due to the competencies of the hospital workforce. (WCSD8)															
Competent staff provide better patient education and support. (WCSD9)															
Competent staff drive innovation in healthcare practices and services. (WCSD10)															
Continuous improvement initiatives are supported by workforce competencies. (WCSD11)															

Source: Primary data

The table 4.27, shows Correlation analysis between various workforce competencies and their impact on hospital performance, including patient care quality, safety, efficiency, and satisfaction.

It can also be concluded that workforce competencies have direct relation with the level of health care services that patients receive. For example, the medical staff competency in terms of qualifications, experience and skills ($r = .453^{**}$) have a direct correlation to quality of care. Other factors that strengthen workforce competencies and thus, patients' outcomes include training and educating initiatives ($r = .430^{**}$) that are ongoing. Moreover, the knowledge of technical staff about how to operate the different types of medical equipment ($r = .369^{**}$) and

how to take wise decisions during the emergency situations ($r = .504^{**}$) are important in order to provide good quality of care.

For example, increase in the quantity and quality of competent staff ensures that clinical guidelines and standards are closely followed; as evidenced by the positive and strong relationship between staff competencies and actualization of protocols ($r = .528^{**}$). High Workforce Competence brings out more competent workforce which is associated with better patient safety outcomes ($r = .665^{**}$) this therefore shows that to enhance patient safety well qualified staff should be employed. This is backed by the positive relationship between staff competencies and disappearance of medical errors as shown by the coefficient of ($r = .327^{**}$), arguing for staff professionalism through continual professional development.

Increased performance in service delivery is always underpinned by the quality of human resource in the health facility, which is reflected by the workforce of the hospital in the current case. The efficiency of utilization of workforce competencies in improving the operations in various hospitals has been shown by the high correlations between the workforce competencies and efficiency of hospital operation, ($r = .655^{**}$). They also contribute to the reduction of patient waiting time through the efficient delivery of services which in turn increases the level of satisfaction among the patients ($r = .670^{**}$).

The competencies of the hospital workforce have a very close bearing on the level of satisfaction of patients. Qualified personnel have a positive relationship with patient's satisfaction ($r = .565^{**}$), this may be because of charged staff's capacity to produce enhanced patient counseling and encouraging ($r = .585^{**}$). This implies that staff do not only improve the

quality of care that is provided to patients, they also improve the perception of the patients by offering educative and supportive services.

Qualitative staff who are employed competently are in a position to encourage innovation of practices and services by proving positive correlation whereby, correlation coefficient ($r = 0.384^{**}$) for innovation in practices. Further, workforce competencies correlate with significantly enhancing sustainability through continuous improvement ($r = .251^{**}$), suggesting that competent and informed people are instrumental in the process of creating sustainable processes.

Altogether, the correlations demand that qualifications and skills, updating, communication, and competencies of the workforce are the essentials to raise the quality of the clients' care, obey the clinical standards, stabilize the safety of the patients, and increase the effectiveness and satisfaction of the clients. You will therefore see that investment in staff training is imperative for better health outcomes and staff efficiency.

4.10. Line graphs

4.10. 1. Charts of Impacts of Hospital Capacity on Health Services

Figure 1. Overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the quality of health services delivered?

Figure 0.1

Figure 2. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on patient satisfaction?

Figure 0.2

Figure 3. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the efficiency of service delivery?

Figure 0.3

Figure 4. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?

Figure 0.4

Figure 5. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the hospital's financial performance?

Figure 0.5

The above figures give a Line graphs that shows how respondents ranked the overall importance of their hospital capacity on the quality of health services delivered, patient satisfaction, efficiency of service delivery, ability of the hospital to handle emergencies and financial performance of the hospital. The horizontal axis is the distribution of results for different impact ranging from 'Very Negative' to 'Very Positive' while the vertical axis shows the number of participants in each category. According to the results of the study, more than half of the respondents are of the view that capacity of the hospital has a positive influence on health services produced. This uptake in what could be termed as general satisfaction underscores the capacity of the hospitals to improve on service delivery. The paper revealed little negative feedback on health facility capacity gives credence to the perception that it is regarded a key enabler in the delivery of health services.

4.10.2. Charts of Impacts of Hospital Leadership on Health Services

Figure 6. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the quality of health services delivered?

Figure 0.6

Figure 7. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on patient satisfaction?

Figure 0.7

Figure 8. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the efficiency of service delivery?

Figure 0.8

Figure 9. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?

Figure 0.9

Figure 10. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the hospital's financial performance?

Figure 0.10

The Figures 6 – 10, present frequency distributions for respondents' ratings on the overall impact of their hospital's leadership across several dimensions: quality of healthcare services that is delivered to the patients, the level of satisfaction of the patients, the delivery of care services in the health facilities, their capacity to tackle any emergency situations, and their financial performance. Every aspect was measured on a 'Very Negative,' 'Negative,' 'Neutral,' and 'Positive' and 'Very Positive' based on the opinions about the effectiveness of the hospital leadership.

In figure 6. About leadership effects on the quality of health services the following findings were established 31. Nine percent of the respondents rated it as 'Very Positive' while 35 percent as 'Positive' Responses to the statement were divided into six categories of which 2 % are categorized as "Positive" meaning that 67% of the respondents are supportive of the

statement made in the argument. One percent of participants perusing leadership have a positive effect on service quality. However, 15. 2% said it as “Very Negative” and 9. as negative, it consists with only 5% while 24% of the respondents are perceiving it negatively. The remaining 8. A 1% for neutral point, while is rather ambiguous, still points to the fact that leadership in this respect is viewed, to a certain extent, negatively, nevertheless rather more positive. In figure 7. Concerning the patients’ satisfaction index, it was 42. In case of the impact of leadership, 9% of the respondents were of the opinion that it was “Very Positive”, while 35% said it was “Positive”. For instance, the “Positive” category obtained 2% while giving an overall majority of 78% for the entire analysis. 1% with favorable views. A smaller group, 13. 3% described it as “Neutral”, 3% as “Positive” and 6 % as “Negative”. 2% of them rated it as “Very Negative” which shows some sort of discontentment. Only 2. self-trained leadership = 4% were neutral = suggesting that in general, leadership has a positive effect towards patient satisfaction whereby the responses have been construed in an extremely positive light with little middle ground.

In figure 8. For the efficiency of service delivery, the respondent rated the impact as 44.3% of respondents said that leadership is “Very Positive which is 33.8% and “Positive” in total B eight percent ‘Positive’ with seventy-eight total score. 1% expressing favorable opinions. Only 3. 3% consider the impact as “Negative”, 5. 2% of respondents identified the sentiment at 2% very negative; 13 % as negative. 3% were neutral.: These responses affirm a strong belief that leadership influences efficiency of service delivery for the better with only a paltry showing negative sentiment. In figure 9, With respect to the role of leadership on the hospitals preparedness for emergencies, 30. No one described it as “Very Positive” while 39%. 5% as “Positive,” resulting to a total of 69% if the totals of the remaining choices are added together. who, Of the total respondents 5% of them believe that there would be a positive impact on their

business. However, 11.4% considered it as “Negative,” and 7%. 6% as “Very Negative”, this means that approximately one sixth of the respondents are worried regarding effectiveness of leaderships in preparedness and responsiveness during emergencies. The neutral response was 11.4% they admitted they were not very sure on some of the questions they answered.

In figure 10, Regarding the leadership and its influence of financial performance of hospital, 33.8% of respondents saw it as “Very Positive and 35%. 7% as “Positive,” adding up to 69%. 5% positive response. However, 11.9% selected it as “Negative,” Whereas; 12%. The scores breakdown for the “Leadership Impact” is as follows: 12% as “Positive,” 41% as “Neutral” and 47% as “Very Negative” this means that almost a quarter of the respondents are dissatisfied with the impact leadership has had on financial performance. The switch of the analysis had a neutral response of 5.7% which means that though the majority of the participants had relatively positive perception of leadership’s financial impact the perception was also fairly divided.

On average, most of the respondent across the different dimensions noted indicate that leadership in their respective hospital has a positive impression on the hospital particularly in the area of patient satisfaction and improved service delivery. These views are always present in numbers although a minority that will in most cases present neutral or negative views about issues like response to disasters and financial health. These results further imply the need to consider the perception holder’s concerns especially those with negative perceptions on how to enhance leadership effectiveness in all these domains.

4.10.3. Charts of Impacts of Hospital's financial management on Health services delivered

Figure 11. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the quality of health services delivered?

Figure 0.11

Figure 12. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on patient satisfaction?

Figure 0.12

Figure 13. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the efficiency of service delivery?

Figure 0.13

Figure 14. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?

Figure 0.14

Figure 15. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the hospital's financial stability?

Figure 0.15

The figures 11 – 15, provide frequency distributions for respondents' ratings on the overall impact of their hospital's financial management across various dimensions: patient satisfaction,

effectiveness of delivering services, response to calamities, and financial viability of the health services organizations. Each aspect was assessed with the help of the scale that ranges from “Very negative” to “Very positive” and the data is the respondents’ one.

In Figure 11. About the effects of financial management on the quality of health services, 41. Four-point percent of respondents rated it as Very Positive and twenty-one percent as somewhat positive. 9% of the respondents gave their perception a positive rating of 9% while the rest gave it 6%. 3% of the participants find it has a positive outcome. On the contrary, 11. 4% considered it to be” Negative,” while 4. The 3% of them embraced ‘Very Negative’ opinion meaning that there are less people with a negative perception towards the product. The remaining 21. No respondent was neutral; indicating that even though the majority of the respondents see financial management as a positive force towards increasing service quality, there is still a block of the population with neutral or even negative attitudes towards the subject. In figure 12. Regarding the patients’ satisfaction, 40. Another 5% of the respondents said it was “Very Positive” while 29%. 0% as “Positive,” and a cumulative of 69 percent nodded to it. 5% of who had something positive to say. A smaller group, 11. In terms of positively impacted stakeholders: 0% rated the impact as “Positive”, 0% as “Neutral” and 2% as “Negative”. they are 1% “Negative”, 8% “Somewhat Negative” and 9% “Very Negative” referring to low levels of dissatisfaction. There was 16 Neutral. 7% I believe that this shows the general population is convinced that financial management is to the benefit of patient satisfaction but there are those who are in-between or have a contrary view as the remaining 7% shows.

In figure 13. Concerning the effectiveness of service delivery, it obtained 35. Seven percent of respondents said that its impact was ‘Very Positive,’ while 29%. Positive response

percentages were as follows: 0% as “Positive,” and overall, a 64. 7% with favorable opinions. However, 12. 4% chose “Negative”, and 4%. 3% as “Very Negative,” and 18. 6% were neutral. Such responses suggest that although the majority of the participants understood that financial management assists in enhancing the efficiency of service delivery, there were still many other respondents whose attitudes were either neutral or negative. In figure 14. Concerning on the notion of emergency interventions, 36 out of 91 respondents opined that the availability of social media in hospital affected the capacity of the hospital to address emergency incidents. 7% of the respondent associated it with” Very Positive” while 28. As a result of the particularization of the components of the scale, 6% of the results are categorized as “Positive,” resulting in an overall 65. 3 % for those that want it to have a positive effect. However, 17. That is, 1% of respondents rated it as “Negative”, and 5%. Another 7% has chosen “Very Negative” which means more than one fifth of the respondents have some doubts as to the readiness of financial management to respond to emergencies. The remaining 11. 9% were those that could be categorized as having a ‘neutral’ outlook which suggests that they are somewhat uncertain or have had some degree of bad experiences.

In figure 15. On financial stability of the hospital, its score is 36. 7% mentioned that they considered it as ‘Very Positive’ while 30. 5% under the heading “Positive”, 67. 2 % of the respondents regarded financial management as having strong positive correlation with financial stability. A smaller group, 13. 8% said it had a “Negative” impact while 2. 9% as “Very Negative” that revealed comparatively low level of dissatisfaction. The percentage of neutral response was 16 percent. 2%, which means that in spite of the general optimism on the overall influence of financial management on financial stability indicated by the respondents, there are still those who are indifferent or unsure.

Furthermore, majorities across all the dimensions believe the financial management of their hospital is positive, and the highest positive scores are noted in “Quality of Health Services” and “Financial Stability”. Although there is a consistent negative/ neutral response from a few percentages in areas such as emergency response and efficiency of service delivery. Such variation is very important in order to consider the dissatisfied respondents and make all the respondents have a common perception of the efficiency of the given hospital’s financial management.

4.10.4. Charts of Impacts of Hospital's Workforce competences on Health services delivered

Figure 16. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on the quality of health services delivered?

Figure 0.16

Figure 17. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on patient satisfaction?

Figure 0.17

Figure 18. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on the efficiency of service delivery?

Figure 0.18

Figure 19. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on patient safety?

Figure 0.19

Figure 20. How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on innovation and improvement?

Figure 0.20

The Figures 16 – 20, present frequency distributions for respondents' ratings on the overall impact of their hospital's workforce competencies across several dimensions: nature: regards to improving the quality of health services, the satisfaction of patients, the efficiency of service delivery and utilization, the safety of patients and the innovation/improvement. All of them were answered on a Very Negative/Very Positive Scale The scale is described as follows:

In figure 16. As for the Effects of workforce competencies on the quality of the health services, there are 44. 3% of respondents chose the option 'Very Positive' while 10. 5% as "Positive" which literally means that over 50% as 55. 7% hold a positive attitude towards the impact. Conversely, 28. 1% chose "Negative" on the impact assessment and 3., and 8% Very Negative indicating the very negative perception on the issue among a percentage of the society. 13. 3% remained neutral. Such distribution indicates an overall positivity in respondents' perceptions, while at the same time a certain number of respondents voiced their concerns. In figure 17. As for the effect on patient satisfaction, 38. One percent of respondents whose experience matched the observation rated the product experience as "Very Positive"; while 12 percent as "Positive". 9% only reacted to the article as "Positive," and 49% of the participants were neutral. Negative views were reported by 14. 3% of respondents; while 7. 1% rated the impact as of Very Negative Perception All the responses show a slight slant of positive perceptions, although a considerable number chose the middle ground as their perception may have varied or even if they had a negative experience, they may also have experienced positive outcomes.

In figure 18. Presented efficiency of service delivery, 33. As for the impact assessments, 8% of the respondents described the impact as "Very Positive", 17% described it as "Positive". 6

% as “Positive”, They represent 51% of the whole study. 4% of favorable responses. On the other hand, only 23.8% said that it is “Negative” and 7. Very Negative” accounted for only 1% while the remaining 17. In agreement, a varied 6% of participants preferred an undefined position. The results about this perception seem more diverse and are rather polarized in certain sense. Regarding figure 19. presented the effect on patient safety, 36.7% of the respondents rated it as “Very Positive while 16%. Workforce competencies as a subject received 2 % rating as “Positive,” meaning that more than half the number (52. However, 25.7% selected “Negative” on the impact scale while 5. This is followed by 2% as “Very Negative”, thus there are issues of concern considering that this group is among a quarter of the respondents. The remaining 15.7% were in the middle, which makes it clear that while the majority are willing to see the positive side of the impact, there also are those who are skeptical about it.

In figure 20. Impact on innovation and improvement was responded by 40% of the respondents with ‘Very Positive’ and 15.7% as ‘Positive’ in which 55.7% of the respondents have a positive perception. On the other hand, the strategy was supported by 14.3% responded it as “Negative,” and 6.2 % respondents rating it as “Very Negative,” 23.8% remaining neutral. This perhaps means that there is consensus that workforce competencies lead to innovation and improvement but a large populace is concerned.

In all the dimensions, majority of the respondents rated the impact of hospital workforce competencies positively with the highest positive ratings in ‘Quality of Health Services’ and ‘Innovation and improvement.’ It is important to note that there are always a few percent of respondents who gave either a negative or a neutral response to their organization’s performance

and therefore though the overall trend is good, there might be specific areas of concern that needs attention.

4.11. Discussion

The findings from **Table 4.5** show variation on the number of available health workers in Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital. In addition, the results indicated that Benadir Hospital has a higher percentage of fully functional health worker in all the categories thus better staffing level and possibly enhanced ability to deliver a wide range of healthcare services. On the other hand, only 0% of staff at Aden Abdulla Hospital is fully functional, thus they might have many issues in addressing the patients as well as managing the hospital's operation. The variation in the staffing quantitative between the two facilities could have implications to the quality of the care that is offered and firm performance; in this case, Aden Abdulla Hospital requires strategies to help towards the solution of staffing problem.

Table 4.6 this shows that Benadir Hospital has competitive advantages in a number of ways especially in admission rate, and the general efficiency of admitted out-patient and in-patient services. However, the functionality of the hospital is comparatively lower in the diagnostic services' area. Regarding functionality, Aden Abdulla Hospital has lower score as compared with other categories that may hamper the health services delivery. The increased capacity especially at Benadir Hospital may mean that they are better placed to meet patient demands while providing quality services. There is an indication of increased efficiency of diagnostic services at the Benadir Hospital; however, it is lower than the overall figure hence the potential of improving on this area to improve on the services given. According to **Table 4.7**, the level of availability of hospitals is positively viewed as impacting positively on the quality of

services, patient's satisfaction level, and efficiency. The mean scores of capacity's impact on service quality and efficiency are relatively higher since people agree that higher capacity means better outcomes in terms of services delivered and operating efficiency. Nonetheless, the low mean score on financial performance indicates that although capacity leads to an improved service quality and better satisfied patients, it does not have as much of an effect on the company's financial health. This implies that there could be special challenges to meet in regard to financial management as opposed to the general aspects of service delivery improvisation in hospital institutions.

Table 4.8 The respondents' score on the various aspects of hospital management are presented, which reveal that the leadership has been rated relatively high on vision, decision-making and communication but low on financial management and in terms of training support provided. The average scores in the financial management indicates that the respondents are hesitant on how leadership conducts financial resources. This suggests that while leadership is a strength in many contexts, organizational financial management and staff training and development, may be areas for further enhancement. Attending to these issues might yet strengthen leadership and the efficiency of the hospitals in general. **Table 4.9** shows that leadership is viewed to affect health services in terms of quality, Patient satisfaction, productivity, and management of disaster. The highest values are pointed out with the reference to the impact of leadership on patient satisfaction which underlines the significance of leadership in improving patients' experiences. However, if other indexes fluctuation is representable then we can infer that leadership, in general, has a positive effect on service improvement, though there may be variations in how leadership contributes to these changes throughout the other facets of hospital operations.

Table 4.10 indicate whereas the respondents in general confirmed that most of the financial management practices are functioning optimally as revealed by hints of clear budget plans, adequate resource mobilization and efficient revenue recovery mechanisms. At the same time, there are questions on the sufficient supplies of funds for the execution of the current investments and financial risks compensation. This means that even though financial practices are viewed in a positive manner there exists areas that if well addressed would offer long term financial solutions that would boost the improvement of hospitals. **Table 4.11** shows that financial management is regarded as having positive effects on different aspects of health service delivery such as patient care quality, staffing and facilities. Whilst there is a broad agreement with the overall ranking, several specific code scores, like the recent medical equipment maintenance and better patient access rank lower; thus, the measures of financial management can marginally tackle many dimensions of service provision. This suggest that though sound financial management enhances the quality of service delivery; detailed focused efforts might be necessary to deal with difficulties.

Table 4.12 respondents agree with the position stating that financial management has a positive influence over the quality of health services, both in terms of the patient satisfaction level, the operation speed and management of the emergency situation, as well the organization's financial situation. A greater consensus of the effect of the fiscal aspect on patient satisfaction indicates that maintaining sound fiscal policies promotes positive patient experience. Such results indicate that the analysis of the financial situation is essential for the general development of service quality and financial security. **Table 4.13** shows that respondents have a favorable attitude towards workforce competencies as perceived from staff qualification, training, communication skills and practice of the best practice. However, there are some concerns which

include leadership training to support their roles and responsibilities and multicultural training. This indicates that although there are some stock of competencies working amongst the overall workforce, there should be constant improvement in specific competencies in order to improve on the staff performance as a way of improving the patients.

Table 4.14 signifies that workforce competencies are regarded with appreciation regarding the effects on the quality, safety and operations of patient care. Highly skilled staff improve the patient outcomes, reduce the medical mistakes as well as increase innovation. Thus, the variation of the response to the opinion on the beneficial effect of competencies testifies to the fact that the effect can be contingent upon some spheres of service delivery. This emphasizes the need for the enhancement of the concept of staff development so as to obtain the maximum gains from workforce competencies. **Table 4.15** confirms that workforce competencies are considered as playing a primarily beneficial role in the health services quality, patients' satisfaction, productivity, safety, and creating new and better solutions. The greatest consensus regarding the innovation and improvement point to proficient employee's engagement towards enhancing healthcare. These result imply that building workforce competencies should be pursued in order to enhance the quality of care and promote ongoing enhancement of health service delivery.

From above, major aspects of health services delivery which are marked by the availability of health workers, leadership, better financial management, and competencies of the health workforce are acknowledged. These areas may be improved and this will result into better care, better patients' experience, hospital's performance and efficiency. Nonetheless, general population solutions and enhancements which are targeted are required in sectors like financial

management, diagnostic services, and staff development to deal with the existing issues to facilitate the overall health service delivery enhancements.

In what aspects are your hospital or healthcare organization resource-deficient or undersupplied? Some of the key informants, when asked said that the hospital did not have a blood bank, a cardiac facility, modern and advanced emergency equipment, and adequate training for some of the personnel. Further informants include; staffing, infrastructure and equipment, financial enabler; funds, medications and supplies and IT deficient. The reasons that account for deficiency of prescription drugs and less number of bed in hospital? We were also questioned. Some of the factors mentioned briefly by the key informants were “the absence of the health instrument industry and biomedical equipment firms are part of it too” and “administrative clogging and overcrowding” that others were “lacking resource, rising demand, supply chain challenges, and bed myths.”

The informants expressed after the interview that the leadership actions that can affect the health services included embodying of communication, setting goals, collaboration, and recognition, while others also noted that there is continually inadequate consistently high-quality commodification care as a top priority how do these leadership actions affect the hospital services? Another question asked during the interview was “what leaders can do to affect the team, staff, and performance”; the respondents answered that; “it can enhance patient care, staff cooperation, and staff satisfaction.” Other groups completed the question saying that it can enhance the understanding of awareness, performance management of staff, and work and mistake supervision.

Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital also shown the different ways in the management of financial, supply and the workforce, which are influenced by the funding and structure of the organizations. Benadir hospital is funded by international donors, NGOs and government and this forms the basis of various special programs such as nutrition, neonatal, TB programs and dialysis. However, this hospital uses other external sources in its funding and this makes it to struggle with fluctuating donations. For example, when a major donor such as Begs Maternal pulled out its support, the hospital was left struggling to meet its costs especially on supplies and equipment as seen through the initiation of fee charge in August 2024. However, the hospital has remained a challenge in terms of resource constraint especially in offering some services such as ECG and scans, thus, patients are forced to seek these services from other places. Financial model of Benadir Hospital is diverse, but still fragile which demonstrates the problem of unpredictable donor support in a situation when reliable and well-organized service delivery is crucial.

Another important difference is that Aden Abdulla Hospital is a private investor model hospital and this shifts the financial dynamics of the organisations. Since it is a private hospital it is owned by some investors and shareholders who aim at generating profits from the hospital. This is a market economy model where the hospital gets revenue from service charges and insurance cover hence getting constant funds to improve the infrastructure of the hospital. The rivalry among the investors to meet the needs of the hospital ensures that the supply and equipment are bought and well maintained thus reducing on service delivery gaps. Aden Abdulla Hospital on the other hand has been able to provide general and specialized services due to its investor backed financial support which is not a problem that Benadir Hospital faces. However, this approach may also have the disadvantage of potentially restricting patient's access to health

care in cases where they cannot afford to pay for the fees or lack insurance coverage, thus raising questions on the equity aspect of the hospital's financial model.

Analyzing the workforce competence in Benadir Hospital one can conclude that it is rather ambiguous. The political factors affect the hiring process of the hospital and therefore, results to a workforce with different levels of competency. Some employees are highly professional and deliver their services as expected while others are not professionally competent thus leading to inconsistencies in service delivery. The politicking that goes into hiring makes people get placed in some positions that they may not be suitable to work in, which is a problem in delivering uniform services. However, the availability of supervisors who are capable of correcting the mistakes made by the employees and assisting the inexperienced employees go a long way in treating some of these challenges. But this supervisory intervention cannot completely address the systemic problem of poor recruitment process that remains a major challenge to quality of care in the hospital.

On the other hand, Aden Abdulla Hospital has put in place a very corporate and systematic way of approaching the hiring process that is, only professional and well experienced personnel are considered. Hospital's pre-employment testing for standard practices is effective in its way of hiring only employees who can meet the expected competencies. It is fortunate that this systematic approach to recruitment is coupled with supervision and training to produce a quality workforce that is able to provide care. Furthermore, the hospital has training sessions every three months to update the employees' skills and knowledge, with special emphasis on the skills of the less qualified employees through bi-annual training. New employees are also taken through an orientation process so that they get to know the environment and standards of the hospital when

they join the hospital. Through the use of this approach in the workforce development at Aden Abdulla Hospital, the employees are well equipped to meet the various challenges that come with their jobs thus enabling the hospital to sustain quality service delivery.

The correlation tables provide complex patterns, where and how the hospital capacity, staff competency profile, training programs, communication channels, leadership, and cultural competency affect or influenced each other in delivering effective hospital's operations. Firstly, the significant and positive correlation between clinical and technical training and health care education performance currently working in hospitals as well as the continuous training courses ($r= 0. 214, p<0. 01$ $r = 0. 214, p < 0. 01$ $r= 0. 214, p<0 01$, and $r=0. 302, p<0. 01$ $r = 0$. Receiving education all the time helps the staff to be well prepared for the current challenges as resulted by correlation to the workforce competencies, problem solving skills, and sound decision making in the times of emergencies. This relationship has exemplified the importance of investment in training programs of both clinical and technical personnel in order to improve operational performance of the hospital besides the quality of care to patients.

Another group of factors relates to the communication and cooperation between the staff of the hospitals, which affects their performance levels. The results have confirmed that enhanced communication within the Health care workforce and with the patient and families is directly related to better Hospital outcomes (correlation coefficient $r=0. 205$, significant at 0. 001 level) thus underlining the focus for patient-centered care. Thus, the quality of the communication is associated with the increased compliance with the best practices and protocols, the increased rate of patients' safety and satisfaction. In addition, staff leadership competency is positively correlated to clinical hospital operation; correlation coefficients point to the fact that

leadership and management training influence the efficacy of clinical operations of the hospital ($r = 0.687$, $p < 0.01$). This means that leadership development is central in creating an organizational culture of improvement and sound decision making in hospitals.

But the impact of cultural competence training on the performances of hospitals in question shows a different picture. Positive correlation was evident between training in cultural competence and patient satisfaction and outcomes with a significance of ($r=0.545$, $p<0.01$) in contrast it is negatively associated with hospital performance ($r=-0.199$, $p<0.01$). Such findings could be interpreted as suggesting that, although cultural competence increases patients' perceived value, it does not necessarily correlate with improved organizational level performance indicators or could be indicative of difficulties in how such training is implemented in the context of an organizational setting of the hospital. This creates a scenario where hospitals have to search for a balance between compromising the cultural competency of the health care delivery system on one hand and the overall hospital organizational performance on the other hand in order to deliver optimal health care to patient as well as to deliver optimal results to the hospital organization. This means that in order to deliver a comprehensive solution to the current state of a hospital capacity and services delivery, cultural competence has to be delivered hand in hand with other areas such as leadership, communication and technical competency.

However, the results of this study hold several limitations which are as follows: Despite the insights derived from this study into the interrelated factors of hospital capacity, staff competencies, training, communication, leadership and cultural competence. However, one major weakness includes leadership assessment which has remained private or rather sensitive. Some of the limitations included lack of receipt of raw data and authentic responses from the

employees and most of them when responding on the leadership within their institutions selected politically correct answers. Likewise, some of the respondent's aspects surrounded certain sensitivity to the financial management that inevitably may have resulted in underreporting or cautious responses, which impacted the study results.

Also, some of the private hospitals such as Aden Abdulla Hospital was sensitive to the questionnaires and interviews, they at first declined to participate. Subsequently, they consented to participate only after a lot of interaction had taken place; this might have affected the truthfulness as well as the quality of the responses. Officials of the Ministry of Education and Sport also showed some reluctance in participating in the study especially when it came to filling questionnaires and interviews thus making it difficult to collect the data. Last but not the least, time as a constraint: The time that was taken to conduct the research restricted the depth at which data was to be collected and analyzed thus restricting the exhaustive conclusion that was to be made on the study. These limitations imply that there is importance of these findings that, however, should be taken with certain degree of cautions, which means that similar research with less sensitivity and more time would likely produce even more concrete results.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Introduction

Findings, conclusions and recommendations on health services delivery in hospitals are presented and discussed in chapter Five of the study. This chapter consults the results of investigations performed regarding the inadequacy of health workers, strength of health services, leadership qualities, financial efficiency, and professionalism of health workers. The analysis is meant to provide cardinal understanding of how these factors influence the quality of the offered health scopes in order to point out the problems which need improvement. Overall, it is the author's hope that by analyzing the relationships of these variables, the reader is provided with suggestions on how to improve the performance of the hospital system for the benefit of its clients.

5.2. Findings of study

5.2.1. Capacity of Hospitals

The findings of in the analysis of the table 4 are as follows., 5 at Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital researcher have encountered different respondents level of response. While 145 of them (63. 0%) from the Benadir Hospital were met to gather this information, only 65 of respondents (30. 9%) were met at Aden Abdulla Hospital. This disparity shows that Benadir Hospital have more availability respondents than Aden Abdulla Hospital which might affect the whole samples of the study whereby the samples were 210 people.

Table 4.6 shows that Benadir Hospital is functional in admitting patients and such output functions as outpatient department and inpatient department with 145 (63.0%) arguing that the

facility is fully functional. Nonetheless, the diagnostic services efficiency in the Benadir Hospital has also improved and based on the responses received it is 94 which is 44.8% fully functional and 51 which is 24.3% partly functional. And from the given table it is clearly identified that Aden Abdulla Hospital providing only 65 (30.9%) services fully functional for all type of categories. These findings show that Benadir Hospital has greater capability overall and utilization than Aden Abdulla Hospital offer a wide range of services in health quality and efficiency diagnostics services' inefficiency at Benadir Hospital. **Table 4.7** The results also demonstrate that respondents strongly agree that hospital capacity plays a tremendous role in the quality of health services, patient satisfaction, service delivery and even the ability to respond to emergencies, as given by the mean scores which vary from 3.73 to 4.40. The highest level of agreement is confirmed with the capacity regarding the improvement of the quality of the services and efficiency that points towards the idea that increased capacity in hospitals will be most beneficial for these parameters. This can be seen from the fact that while the mean score obtained for financial performance was relatively lower than the mean score obtained for non-financial performance that indicate that though the perception of capacity affecting financial stability is somewhat lower it is positive.

The study found significant differences in patient admission rates, emergency response efficiency, outpatient services efficiency, inpatient services efficiency, and diagnostic services efficiency in hospitals, rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) and accepting the alternative hypothesis (H_1), suggesting that hospital capacity affects these factors. but the Patient Admission Rates: Hence the p-Value is 0.079 which is higher than 0.05. This means that accepting the null hypothesis (H_0).

5.2.2. Leadership Evaluation

According to Table 4. 8, respondents supported the hospital leadership on the following aspects: The ability to articulate strategic directions, the speed of decision-making, the ability to address issues and be transparent. Unfavorable perception of leadership's involvement in the management of financial aspects and trainings too lacks a positive connotation as shown by the mean scores that have been neutralized. This means that, with an exception of strategic and operation where leadership is associated with positive reactions; there could be some uneasiness or mixed emotions towards a leadership responsibility on financial management for their professional development support. The results which have emerged from Table 4. 9 reveal that agreeance with the assertion that leadership improves the quality of health services, patient satisfaction, service delivery efficiency, emergency response, and financial stability with mean values of 2. 89 to 3. 53. The responses which received the highest rating involved leadership often being viewed to positively influence patient satisfaction thereby improving service delivery.

The ANOVA analysis presented Significance P value. As for the values of p as to all the leadership factors mentioned above, the values are below 0.05, that imply the differences between the hospitals with different leadership effectiveness. Therefore, we fail to support null hypothesis (H_0) but support the alternative hypothesis (H_1) in supporting that leadership has a significant influence on healthcare management.

5.2.3. Financial Management Practices

Table 4. 10 depicts that respondents affirm that the hospital has sound budget strategies, sound resource management, efficient revenue mobilization, and proliferation of revenues. Measures concerning expenditure control, ways of reducing cost, and reporting about the financial situation are also valued. There are issues of while there is adequate amount of funds for new project there seems to be issues of inadequate funds for existing projects, also the institutions seem to have issues on how best to manage financial risks. This all indicates that despite trends in general financial practices and activities as being positive, there are a few areas that require enhancement for sound financial structure and for enhancing financial backing of hospital improvements.

Table 4. Thus, based on the results in table 11, respondents confirm that good financial has positive impact on the quality of patient care and availability of staffs and structures. It was noted that the total financial problems affect the service delivery time with fewer but essential variations: the aspects, such as having modern medical equipment and the effect of finances on patient demand, represent lower scores. This means that generally financial management in health services has a positive influence but areas like equipment upgrade and patients' access could be enhanced. The results from Table 4 are shown below The results from Table 4. 12 reveal that the study participants support the notion that FM enhances health care quality, patient satisfaction, service delivery effectiveness, emergency management and financial health with a mean of 3. 22 to 3. 53. The areas with the highest level of consensus are: financial management: this of course underlines the significance on patient satisfaction and or service delivery.

All the p-values that have been obtained are less than the significance level of 0.001 for most of the financial management factors apart from cost reduction strategies where the test has a p-value of 0.290, we can infer that the financial management practices differ significantly between the two hospitals. The findings lead us to support the H_1 and fail to support the H_0 for most of the financial aspects except the cost saving where we are unable to reject the H_0 .

5.2.4. Workforce Competencies

Table 4.13 shows the respondents' opinion that the medical and technical staff of the center possesses the necessary qualification and skills, with the existing opportunities to attend continuous training. Collective work; conveying of information; use of standard precautions; and problem solving are considered by most as having a 'positive outlook. Nonetheless, there is lower consensus on leadership trainings as well as on cultural competency as the field offers opportunities for improvement for staff development and trainings. The results from table 4 above shows that., fourteen of the studies support the notion that workforce competencies enhance patient care quality, safety and gain while staff competency diminished medical mistakes and have boosted creativity. While there is consensus on these positive effects, dispersion of the reaction points to the probability of the variation of these effects across the various aspects of service provision. Table 4.15 confirms that respondents' perception towards workforce competencies is positive on the quality of health service, patient satisfaction, service delivery efficiency, safety, and innovation. The largest difference of opinion resides in the competencies and how they affect innovations and improvements in the health care system to indicate that developed staff competencies have direct effects on innovation and improvement of practices in the health care system. In general, these results underscore the importance of health

worker presence, decision-making funding, financial management, and worker skills for the components of health services. Enhancements in such areas are expected to ultimately result in better quality of services rendered to the patients, high levels of satisfaction among the patients as well as high overall efficiency in delivering hospital services.

Every component of the whole workforce competence is presented with p-values below 0.001, thus suggesting a relation to the level of workforce competence in the management of health care between different hospitals. Hence, we fail to support the null hypothesis (H_0) and we support the view in the alternative hypothesis (H_1) that workforce competence affects healthcare management.

5.3. Conclusion

In light of the findings of the assessment of the health services delivery in the analyzed hospitals, it is now possible to see different factors discussed above like health workers, leadership, finance and competency and how they interact and impact on the health systems in these hospitals. It is evident from staffing situations presented between the Benadir Hospital and Aden Abdulla Hospital that this factor plays a key role within healthcare facility. What is more important is that Benadir Hospital has got a higher percentage of staff with complete functionality which indicates that the hospital is in a better place to provide for the patient's needs and meet the desired service standards. On the other hand, similar to other health facilities in Somalia, Aden Abdulla Hospital has the following key weaknesses that affect staffing and hence the service delivery; Comparing with Aden Abdulla Hospital, Benadir Hospital has a higher bed capacity, admission capacity, outpatient capacity and, all other services it has a stronger service delivery system. The fact that the diagnosis services in Benadir Hospital have

been identified as needing enhancing means that there is area of service delivery that could be boost through interventions.

It has been determined that hospital leadership is important in improving the several performance dimensions such as service delivery, patient satisfaction, and productivity. Nevertheless, the crises arising from lack of adequate financial management and training support imply that leadership effectiveness has the potential to be even better, if specific challenges are given undue attention. The generally positive view of the financial management practices underlines their significance for the management of resources, for the receipts and the paradigm of financial reliability. However, some of these problems are, for instance, inadequate funds to fund the projects and managing risks point towards the potential for enhancing financial initiatives to support the functioning and development of hospitals. The assessment of workforce competencies in a positive manner demonstrates their major contribution to the enhancement of patients' outcomes and care quality and safety with reference to organizational effectiveness. Training and development on leadership, technical and cultural aspects ought to be done as a way of tapping the potential of a skilled workforce. Furthermore, the research results are coherent in indicating the causal relationship of sound financial position and well-developed workforce capabilities with increased service delivery quality, patients' satisfaction levels, and organizational performance. However, there are certain issues for instance equipment maintenance, and for financial challenges to be well handled, in order to enhance operational health services delivery.

In conclusion, it presents the findings that make it clear that the different factors maintain close relations in contributing to the quality of the health services. Effective staffing, efficient

financial management as well as appropriate professional development of human resources are considered as great deficiencies that need to be addressed to enhance health service delivery. In this manner, it is possible to emphasize some areas that can contribute to improving hospitals' ability to deliver better, satisfactory and efficient care.

5.4. Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance health services delivery: Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance health services delivery:

5.4.1. Improve Staffing Levels:

- **Address Staffing Gaps:** Evaluate staffing requirements in the Aden Abdulla Hospital and where necessary come up with means of obtaining fully functional personnel in the health sector. It may need the involvement of more staff, better working schedules and improving ways of keeping experienced employees.
- **Regular Staffing Reviews:** It is necessary to set specific meeting time to review the staffing levels and then make necessary changes to guarantee that both of the hospitals have enough workers to treat patients and guarantee the quality of the services delivered.

5.4.2. Enhance Service Delivery Capacity:

- **Focus on Diagnostic Services:** Increase the capacity of diagnosis at Benadir Hospital through the acquisition of better-equipment, increase training for staff diagnosis and redesigning of systems to increase efficiency.

- **Expand Service Capabilities:** Ideally, the two hospitals should also look at development ways in service delivery to mean among them increasing the number of beds, enhancing medical technology and improving the response to emergency situations.

5.4.3. Strengthen Leadership:

- **Financial Management Training:** Offer relevant and comprehensive training to leaders in all the specialized hospitals concerning financial management in an effort to enhance the manner in which the budgets are overseen; and how to address current or projected financial issues.
- **Improve Communication:** Promote the provision of information flow to and from the leadership, whereby; strategic initiatives, organizational operational changes, or surveys are relayed to all the staff or employees.

5.4.4. Enhance Financial Management Practices:

- **Develop Comprehensive Financial Strategies:** Outline sound financial strategies which explicates the financial budgets, different revenue models, and good measures of mitigating financial risks. Make sure that financial reports are frequently checked and then disclosed to all the interested parties.
- **Invest in Infrastructure:** Invest in critical medical commodities and firm upgrades needed to provide quality patient care and upgrade healthcare facility productivity.

5.4.5. Promote Workforce Competencies:

- **Ongoing Training and Development:** Continuing education for both clinical and technical personnel to enable them embrace new knowledge on technologies, leadership qualities and cultural diversity to de-pave way for improved quality health care delivery to the public.
- **Enhance Leadership Skills:** Retrain hospital leaders and managers in order to produce system-oriented and efficiency-oriented leaders who are able to change hospital's environment for the better.

5.4.6. Address Financial and Operational Challenges:

- **Mitigate Financial Constraints:** Such contingency mechanisms should be put in place to handle any financial crises so that disruptions are not evidenced across the facilities in regards to patient care and services.
- **Optimize Efficiency:** Optimize management of core hospital workforce competencies for increased efficiency, operational processes for shortening down the patient waiting time and recent practices for improving patient satisfaction.

5.5. Recommendation future research

- **Integration of Technology in Service Delivery:** As the advanced technologies in the form of telemedicine, EHRs and AI are increasingly finding application in healthcare organizations, it is worthy of further research to determine the efficiency of these technologies in enhancing the delivery of quality services in health care facilities. Research could be conducted to determine measures through which these technologies

could be incorporated into the various health organizations to improve patients' experiences and organization efficiency.

- **Patient-Centered Care Models:** Studying both the strategies in which patient centered care models are being practically applied and tested in various settings and the results attained from these tests would have been useful in enhancing the delivery of services. Possible research questions may be concerned with identification of factors that may enable or hinder the implementation of these models, especially the ones that work in low budget settings, as well as patient satisfaction and outcomes yielding from the presence of these models in the delivery of health services.
- **Leadership and Organizational Culture:** More efforts are required in an attempt to establish the relationships between leadership styles and organizational culture and the provision of healthcare services. Subsequent research can further explore the relationship between the leadership behavior and cultural influences in the healthcare organisations to the service outcomes, staff productivity and patients' satisfaction.
- **Healthcare Management in Crisis Situations:** COVID-19 demonstrated the need for sound health management particularly during disasters. Further research can be made on analyzing the strategies and models that the healthcare can attain in order to enhance service provision within cases of disasters or epidemics. Here, some of the areas to explore are the stress-tests of human and healthcare systems.
- **Quality Improvement Initiatives:** More studies should be conducted to assess the impact of different management for quality enhancement in the delivery of health care services. Research could evaluate the effectiveness of CQI programmers, lean management and

other quality improvement interventions on service delivery goals and objectives in several healthcare organisations.

- **Equity and Access to Healthcare Services:** It is pertinent to emphasize that reduction of disparities in the provision of healthcare services is crucial. More studies could examine how several elements cause disparities in the delivery and receipt of medical care in particular to the vulnerable communities. Research could also examine prevention and elimination strategies for these disparities with an overall intention of enhancing parity in provision of health care services.
- **Healthcare Workforce Management:** Healthcare workers themselves and how organizational management particularly in aspects of recruitment, retention and staff development is quite worthy of further study. In future studies, it may be possible to investigate how HCM practices affect services, such as how overall employees' productivity can be enhanced or methods of preventing burn out of the healthcare workforce.
- **Patient Safety and Risk Management:** Patient safety is a critical element in the provision of health care services. Subsequent research can potentially turn its attention toward establishing and evaluating mechanisms that can help to avoid error-related behaviors and enhance safety for the patients. Further research studies may also be conducted on the position of safety culture within health- nature and care organizations and how this impacts the provision of services.

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Appendix I. Work plan of PhD thesis

Semester/Activities	Semester I (April –Sept 2021)	Semester II (Oct 2021–Dec 2022)	Semester III (January 2023 – March 2024)	Semester VI (March 2024–Sept 2024)	Semester V (April –Oct 2023)	Semester IV (November 2024–Jan 2025)
Topic						
Problem statement						
Background						
Proposal						
Defense of proposal						
Data collection						
Report writing						
PhD thesis completion						
Defense of PhD						

Appendix II. Budget of PhD thesis

Internet cost	24months	\$20 per month	\$500
Telephone cost	36hrs 2 years	\$0.5 per hours	\$18
Transportation cost	12months	\$50 per month	\$600
Note books	4books	\$4 per note books	\$16
Pens	10pens	\$0.25	\$2.5
Questionnaire Printing cost	930pages	\$0.25 per pages	\$232
Article Publishing charges	3 articles	\$250	\$750
Final books Printing costs	4books	\$100 per book	\$500
Total			\$2,618

APPENDIX III, QUESTIONNAIRE

Title: Healthcare Management and Health Service Delivery

1. Questionnaire Objective One: Impacts of capacity of Hospital on health services Delivery -

Section 1: General Information

Hospital Name:

- a) Benadir Hospital
 - b) Adan Abdulla Hospital
 - c)
-

Demographic

characteristics

Gender

- a) Male
- b) Female

Age

- a) 20 – 25
- b) 25 – 30
- c) 30 – 35
- d) 35 – 40
- e) 40 – 45
- f) 45 and Above

Marital Status

- a) Single
- b) Married
- c) Divorced
- d) Widow/widowed

Educational Level

- a) Certificate
- b) Diploma
- c) Bachelor

d) Master

e) PhD

Occupation

a) Ministry of Health

b) Health workers

c) Patients

d) Family of Patients

e) Others

Section 2: Hospital Capacity

Availability of Medical Equipment, Facilities and services				
No	Items	Fully Functional	Partially Functional	Not Available
1.	MRI Machine			
2.	CT Scanner			
3.	X-ray Machine			
4.	Ultrasound Machine			
5.	Emergency Room			
6.	Intensive Care Unit (ICU)			
7.	Operating Theatres			
8.	Pharmacy			
9.	Cardiology			
10.	Oncology			
11.	Pediatrics			
12.	Orthopedics			
13.	Doctors			
14.	Nurses			
15.	Technicians			
16.	Support Staff			

Section 3: Health Services Delivery

No	Items	Fully Functional	Partially Functional	Not Available
1.	Patient Admission Rates			
2.	Surgery Success Rates			
3.	Emergency Response Efficiency			
4.	Outpatient Services Efficiency			
5.	Inpatient Services Efficiency			
6.	Diagnostic Services Efficiency			

Section 4: Overall Impact on Health Services

No	Items	Very Positive	Positive	Neutral	Negative	Very Negative
1.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the quality of health services delivered?					
2.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on patient satisfaction?					
3.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the efficiency of service delivery?					
4.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?					
5.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's capacity on the hospital's financial performance?					

2. Questionnaire Objective two: Impacts of Leadership of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery

Section 1: Leadership Evaluation

Please rate the following statements based on the leadership of your hospital on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = Strongly Disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree.

No		SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	The hospital leadership provides a clear vision for the future.					
2.	The hospital has a well-defined strategic plan that is effectively communicated.					
3.	The leadership makes decisions in a timely and efficient manner.					
4.	Leaders effectively solve problems and address challenges.					
5.	There is open and transparent communication between leadership and staff.					
6.	The leadership regularly provides updates and information about hospital operations.					
7.	Leadership provides adequate support for staff professional development.					
8.	The hospital invests in training and development programs for its staff.					
9.	The leadership prioritizes patient care and safety.					
10.	Leaders ensure that the hospital follows best practices for patient safety.					
11.	The leadership encourages innovation in healthcare delivery.					
12.	The hospital leadership is committed to continuous improvement.					
13.	The leadership effectively manages the hospital's financial resources.					
14.	Leaders make sound financial decisions that benefit the hospital.					

Section 2: Overall Impact on Health Services

No	Item	Very Poor	Poor	Neutral	Good	Very Good
1.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the quality of health services delivered?					
2.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on patient satisfaction?					
3.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the efficiency of service delivery?					
4.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?					
5.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's leadership on the hospital's financial performance?					

3. Questionnaire Objective three: Impacts of Financial Management of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery

Section 2: Financial Management Practices

Please rate the following statements about the financial management practices of your hospital using the options provided:

No	Item	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	The hospital has a clear and detailed budget plan.					
2.	Resources are allocated efficiently according to the hospital's needs.					
3.	The hospital has effective revenue collection systems in place.					
4.	There are diverse sources of revenue for the hospital.					
5.	Expenditures are tracked accurately and regularly.					
6.	The hospital implements cost-saving measures without compromising quality.					
7.	Financial reports are generated regularly and shared with relevant stakeholders.					
8.	There is transparency in the hospital's financial transactions.					
9.	The hospital invests in essential medical equipment and infrastructure.					
10.	There are adequate funds for ongoing projects and hospital improvements.					
11.	The hospital has strategies in place to manage financial risks.					
12.	Contingency plans are available for financial emergencies.					

Section 3: Impact on Health Services Delivery

Please rate the following statements regarding the impact of financial management on health services delivery using the options provided:

No	Item	SD	D	N	A	SA
1.	Effective financial management has improved the quality of patient care.					
2.	Financial constraints do not compromise patient care.					
3.	Patients have better access to health services due to sound financial management.					
4.	There are no significant delays in service delivery due to financial issues.					
5.	Adequate financial resources ensure sufficient staffing levels.					
6.	Staff receive timely salaries and benefits.					
7.	The hospital maintains up-to-date medical equipment due to good financial practices.					
8.	Infrastructure improvements are regularly made to enhance service delivery.					
9.	Financially sound management practices have led to higher patient satisfaction.					
10.	Patients are generally satisfied with the cost of services provided.					

Section 4: Overall Impact of Financial Management

No	Items	Very Poor	Poor	Neutral	Good	Very Good
1.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the quality of health services delivered?					
2.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on patient satisfaction?					
3.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the efficiency of service delivery?					
4.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the hospital's ability to respond to emergencies?					
5.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's financial management on the hospital's financial stability?					

4. Questionnaire Objective four: Impacts of Workforce Competencies of Hospitals on Health Services Delivery

Section 2: Workforce Competencies

Please rate the following statements regarding the competencies of your hospital workforce on a scale from 1 to 5, where 1 = Strongly Disagree and 5 = Strongly Agree.

o	Items	D				A
1.	The medical staff have the necessary qualifications and skills to provide high-quality care.					
2.	Continuous training and education programs are available for clinical staff.					
3.	The technical staff are proficient in operating medical equipment and technologies.					
4.	Technical staff receive regular training on new equipment and technologies.					
5.	The hospital workforce demonstrates effective communication skills with patients and families.					
6.	There is good communication and teamwork among hospital staff.					
7.	The staff adhere to best practices and protocols for patient safety.					
8.	Workforce competencies positively impact patient care quality.					
9.	The staff are capable of making sound decisions in critical situations.					
10.	Problem-solving skills are emphasized and developed among the workforce.					
11.	The hospital has effective leadership and management training programs.					

12.	Leadership skills among the staff contribute to efficient hospital operations.					
13.	The workforce is trained to provide culturally sensitive care.					
14.	Cultural competence training improves patient satisfaction and outcomes.					

Section 3: Impact on Health Services Delivery

Please rate the following statements regarding the impact of workforce competencies on health services delivery using the options provided:

No	Items	SD	D	N	A	SA
	Workforce competencies have improved the quality of patient care.					
2	Competent staff ensure adherence to clinical guidelines and standards.					
3	High workforce competencies contribute to better patient safety outcomes.					
4	Staff competencies help in reducing medical errors and adverse events.					
5	Efficiency of Service Delivery					
6	Competent staff enhance the efficiency of hospital operations.					
7	Workforce competencies lead to reduced waiting times for patients.					
8	Patient satisfaction is higher due to the competencies of the hospital workforce.					
9	Competent staff provide better patient education and support.					
	Competent staff drive innovation in healthcare practices and services.					
	Continuous improvement initiatives are supported by workforce competencies.					

Section 4: Overall Impact of Workforce Competencies

No	Item	Very Poor	Poor	Neutral	Good	Very Good
1.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on the quality of health services delivered?					
2.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on patient satisfaction?					
3.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on the efficiency of service delivery?					
4.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on patient safety?					
5.	How would you rate the overall impact of your hospital's workforce competencies on innovation and improvement?					

INTERVIEW SECTIONS only Supervisors/Directors/ Managers/Minister workers

Objective 1, Interview of the capacity of healthcare facilities on service delivery

1. What are the less resources / insufficiency resources in your hospital?
2. What factors lead to a shortage of medication, and fewer beds?

Objective 2, Interview of healthcare Leadership on service delivery

3. What leadership activities affect both personnel and healthcare services in your hospital?
4. How do these leadership activities affect hospital services?

Objective 3, Interview of financial funding on service delivery

5. Where are the Sources of financial support of the hospital?
6. Did do purchase and maintained supplies or equipment's that hospital service needed prompt?

Objective 4, Interview of influence of workforce competence on service delivery

1. How is the employee knowledge and skills on their work toward standard practices?
2. Did you do any developments concerning about employees work?

All Thanks to Allah